

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

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Soil threats and soil ecosystem services
of interest in SERENA

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Abstract

This report from task 2.2 of the EJP SOIL SERENA project presents definitions, information and indicators related to soil threats, soil ecosystem services (SES) and their bundles relevant for European member states. A significant part of the work consisted in finding common harmonised definitions for the soil threats and ES between the 16 participating European member states in SERENA. Based on these harmonised definitions, a prioritisation of soil threats and SES was done by each member state. This resulted in an overall ranking of the soil threats and SES in order from high to lower interest for SERENA. The soil threat 'Loss of soil organic carbon' and the SES 'Soil organic carbon and Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration' were scored with the highest priority. Finally, an additional translation was done from technical English to a non-soil-expert language for each soil threat and SES. This translation and the prioritisation of the soil threats and SES will be evaluated by the SERENA stakeholders in WP1 of the SERENA project. The selection of specific indicators and the assessment of thresholds for the soil threats and SES of interest in SERENA will be done by WP2 T2.3.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

BAU	Business as usual
BSQI	Brussels Soil Quality Index
CICES	Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services
COP	conference of the parties
EEA	European Environment Agency
ES	Ecosystem service
ESADC	European Soil Data Centre
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
GHG	Greenhouse gases
ITPS	Intergovernmental Technical Panel on Soil
JRC	Joint Research Centre of the EU comission
LDN	Land degradation neutrality
LUCAS	Land use and land cover survey
OM	Organic matter
SDG	sustainable development goals
SES	Soil ecosystem service
SICS	soil-improving cropping systems
SOC	soil organic carbon
SOM	soil organic matter
SSM	sustainable soil measures
UNCCD	United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification
WP	work package

1. Introduction

This report describes the selection of soil threats and soil ecosystem services (SES) of interest in the EJP SERENA project and their associated indicators. It is the result from task 2.2 of the SERENA project.

The objectives of SERENA are:

- to enhance policy effectiveness through the analysis of SES bundles across European agricultural landscapes,
- to highlight how soil threats impact the supply of SES bundles through adoption of a set of site-specific thresholds.

Task 2.2 is central in SERENA and derives information from task 2.1 and task 3.1. The results in this report are of highest interest of task 2.3, task 3.2 and task 5.1 (Figure 1-1).

Figure 1-1 The embedding of task 2.2 in SERENA

The objective of T2.2 as described in the SERENA proposal:

“Objective 2.3 is dealt with by T2.2 and T2.3: to provide a list of soil threats and soil-based ES of interest for the SERENA project, with the indicators and threshold/reference values to evaluate them. Several soil threats have been defined by the European Thematic Strategy for Soil Protection and the Global Soil Partnership, and a lot of ecosystem services using soil quality data are defined in the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES). Nevertheless, depending on the local agro-pedo-climatic conditions over Europe, Member States may be concerned by local specific threats and/or soil-based ES. The objective is here to select both a minimum list of common

threats and soil-based ES (in collaboration with WP1) to be evaluated by each partner for a general comparison over Europe (with close links to WP3 and WP5), and a larger list which can be dealt with only by some specific partners. Specific indicators used by Member States or common indicators and threshold/reference values which could be used extensively will be specified, in accordance with previous EJP SOIL stocktakes (from EJP SOIL WP2, EJP SOIL WP6 or SIREN)”.

Task 2.2 contributes to this objective by providing a ranking of soil threats and SES in order of interest for the SERENA project both for each individual country as for all the participating countries together. In addition, definitions, information, associated indicators and translation to non-soil-experts for each soil threat and SES can be found in this deliverable of T2.2. The selection of specific indicators and the assessment of thresholds for soil threats and SES of interest in SERENA will be done by WP2 T2.3.

Resources from other tasks of the SERENA project

The definitions of soil threat, SES and their bundles as well as what is an indicator have been derived from the SERENA D2.1 (van den Elsen et al., 2022) in task 2.1:

- **Soil threats** are processes that could degrade (some of) the functions of soils and the services that soils provide.

Adapted, after EJP Soil Glossary (2022)

- **Soil Ecosystem Services** is the soil-related subset of Ecosystem Services, directly and quantifiably controlled or provided by soils and their chemical, physical and biological properties, processes and functions.

Adapted, after Paul et al. (2021)

- **A bundle of soil threats and SES** is a set of ecosystem services, soil threats, or the combination of the two, that appear together repeatedly in time or space, as related to a specific context.

Adapted, after Potschin-Young et al. (2018).

- **an indicator** as a soil quality indicator which is “A single or a set of variables chosen to represent or infer a specific object of interest. Indicators can be measured using analytical protocols, estimated through modelling or expert-based approaches and they can be quantitative, semi-quantitative or qualitative”.

From Kandziora et al.(2013).

A stocktake of existing studies, maps, models and indicators related to soil threats and SES was done in WP3 T3.1 of the SERENA project (Michel, 2022). All ten soil threats according to EU and FAO were considered. M3.2 concluded that none of the soil threats were investigated in all project member states. The soil threat most often studied was **soil erosion**. Further, seven SES were considered in the questionnaire. In accordance with the soil threats, none of the SESs were investigated in all member states. The SES most often evaluated were **primary and biomass production** and **greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration**. Finally, eight member states evaluated different types of bundles were considered. For details, please see M3.2 of SERENA (Michel, 2022).

Workflow

The starting list of soil threats and SES was taken from SERENA task 3.1 and one soil threat (soil drought) was added in the process. However, common definitions of the soil threats and SES were missing. Therefore, we discussed the definitions among project member states which resulted in the harmonised common scientifically definitions presented for each soil threat and SES in this report.

Afterwards, a translation of these definitions, indicators and the relevance of each soil threat or SES were translated to non-soil-experts so that they are also useful and understandable by politicians, spatial planners, farmers, ... who may use different terminology, and may not have a deep understanding of soil processes, but, nevertheless, need thematic soil maps and indicators to make decisions that go further than only the soil.

Besides indicators for specific soil threats and SES, this task investigated if some 'super' indicators can be formulated by combining different soil threats and SES, to provide means of evaluating bundles and their dynamics (Haines-Young et al., 2012).

Finally, the project partners of the SERENA project made a prioritisation for their country of the most important soil threats and SES to be discussed within the SERENA project. This resulted in an overall ranking of soil threats and SES based on the prioritisation done in 16 European countries. The results of the current report will be discussed among the WP1 SERENA stakeholders as the stakeholder needs form a core pillar of the SERENA project. A more detailed workflow of this D2.2 report is given in Appendix A 3.

Structure of the report

To begin with, this report gives a brief overview of contextually related documents including EU policy and previous selected European and international soil projects. In the subsequent chapters we go into depth on soil threats, SES and bundles with their definitions and associated indicators. In the last chapter, we describe the methodology and results of the selection/prioritisation of soil threats and SES over the 16 participating countries of the SERENA project member state level as well as some summary remarks of the interrelation between soil threats and/or SES as well as their indicators.

2. Information from reports and other projects

2.1 EU Soil Strategy for 2030

The European Soil Strategy for 2030 (European Commission, 2021a) is the set of directions for the Member States to keep and restore soils' health. The main goal is to achieve good soil health by 2050. This ambitious goal can be fulfilled by medium-term goals that were set to be achieved by 2030.

The European Commission emphasizes that 60 to 70% of EU soils might not be healthy. This is caused by the multiple threats leading to degradation processes, such as erosion, compaction, a decline in organic matter, pollution, loss of biodiversity, salinization, and sealing. This damage is caused mostly by human activity, especially irresponsible and unsustainable soil management.

Linking the long-term objectives by 2050 to the soil threats and SES, European Commission assumed to reach no net land take (to decrease soil sealing and soil compaction) and reduce the soil pollution to a minimum (the level that is not harmful to human health and the environment). Taking into account the value of ecosystem services provided by cropland and grassland (EUR 76 billion per year) the goals become even more important to achieve.

According to the European Commission, healthy soils provide as many of the following ecosystem services as possible (European Commission, 2021a):

- ***provide food and biomass production, including in agriculture and forestry;***
- ***absorb, store and filter water and transform nutrients and substances, thus protecting groundwater bodies;***
- ***provide the basis for life and biodiversity, including habitats, species, and genes;***
- ***act as a carbon reservoir;***
- ***provide a physical platform and cultural services for humans and their activities;***
- ***act as a source of raw materials;***
- ***constitute an archive of geological, geomorphological, and archaeological heritage.***

To achieve all the objectives European Commission proposed a list of solutions, directions, and pressing problems of the European soils. First of all, soils are the solution to the key environmental problems in Europe. They play an important role in climate regulation and can reduce the rate of climate change (for example peatland restoration can significantly reduce the CO₂ emission). Soils will also help to create a resource-efficient and circular economy through reusing excavated and devastated soils, limiting land take and soil sealing, storing nutrients, and closing the carbon cycle. Another important aspect is that healthy soils maintain a high level of biodiversity to keep the plant, animals, and human health. This could be achieved also by storing clear, pollution-free water (groundwater and surface water in peatlands). All these functions and ecosystem services can be reduced by the multiple soil threats. Due to the changing climate and anthropic pressure, most soils in Europe are endangered. Hence, sustainable soil management and soil monitoring are key to minimalizing soil degradation (European Commission, 2021a).

The drivers and impacts of soil degradation know no borders. An uneven and fragmented response by Member States to tackle soil degradation has led to an uneven playing field for economic operators who have to operate under different rules on soil protection while competing in the same market. The fragmented response has also prevented the halt of soil degradation in the EU and its effective restoration.

The Strategy announces that the Commission will table a new legislative proposal on soil health to ensure the same level of protection to soil that exists for water, the marine environment and air in the EU. Such a legislative initiative will be based on an impact assessment, including a subsidiarity check, and fully respect the better regulation requirements and the competences of Member States.

Currently, the Commission is working on this legislative proposal namely the **Soil Health Law** to address transboundary impacts of soil degradation, secure equal market conditions, promote policy coherence at EU and national level and thus be able to achieve the EU goals on climate change, biodiversity, food security and safety, and water protection. This Soil Health Law is foreseen for 2023. It aims to contain:

- definitions,
- indicators for soil health,
- requirements for sustainable soil use,
- a target for the reduction of nutrient losses,
- a passport for excavated soil and a soil health certificate,
- identification, registration and remediation of contaminated sites,
- monitoring of soil health, reporting on progress.

2.2 Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe'

The mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' aims at putting Europe on a trajectory towards sustainable soil management and soil restoration as part of a wider, green transition in rural and urban areas (European Commission, 2021b). The Mission is at the heart of the Green Deal.

As a basis for reporting, the mission proposes to use a set of eight soil health indicators to assess current status and track changes. These indicators will serve as a basis for discussion with Member States. If sampled correctly (e.g. not after a fertiliser application) they provide stable indicators for soil health at a given time and of change if repeated at permanent locations.

1. Presence of soil pollutants, excess nutrients and salts. When present in higher concentrations than allowed by health regulations or plant requirements: soils are unhealthy. A reduction in levels below recognized threshold values indicates an improvement in soil health.
2. Soil organic carbon. Organic matter is important for adsorbing nutrients, retaining water and for improving soil structure and workability of soils as well as plant productivity. Soil organic carbon (SOC) is a major constituent (56%) of soil organic matter and the global soil organic carbon reservoir of soils is two to three times bigger than the carbon as atmospheric CO₂. Therefore, an increase in SOC concentration and stock allows drawing down CO₂ from the atmosphere and an improvement in soil health.
3. Soil structure including bulk density and the absence of soil sealing and erosion. Good soil structure as indicated by reduced bulk density, the absence of soil sealing and erosion allows for healthy root growth, reaching all parts of the soil and allowing infiltration of rainwater to prevent runoff and soil loss.
4. Soil biodiversity. Presence of functional diversity of appropriate bacteria and fungi and of soil animal communities that are important for soil functions and services, such as soil structure, litter decomposition, organic carbon storage and nutrients cycling promotes all soil functions. Currently, nematodes and earthworms are well tested. Ongoing research will soon deliver indicators for soil microbial parameters.
5. Soil nutrients and pH. Essential nutrients for plant growth in part at least, derived from soils include N, P, K, S, Ca. A range of plant micro-nutrients usually found at very low concentrations (parts per million) in soils may limit plant growth, such as boron (B), chlorine (Cl), cobalt (Co), copper (Cu), iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), molybdenum (Mo) and zinc (Zn). Soil pH affects many chemical and biological processes, including plant nutrients availability and the balance and functions of soil microbial communities. In farmland and forestry soils, an optimal balance is required for growth. In supporting biodiversity-rich ecosystems, nutrient limitations provide an essential set of sub-optimal conditions to support a diversity of biota above and below-ground.
6. Vegetation cover. The annual duration and diversity of the vegetation cover and its net primary productivity is essential for soil health, providing nutrients for soil biodiversity and carbon inputs to soil organic matter, also reducing erosion and surface runoff. A more diverse and long duration cover indicates conditions favourable to soil biodiversity and health and increasing vegetation cover is also valuable for urban settings.
7. Landscape heterogeneity, including farmland (field size, fragmentation, presence of natural green elements), forestry (types of forest, monocultures, clear-cuts with bare land) and urban green infrastructures (adequate presence). The diversity of landscape elements (composition) and the way these elements are distributed, including their relative size and their location in relation to the morphology (configuration) strongly influence biodiversity, the water cycle and soil erosion.
8. Area of forest and other wooded lands, classified by the number of species, the share of non-native tree species, and the proportion of natural and artificial regeneration. In forests, soil

health is influenced by the naturalness in terms of species composition and the management practices, including disturbance by clear cuts.

Note that measurements are soil-specific showing characteristically different ranges of values for different soil types, land uses and climate zones. Methods for capturing information, which can be combined in different ways, include: visual assessments in field; soil sampling with professional laboratory analysis; remote sensing; modelling, crowd sourcing and citizen science. Many methods are already well described but need standardising if time series are to be robust.

The implementation plan of the mission ‘A Soil Deal for Europe’ has eight specific objectives which are presented in Table 2-1 with their associated targets, baselines and indicators.

Table 2-1 The Soil Mission’s specific objectives, targets and proposed soil health indicators

Objectives	Mission targets in line with EU and global commitments	Baseline (see 8.A)	Soil health indicators
1.Reduce land degradation relating to desertification	T 1.1: Halt desertification to help achieve land degradation neutrality and start restoration ----- In line with SDG 15.3	25% of land in Southern, Central and Eastern Europe at risk of desertification.	All eight soil health indicators
2.Conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks	T 2.1: Current carbon concentration losses on cultivated land (0.5% per year) are reversed to an increase by 0.1-0.4% per year T 2.2: the area of peatlands and wetlands losing carbon is reduced and the natural sink is significantly increased to help meet GHG reduction targets by 2030 and the Climate law goal by 2050. ----- In line with the Fit for 55 Climate Energy Package (Climate Law, revised LULUCF regulation) and the Paris Agreement 4 per mille initiative.	Area of land with low and declining carbon stocks = 23%. Area of degraded peatland = 4.8%	Soil organic carbon stock Vegetation cover
3.No net soil sealing and increase the reuse of urban soils	T 3.1: increase urban recycling of land beyond 13% and switch from 2.4% to no net soil sealing as a contribution towards meeting the target of no net land take by 2050. ----- In line with Roadmap to a resource efficient Europe, and Biodiversity Strategy including upcoming nature restoration targets	Area of land affected by soil sealing = about <1% of EU, but can be as high as 2.4%, Current rate of recycling of urban land for development: 13%	Soil structure (incl. soil bulk density, absence of soil sealing, erosion and water infiltration) Vegetation cover
4.Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration	T 4.1: reduce the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50% and the use of more hazardous pesticides by 50% T 4.2 reducing fertilizer use by at least 20% T 4.3: reduce nutrient losses by at least 50% T 4.4: 25% of land under organic farming T 4.5: Reduce microplastics released to soils to meet 30% target of zero pollution action plan T.4.6 Halt and reduce secondary Salinization All to be achieved by 2030 to contribute to meeting the target by 2050 that soil pollution is reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems. ----- In line with the Biodiversity strategy, the Farm to Fork Strategy and the Zero Pollution Action plan.	27% - 31% of land with excess nutrient pollution Soil contamination: 2.5% (non-agricultural), 21% (conventional arable), ca. 40-80% of land from atmospheric deposition depending on the pollutant. Farmland under organic agriculture: 8.5% (2019)	Presence of soil pollutants, excess nutrients and salts

<p>5.Prevent erosion</p>	<p>T 5.1: reduce the area of land currently affected by unsustainable erosion from 25% to sustainable levels</p> <p>-----</p> <p>In line with the Roadmap to a resource efficient Europe</p>	<p>Area of land with unsustainable soil water erosion is 25%, with 70% of this being agricultural land.</p>	<p>Soil structure, absence of soil sealing, erosion and water infiltration</p> <p>Vegetation cover</p> <p>Landscape heterogeneity</p> <p>Forest cover</p>
<p>6.Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops</p>	<p>T 6.1: Reduce compaction of soils to go significantly below current levels of 23% - 33%</p> <p>-----</p> <p>As for forest soils: in line with the new EU Forest Strategy</p>	<p>Area of land with critical levels of soil compaction = 23-33%, 7% of which is outside agricultural area.</p>	<p>Soil structure, absence of soil sealing, erosion and water infiltration.</p> <p>Vegetation cover</p> <p>Landscape heterogeneity</p>
<p>7.Reduce the EU global footprint on soils</p>	<p>T 7.1: Establish the EU’s global soil footprint in line with international standards</p> <p>T 7.2: The impact of EU’s food, timber and biomass imports on land degradation elsewhere is significantly reduced without creating trade-offs</p> <p>-----</p> <p>In line with the Zero Pollution Action Plan</p>	<p>Baseline to be created by mission activities</p>	<p>Food, feed and fibre imports leading to land degradation and deforestation</p>
<p>8.Increase soil literacy in society across Member States</p>	<p>T. 8.1: awareness of the societal role and value of soil is increased amongst EU citizens, including in key stakeholder groups, and policy makers</p> <p>T. 8.2: soil health is firmly embedded in schools and educational curricula, to enable citizens’ behavioural change towards the adoption of sustainable practices both individually and collectively.</p> <p>T 8.3: citizen involvement in soil and land-related issues is improved at all levels</p> <p>T 8.4: practitioners and stakeholders have access to appropriate information and training to improve skills and to support the adoption of sustainable land management practices.</p>		<p>All eight indicators (on a long term)</p>

Current management practices result in, approximately, 60-70% of EU soils being unhealthy, with a further, as yet, uncertain percentage of soils unhealthy due to poorly quantified pollution issues. A radical change in current land management practices is both feasible and necessary. Soils will also benefit from improvement to indirect drivers of change such as reductions in air pollution and carbon emissions. The main reasons for unhealthy soils are direct nutrient inputs in agricultural systems (excluding air pollution issues), declining carbon stocks, peatland degradation, soil erosion, soil compaction, soil contamination, soil sealing and secondary salinization.

2.3 Soil Monitoring in Europe. Indicators and thresholds for soil health assessment (EEA)

The European Environment Agency (EEA) draft report “Soil monitoring in Europe. Indicators and thresholds for soil health assessments” (EEA, 2022a) synthesises the current knowledge about key soil indicators in the light of current and new policies in support of healthy soils. The report considers the 8 main soil threats (soil organic carbon loss, soil nutrients status, soil acidification, soil contamination, soil biodiversity loss, soil erosion, soil compaction, soil sealing) listed in the EU Soil Thematic Strategy. The soil threats wind erosion and salinization are not considered in the report.

The impact of each threat on key SES was analysed and information on indicators used to assess soil threats was collected. In addition, the report compiles relevant information on indicator threshold values and proposes a conceptual framework for assessing soil degradation based on the assumption that exceeding an indicator threshold value triggers action.

The report shows that the existing systems for assessing soil degradation in Europe are not easily comparable and require harmonisation and additional research in this field. In particular, it is recommended that definitions of indicators, methods of analysis and sampling and threshold values be harmonised and agreed at the level of individual EU countries.

The authors selected 12 soil quality indicators (Table 2.2) in view of their appropriateness to assess soil degradation (unhealthy soils) related to various important soil functions or ecosystem services. For most cases, the selected indicators are well established, data availability is, at the European level, at least acceptable and they are appropriate to describe key soil degradation types and impairment of key soil services. With a healthy, undegraded soil, in full capacity of its expected functions, none of the thresholds for these indicators would be exceeded.

The authors recommend for the future:

- the filling of remaining gaps (e.g., indicators for water storage, soil biological indicators, wind erosion)
- improvement of regional validity of thresholds
- representativity of indicators and thresholds by land use (since existing threshold do not cover all land use types).

Table 2-2 Overview of soil threats and indicators investigated in the EEA draft report

Table 10-1: Overview of soil threat indicators investigated in this report

Note: The current knowledge base covers a limited set of land uses and soil properties, for which thresholds are available; in the future, all relevant land uses and sites need to be covered.

Soil threat	Indicator	Thresholds	Comment
Soil organic carbon loss			
Cropland	Falling below optimal SOC	Light: < 1.2 [% SOC] Medium: 1.2-1.9 Heavy: > 1.9	SOC/Clay ratio (Johannes et al., 2017) optimum SOC content as 10% of the clay content/vulnerability limit
Nutrients loss			
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	NH ₃ in air: 1 – 3 [mg NH ₃ m ⁻³] NO ₃ in ground water: 50 [mg NO ₃ l ⁻¹] N in surface water: 1.0 to 2.5 [mg N l ⁻¹]	Mineral N: sum of available NH ₄ and NO ₃
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C/N ratio	C/N 20-25 leakage from forests: 1 [mg N l ⁻¹]	Forest floor organic layer
Agriculture	Falling below of optimal phosphorus	P concentration 25-35 (optimal P fertility class)	Extractable P concentration < optimum (value range refers to Mehlich 3-ICP; also available: P-Bray P1 and Olsen P)
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N/P ratio	N/P ratio > 18 (coniferous forests) N/P ratio > 25 (deciduous forests)	Forest floor organic layer

Acidification			
<i>Agriculture</i>	Exceedance of critical pH levels	1. pH < 4.5 - 4.7 (critical) 2. pH < 5.0 - 5.5 (avoid)	1. Risk of Al toxicity 2. Limited availability of Ca, Mg, K and P
<i>Forest land</i>	Exceedance of critical inorganic Al levels	base cation (Bc)/aluminium ratio = 1 (0.5-2.0)	Bc = Ca+Mg+K
Soil pollution			
<i>All land uses</i>	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals and organic pollutants	Updated values for Cd, Cu, Pb and Zn [mg/kg] in this report - by country - data base developed (Cd, Cu, Pb, Zn, As, Hg, Ni, Cr) - organic pollutants:	Country-specific values vary broadly and are not necessarily comparable Stratification by land use and soil texture
Soil erosion			
<i>Agriculture</i>	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2 [t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹] for shallow soils (< 70 cm depth) 4 [t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹] for deeper soils (>= 70 cm) ^{*)} (soil loss tolerance)	Soil formation rate: 0.3 to 1.4 t/ha/yr (Verheijen et al. 2009) Preliminary thresholds, derivation of site-adapted tolerable soil loss rates recommended The current indicator description in this report only includes soil erosion by water, whereas the threshold addresses all other erosion types.
Soil biodiversity loss			
	Loss of soil biodiversity (subindicators)	to be developed: (a) Exceedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation (b) exceedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	Requires sub-indicators by species and/or (functional) group
Soil compaction			
	Harmful subsoil compaction (subindicators)	Priority (sub) indicators: Saturated hydraulic conductivity (Ks) < 10 [cm/d] Air capacity (AC) < 5 [%]	Exceedance of "action values" (Zink et al. 2011) Secondary subindicators with available thresholds: bulk density, internal soil strength, air permeability and oxygen diffusion
Soil sealing			
	Sealed area per land total area	National targets to achieve No Net Land Take	

^{*)} Loss rates lower than 2 t/ha/yr shall be mandatory on soils adjacent to water bodies, and/or soils with elevated levels of pollutants; such lower limits are needed to maintain water quality.

2.4 Stocktaking for Agricultural Soil Quality and Ecosystem Services Indicators and their Reference Values (SIREN project)

The EJP SOIL WP3 project SIREN (2021-2022) aimed to identify and review national approaches to make use of soil data in the assessment of SES, and identified knowledge gaps and development needs that prevent policy implementation as experienced in the 20 countries participating in the SIREN consortium (Faber et al., 2022).

In doing so, a comprehensive conceptual framework linking soil quality to ecosystem services has been implemented through the review of scientific literature by unifying various concepts associated with soil quality and ecosystem services. This was done by asking project member states to fill a questionnaire to evaluate the way they use Soil Quality indicators to evaluate SES. They were asked to express soil indicators which are used in the evaluation of some specific ecosystem services, together with the type of associated SES indicator and, if possible, its reference values. But not specific list of SES was provided during SIREN, and the MS were free to answer as they want, even if the CICES classification was available for use and recommended if relevant.

The questionnaires consisted in a huge list of names for SES, some of them being close to the CICES proposition, other being far from the CICES classification. In order to compare them, ontology was needed to try to classify them into a short and consistent list, even if, without any definition of SES, the creation of a category was difficult. In

Table 2-3 the names of SES given by the project member states are listed in the column "Synthetic name of soil-based ES", together with the associated new ontology as "Super-group of ES", and the "Direct beneficiaries", who can be either the "whole society", or the farmer. "Equivalent SES of in SERENA" is also provided in the table, for comparison purposes.

In addition, to support this framework, a glossary of consistent terminology has been created to define what is meant by: indicator, soil processes, soil functions, ecosystem approach, ecosystem services, nature's contributions to people (NCP), potential supply of ecosystem services, ecosystem service flow, ecosystem capacity, ecosystem health, soil quality and soil health, reference or reference value, target value, and natural capital.

SIREN produced a synthesis of policy-relevant soil quality indicators with high potential for harmonised application in national and European monitoring based on literature, international policy, international stakeholder opinions, wide application in national soil monitoring and EU projects contributing to agricultural soil quality assessment.

Table 2-3 Proposition of an ontology of ecosystem services based on the EJP SOIL SIREN project questionnaires. The blue items represent ecosystem services consistent with the CICES classification

Super-group of ES	Synthetic name of soil-based ES	Equivalent SES in SERENA (when relevant)	Direct beneficiary	Country	Name of soil-based ES in each country	
Biomass production	Biomass production	Primary/Biomass production	Farmer	Czech Republic	1.1.1.1 - Cultivated crops	
				Estonia	1.1.1.1 - Cultivated terrestrial plants (including fungi, algae) grown for nutritional purposes	
				Finland	1.1.1.1 - Cultivated terrestrial plants (including fungi, algae) grown for nutritional purposes	
Other provisioning services	Mineral substances used for nutritional purposes	Abiotic provision of material	Society	France	Biomass production	
				Ireland	Primary productivity - grass biomass production	
	Blue Water provision	Hydrological control (1)	Society	Slovakia	Provisioning, biomass-food	
				Estonia	1.1.1.3 Cultivated plants (including fungi, algae) grown as a source of energy	
	Nutrient cycling or provision to crops	Hydrological control (1)	Farmer	Czech Republic	4.3.3.1 - Mineral substances used for nutritional purposes	
				Czech Republic	4.3.1.2 - Mineral substances used for material purposes	
	Provisioning services to crops	Water provision to crops	Hydrological control (2)	Farmer	Portugal	4.2.2.1 - Ground (and subsurface) water for drinking
					Portugal	4.2.2.2 - Ground water (and subsurface) used as a material (non-drinking purposes)
		Water quality regulation	Hydrological control (1)	Society	Czech Republic	4.2.1.2 - Surface water used as a material (non-drinking purposes)
					France	Blue Water provision
Climate regulation		Greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration	Farmer and society (depending on the spatial and time scales)	France	Nitrogen provision to crops	
				Ireland	Nutrient cycling	
Regulation of Soil Quality		Environmental pollution control	Farmer and society (depending on the spatial and time scales)	Ireland	Regulation of nutrients provision	
				Ireland	Regulating of nutrient provision	
Soil attenuation of waste		Environmental pollution control	Farmer and society (depending on the spatial and time scales)	Ireland	P delivery	
				Ireland	K delivery	
Soil erosion control	Erosion control	Farmer and society (depending on the spatial and time scales)	France	Water provision to crops		
			France	Water availability		
Cultural use of land	Biodiversity conservation	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Society	Italy	Water storage and infiltration rate	
				Ireland	Water quality regulation	
Biodiversity conservation	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Society	Czech Republic	2.2.1.3 - Water flow regulation	
				Ireland	2.2.1.3 - Hydrological cycle and water flow regulation (Including flood control, and coastal protection)	
Biodiversity conservation	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Society	Estonia	2.2.1.3 - Hydrological cycle and water flow regulation (Including flood control, and coastal protection)	
				Italy	Hydrological cycle regulation	
Biodiversity conservation	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Society	Czech Republic	Flood control	
				Slovakia	Natural Hazard regulation	
Biodiversity conservation	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Society	Finland	Nutrient retention and consequent impacts on water bodies	
				Latvia	Surface water quality	
Biodiversity conservation	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Society	France	Water quality regulation	
				France	Climate regulation (links to C storage and Greenhouse gases mitigation)	
Biodiversity conservation	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Society	Ireland	Climate regulations - carbon cycling and storage	
				Finland	Regulation of carbon stocks	
Biodiversity conservation	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Society	Ireland	Climate sequestration	
				Slovakia	Regulation of climate, atmospheric regulation	
Biodiversity conservation	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Society	Italy	Climate regulation	
				Czech Republic	2.2.4.1 - Weathering processes and their effect on soil quality	
Biodiversity conservation	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Society	Estonia	2.2.4.2 - Decomposition and fixing processes and their effect on soil quality	
				Czech Republic	2.2.4.2 - Decomposition and fixing processes and their effect on soil quality	
Biodiversity conservation	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Society	Portugal	2.2.4.2 - Decomposition and fixing processes and their effect on soil quality	
				Czech Republic	5.2.2.1 - Maintenance and regulation by inorganic natural chemical and physical processes	
Biodiversity conservation	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Society	Denmark	5.2.2.1 - Maintenance and regulation by inorganic natural chemical and physical processes	
				Lithuania	Regulation of Soil Quality	
Biodiversity conservation	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Society	Portugal	2.1.1.2 - Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes - Filtration/sequestration/storage/accumulation by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals	
				Portugal	2.2.1.1 - Control of erosion rates	
Biodiversity conservation	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Society	Estonia	2.2.1.1 - Control of erosion rates	
				Slovakia	Erosion regulation	
Biodiversity conservation	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Society	France	Soil stabilisation and control of erosion	
				Italy	Erosion control	
Biodiversity conservation	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Habitat for biodiversity (2)	Society	Czech Republic	Physical use of land in different environmental settings	
				Ireland	Biodiversity	

Recommendations of the SIREN project:

- Do not to limit 'soil health' to the functions and associated SES dealt with in SIREN, but to cover a full range of SES to promote the prevention of potential trade-offs, including cultural ESs, and facilitate soil management to support broad bundles of ESs. Indicators for cultural ES are missing and, in order to promote social equity in sustainable land use, it is recommended take into consideration the concepts of ES versus Nature's Contributions to People (NCP).
- In order to facilitate SES assessments in soil research and make the results comparable, harmonization of SES terminology and indicators will be necessary.
- In the scope of soil monitoring, will be necessary developing a modular system of soil quality indices based in packages associated to individual STs and bundles and trade-offs of SESs (a tiered system). These packages should be developed for a minimum dataset to harmonize pan-European soil monitoring.
- Regarding SES assessment, common expert judgement approaches should be replaced by robust ecological production functions. Moreover, soil monitoring and SES assessment would require to be synchronized in space and time.
- Early involvement of stakeholders together with the adoption of indicators and target value for soil quality derived from policy objectives of common, will provide profit to the soil monitoring program.
- Biological indicators are missing in most European countries but this is not due to the lack of importance of tracking, targeting and conserving soil biodiversity.

Relevancy of this project for SERENA

Compared to the SERENA list of SES, some are largely studied by MS involved in SIREN, especially "Primary/biomass production", "Greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration", and "Erosion control". The "Hydrological control" is interpreted in 3 sub-ES, say "Water provision to crops", "Blue water provision" and "Hydrological cycle and water flow regulation / Flood and hazard control". The SES "Environmental pollution control" may correspond to both SIREN "Regulation of Soil quality" and "Soil attenuation of waste".

Truly, SERENA has profited from the main results of the SIREN project that have been summarized above. In addition, SERENA is in perfect continuity and relationship with SIREN since all the research questions and issues that remained open at the end of the SIREN project are the basis of development and many of the objectives of SERENA.

2.5 LANDMARK project

The LANDMARK project was a European project on the sustainable management of land and soil in Europe, which ran with 22 partners from 2017 to 2019 as part of Horizon 2020. The website is: <https://landmarkproject.eu/>

The LANDMARK project provides a LANDMARK glossary with many useful definitions: <https://landmark2020.eu/landmark-glossary/>.

Within the LANDMARK project, soil quality is defined as “the degree to which a soil can perform its soil functions”. Following the Functional Land Management approach (Schulte et al., 2014), the LANDMARK project refers to the five main soil functions with corresponding definitions:

- **Primary productivity**

The capacity of a soil to produce plant biomass for human use, providing food, feed, fiber and fuel within natural or managed ecosystem boundaries (Sandén et al., 2019)

- **Water purification and regulation**

The capacity of a soil to remove harmful compounds from the water that it holds and to receive, store and conduct water for subsequent use and the prevention of both prolonged droughts and flooding and erosion (Wall et al., 2020).

- **Climate regulation**

The capacity of a soil to reduce the negative impact of increased greenhouse gas (i.e. CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O) emissions on climate (Van de Broek et al., 2019)

- **Soil biodiversity and habitat provisioning**

The multitude of soil organisms and processes, interacting in an ecosystem, making up a significant part of the soil’s natural capital, providing society with a wide range of cultural services and unknown services (van Leeuwen et al., 2019)

- **Nutrient cycling**

The capacity of a soil to receive nutrients in the form of by-products, to provide nutrients from intrinsic resources or to support the acquisition of nutrients from air or water, and to effectively carry over these nutrients into harvested crops (Schröder et al., 2016).

This approach entails that all soils perform these five functions simultaneously, but both the extent and the relative composition of this functionality depends upon the interaction of three factors: soil (pedological, physical, chemical and biological properties), environment and management.

The LANDMARK project had three main pillars and outcomes:

- Pillar 1 (local scale): The Soil Navigator - A decision support system for assessing and optimizing soil functions (soilnavigator.eu, (Debeljak et al., 2019).
- Pillar 2 (regional scale): A soil functions monitoring schema for the range of soil functions associated with different soil types, land-uses and European major climatic zones.
- Pillar 3 (EU scale): EU policy options for functional land management to optimise the sustainable use of Europe’s soil resource.

Conclusion of the project

The project indicated five main soil functions, which can be seen as most important to assess and describe soil functioning. Unlike previous projects that emphasised threats, this work focussed on the functional capacity of soils taking into account the five key functions delivered ubiquitously across agricultural landscapes – productivity, water regulation and purification, climate regulation, nutrient cycling and biodiversity. The magnitude of the suite of soil functions is governed by intrinsic soil properties interacting with environment and management. Vrebos et al. (2021) proposed indicators to evaluate the performance of each soil function. The DayCent model was used to build crop-specific Bayesian networks that were used to assess performance and trade-off between the soil functions under current conditions. For each soil function, the maximum potential was estimated across the EU and changes in trade-off assessed. Hence indicators of relevance to assess soil functions have been developed through this work. However, indicators were used to assess soil functions, thus a singular indicator may only partially represent the extent of functionality.

Remaining/open (research) questions

In particular, soil biodiversity was most indirectly measured owing to the data limitations and availability of soil biodiversity for modelling and mapping purposes. How to assess/measure this remains challenging. A review of soil monitoring systems highlighted that no current national or European monitoring system exists which has the capacity to quantify the five soil functions and therefore evaluate multi-functional capacity of a soil and in many countries no data exists at all. van Leeuwen et al. (2017) called for the addition of soil biological and some physical parameters within the LUCAS-soil survey at European scale and for further development of national soil monitoring schemes.

Relevancy of this project for SERENA

The LANDMARK project gives 5 main soil functions that can be relevant for the SERENA project. The supply of soil functions varies regionally due to soil, environment and management with maximisation of individual soil functions highlighting different patterns of impact on other soil functions. In many cases, favouring or maximising a singular function can generate a negative impact in many cases. Further work should seek to elucidate the variability of soil functions due to the regionalisation associated with difference in soil, environment and management. Context specific ranges that can account for differences would allow for a more targeted approach to manage soil health at relevant scales. Not all soil functions can be maximised everywhere due to the trade-offs that occur and so balanced optimisation pathways that enhance soil health should be explored.

2.6 Preventing and Remediating degradation of soils in Europe through Land Care (RECARE)

RECARE Project was a research initiative to develop effective soil degradation prevention and remediation solutions across Europe. It involved 27 partners during the period from 2013 – 2018. <http://www.recare-hub.eu/>

The project aimed to:

- fill knowledge gaps in our understanding of the functioning of soil systems under the influence of climate and human activities;
- develop a harmonized methodology to assess the state of soil degradation and conservation;
- develop a universally applicable methodology to assess the impacts of soil degradation upon soil functions and ecosystem services;
- select, in collaboration with stakeholders, innovative measures, and evaluate the efficacy of these regarding soil functions and ecosystem services as well as costs and benefits;
- upscale results from 17 case studies to European scale to evaluate the effectiveness of measures across Europe;
- evaluate ways to facilitate adoption of these measures by stakeholders;
- carry out an integrated assessment of existing soil related policies and strategies to identify their goals, impacts, synergies and potential inconsistencies, and to derive recommendations for improvement based on RECARE results;
- disseminate project results to all relevant stakeholders.

The soil threats taken into account were:

- soil erosion by water,
- soil erosion by wind,
- decline of organic matter (OM) in peat,
- decline of OM in mineral soils,
- soil compaction,
- soil sealing,
- soil contamination,
- soil salinization,
- desertification,
- flooding and landslides,
- decline in soil biodiversity.

For each specific soil threat the following topics were discussed:

- description and definition of the soil threat and processes involved,
- state of the soil degradation by each soil threat,
- drivers/pressures (including climate, human activities, policies) for the occurrence of each soil threat,
- key indicators of the soil threat and methods for their assessment,
- effects of the soil threat on other soil threats and on soil functions.

A chapter is dedicated to the concepts of soil functions and ecosystem services and a review of the current scientific debate. This chapter provided the basis for the development and selection of appropriate methods for measuring, mapping, evaluating, communicating and negotiating with stakeholders the services obtained from the soil with the ultimate aim of improving land management (Stolte et al., 2015).

Finally, the last chapter provides the state of soil degradation in Europe, soil threats and the impact of the main drivers (climate, policy and socio-economic conditions) on soil threats. The interaction between soil threats is also analysed, which provides information on bundles of soil threats that can be expected. Methods/procedures are also provided for assessing soil degradation using key soil properties. For this purpose, a list of key indicators and/or proxies for the different soil threats is provided along with (for comparison) those of the ENVASSO project (Huber et al., 2008).

Relevancy of this project for SERENA

Given the scope of the SERENA project, the result of the RECARE project that is most relevant is the framework developed in the Work Package 2 (Base for RECARE data collection and methods), which provided an improved overview of existing information on soil threats and degradation at the European scale.

Further, RECARE gave an overview of the impact of the analysed soil threats on soil functions and ecosystem services.

2.7 ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT OF SOIL FOR MONITORING (ENVASSO)

The ENVASSO Consortium, comprising 37 partners drawn from 25 EU Member States, succeeded in reviewing existing soil inventories, monitoring programmes, soil indicators and criteria that could serve as a base for a soil monitoring system for Europe. Project was funded as Scientific Support to Policy (SSP) under the European Commission 6th Framework Programme (Contract 022713, 2006-8) from 2006 – 2008 (ENVASSO, 2008).

Main objective was to define and document a soil monitoring system for implementation in support of a Soil Framework Directive, aimed at protecting soil in the EU.

Interesting for SERENA ENVASSO reported on the existing soil inventory and monitoring systems in the EU Member States and evaluated the extent to which existing soil monitoring networks adequately represent European soil typological units, land use/cover, specific soil criteria - such as soil organic carbon, bulk density, heavy metal contents - and existing spatial assessments of threats to soil such as soil erosion, compaction and desertification.

The ENVASSO consortium reviewed currently available soil indicators and criteria (Huber et al., 2008), and existing soil inventories and monitoring programmes in the EU Member States (Arrouays et al., 2008b, 2008a). A database system to capture, store and supply soil profile data was designed and programmed (Baritz et al., 2008), and procedures and protocols were defined and fully documented (Jones et al. 2008). Several of these procedures were also evaluated in pilot studies (Stephens et al., 2008), and a design for a European Soil Monitoring System was described (Kibblewhite et al. 2008).

Regarding soil indicators, ENVASSO identified three priority indicators for nine different soil threats identified by the European Commission (Huber et al. 2008). The main focus was on state, pressure and impact indicators, and the main criteria for selection were indicator significance, methodological soundness, measurability and policy relevance. Some of the selected indicators are chemical, physical and biological soil quality indicators such as soil organic carbon and carbon stock, concentration of heavy metals, sulphur and nitrogen, electrical conductivity, bulk density, diversity of earthworms and collembolans, and microbial respiration.

2.8 Intergrated planning tool to ensure viability of grasslands (LIFE Viva Grass)

Through encouraging ecosystem-based planning and economically viable grassland management the project (2014 – 2019) aimed to support the maintenance of biodiversity and ecosystem services provided by grasslands in Lithuania, Latvia and Estonia. Furthermore, the project demonstrates opportunities for multifunctional use of grasslands and grassland ecosystem services as a basis for sustainability and for sustainable development of rural areas (<https://vivagrass.eu/ecosystem-services/valuation-of-ecosystem-services/>)

Project actions

- **Grassland ecosystem service assessment** at the selected case study areas
- Development of **the integrated planning Tool** (the Viva Grass Tool) by addressing socio-economic matter in nature conservation policies;
- **Analysis of the national policies and regulatory** framework in the Baltic States
- **Development of pilot scenarios for long-term grassland management;**
- **Capacity building on applying the Tool** for the relevant target groups and operating the Tool at national, regional, municipal, protected areas and farm level.

LIFE Viva Grass project encompasses the three Baltic States and nine case study areas and consequently, the construction of a basemap faced large differences in data availability. European-scale maps such as CORINE land cover do not offer the level of spatial and thematic detail required to link, in a spatially explicit way, grassland classes with the ES they provide. On the other hand, the basic national LULC maps differ substantially from one country to the other in terms of their thematic scales. Therefore, a common grassland typology was created in order to provide the basis for the ES mapping and assessment in LIFE Viva Grass Project.

The Viva Grass Tool provides spatially explicit decision support for landscape and spatial planning and sustainable grassland management.

Viva Grass Viewer is the basic module of the Viva Grass Tool accessible to the general public. The viewer aims to visualise the results of mapping and assessment of ES supply potential, as well the grouping of ES in bundles and interaction of ES in agro-ecosystems. Viva Grass viewer intends to serve informative and educational purposes. Users are able to get acquainted with ES approach, its representations, spatial representation of basic logic behind assessment of ES and their spatial interaction.

Contextual data layers available in Viva Grass Viewer are farmland land use, supply potential of selected ES, bundles and tradeoffs of ES supply potential and cold/hot spots of ES supply potential. Regards to land block of interest, users can view supply potential of ES in selected field. For informative and educational purposes users can change land use type to view changes in supply potential due to land use change. Supply potential of ES is the contextual data layer that allows users to explore mapping and assessment results of selected ES by choosing one in a drop-down menu.

Relevance for SERENA

In this project policy and regulation objectives as well as data of soil properties and SES of grassland for the three Baltic countries were compiled and possessed. This first cross-national experience of defining and displaying bundles of SES of grassland soils is held by SERENA partners.

2.9 Soil Care for profitable and sustainable crop production in Europe (SoilCare)

The H2020 project SoilCare aimed to identify soil-improving cropping systems (SICS) that are sustainable and profitable (Hessel et al., 2022). To do this potential SICS were selected and implemented for testing in 16 study sites distributed throughout Europe, in collaboration with stakeholders. Within these study sites SICS were investigated to determine whether they resulted in improved sustainability and profitability, using indicators. The project started off with a review of literature looking at SICS (Oenema et al., 2017) with the general aim to improve soil quality and SICS with the specific aim to combat certain soil threats. This resulted in a list of indicators that could be used to assess the capacity of the soil to produce biomass (Table 2-4) and a list of indicators suitable for soil threats (Table 2-4).

Table 2-4 Possible soil quality indicators and related measurable soil properties for assessing the quality of soil for crop production (based on Oenema et al., 2017)

Indicator of soil quality	Measurable soil properties
Soil water retention and delivery	Soil depth, mean groundwater level, soil moisture retention curve, bulk density
Soil nutrient retention and delivery	pH, bulk density, SOM, extractable ions (N, P, K, Ca, Mg, S, CL, Cu, Zn, Co, Mn, Fe, Mo), soil texture
Soil-borne pathogens & soil biodiversity	Earthworm diversity (number of species), Collembola (springtail) diversity (number per species), microbial respiration, parasitic fungi, parasitic nematodes, DNA sequencing
Soil-borne weeds	Germination of weeds (number m ⁻²), stubborn weeds
Soil structure and tilth	Size of soil aggregates, shape and stability aggregates, water infiltration rate
Soil pollutants	Extractable heavy metals, organic micro pollutants, oil residues and metals from actinide series, plastics, antibiotics
SOM content and quality	Total C, mineralizable C, extractable C&N, C/N ratio

Table 2-5 Main soil quality indicators and related soil properties for assessing the effectiveness of soil threat specific SICS (from Oenema et al., 2017).

Soil threat specific SICS	Soil Quality indicator	Measurable soil properties
1 Acidification	Change of acid neutralizing capacity (mol. ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	Sum of basic cation minus sum of anions
	Change of soil pH	pH (H ₂ O), pH (KCl), pH (CaCl ₂)
2 Erosion	Loss of soil (ton ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	Mass of soil (via wind / water)
	Soil surface phenomena	Visual observation
	Aggregate stability of surface soil (%)	Aggregate stability
3 Compaction	Soil cohesion	Shear strength
	Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	Bulk density
	Water infiltration rate (mm day ⁻¹)	Water infiltration rate
4 Pollution	Penetration resistance (MPa cm ⁻²)	Penetration resistance
	Metal content (mg kg ⁻¹)	Cd, Pb, Cr, Zn, Cu, As contents
	Organic pollutants (µg kg ⁻¹)	PACs, PCBs
	Radiation pollution (beq kg ⁻¹)	Actinides
	Oil (mg kg ⁻¹)	Oil
	Plastics (mg kg ⁻¹)	plastic
Antibiotics (µg kg ⁻¹)	Antibiotics	

5	Organic matter decline	Total organic C (g kg^{-1})	Organic C
		Mineralizable C ($\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$)	Mineralizable organic C
		C/N ratio	C/N ratio
6	Biodiversity decline	Earthworms diversity (number per species)	Number per species
		Collembola (springtails) diversity (number per species)	Number per species
		Microbial respiration ($\text{mg CO}_2\text{-C m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$)	Respiration
		Parasitic fungi (m)	
		Parasitic nematodes (number per species)	Number per species
7	Salinization	Extractable salt contents (mg kg^{-1})	Na, K, Cl, SO_4^{2-} , HCO_3^-
		EC (mS)	Electric conductivity
		pH	pH (H ₂ O), pH (KCl), pH (CaCl ₂)
		Soil structure (descriptive)	Soil structure
8	Flooding	Period and number of days year ⁻¹	Flooding
		Regional drainage (canals, dams, pumping stations)	Descriptive
9	Landslides	Tree density (number m ⁻²)	Number of trees
		Drainage (canals, rivers)	Descriptive
10	Desertification	Change in green cover (ha yr^{-1})	Surface mapping
		Water infiltration rate (mm day^{-1})	Infiltration rate

These lists were input to other parts of the SoilCare project, and a selection of a smaller number of indicators to be used for evaluation of SICS was made (Alaoui et al., 2022) to assess the effects of SICS on soil quality, profitability and sustainability. The evaluation framework was based on monitoring environmental dimension (physical, chemical and biological soil properties, see Table 2-6, socio-cultural dimension and economic dimension. Indicators were used in a decision tree to be able to use a combination of quantitative and qualitative data, and to be able to give different weights to different indicators (Alaoui et al., 2022).

Table 2-6 Indicators used for the environmental dimension in SoilCare

physical	Infiltration Aggregate stability Bulk density Penetration resistance
chemical	Mineral nitrogen SOC pH
biological	Earthworm density Crop yield Yield quality Crop cover characteristics Pests Root diseases Weed diseases

3. Soil Threats and their indicators

3.1 General

Soil threats are processes that could degrade (some of) the functions of soils and the services that soils provide.

(Adapted from EJP Soil Glossary, 2022)

This chapter gives an overview of the different soil threats and their indicators discussed in SERENA. Some of the soil threats respond rapidly with minor or great on- or off-site changes (e.g. soil erosion, compaction, soil sealing), whereas others evolve slowly over time (e.g. soil organic carbon loss, loss of diversity, soil acidification). The different scales across time and space makes some soil threats appear more severe as others for the farmer and society. Nevertheless, they are all a threat to biological, chemical or physical properties and processes of agricultural soil.

Several of the soil threats listed will also be addressed in the deliverable 6.5 of task 6.3 of WP6 of the general EJP SOIL project namely the deliverable “Guidelines for accounting and mapping agricultural soil carbon, fertility and degradation changes at different scales”.

The following subchapter starts with a common harmonized definition of the specific soil threat followed by information about the soil threat and remarks that were expressed by some project partners related to the soil threat in their country. The definitions were held from literature and thoroughly discussed and harmonised among projects partners. It is namely extremely important that we have in the SERENA project a common understanding of the soil threats and their indicators in order to exchange data and experiences with stakeholders at every level all over Europe. In a second part of each subchapter associated indicators to the soil threat are listed. In a third part, the soil threat is translated to non-soil-scientists. Finally, each subchapter ends with the interrelation with other soil threats or SES. The prioritisation of the soil threats is not part of this chapter but is the subject of chapter 6.3.

Figure 3-1 Moring at the field (© Ungaro, F. n.a.)

3.2 Soil erosion (water, wind, tillage)

Definition, information and remarks about soil threat

Definition

Soil erosion is a soil degradation process consisting of the detachment, disintegration and transport of soil particles by erosive agents, such as water (water erosion), wind (wind erosion), ploughing (erosion by tillage) or ice (glacial erosion).

(From Spanish Society of Soil Science, n.d.)

Information

Soil texture, relief, land cover and meteorological conditions have an impact on the extent of erosion events. Management events can be either a source of or a solution to erosion. The reviewed studies most frequently describe water erosion, either measured or modelled.

As soil erosion by water is an important source of sediment in water, it is important to take also in account sediment transport by water. Some key voluntary actions were expressed by the European Commission concerning Healthy soils for clean water:

- Improve soil-sediment-water nexus
- Guidance on sustainable management of sediment
- Better integrate soil and land use management in the River Basin Management Plans

Remarks

Within the surveyed countries, soil erosion has been quite frequently studied and is mostly regarded as a regional or local soil threat (hilly regions). In the Mediterranean countries, as stressed by Portugal, soil erosion by water is a big concern. The trend towards shorter and more intense rainfall exacerbates the problem. Water erosion is more severe when periods of drought are broken by intense rain falling on bare or poorly vegetated and steeply-sloping soil surfaces. Also, soil erosion by water may occur in irrigation agriculture.

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

The EJP SOIL SCALE project 'Strategies for connected landscape elements to reduce water erosion' focuses on water erosion. SCALE focus on modelling and connectivity and mitigation scenarios but does not intend to calculate an indicator for soil erosion.

Indicators

The indicator is soil loss in tons per hectare ($t\ ha^{-1}$) mostly within a time frame (yr^{-1})

Soil loss $t\ ha^{-1}$ or $t\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$

This indicator for soil erosion is already calculated with existing data in the majority of the countries. However, it is not clear for which type(s) of soil erosion this indicator is calculated (water, tillage, wind or a combination). And it is not obvious whether it concerns actual or potential soil erosion.

In addition, in different countries the use of soil erosion indicators is often limited to specific types of erosion:

- Water, wind and/or soil tillage: Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, the Netherlands, Spain
- Water and/or wind: Austria, Ireland
- Water erosion: Belgium, France, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain
- Coastal erosion (sea coast, river coast): Latvia

- Not specified: Hungary
- In Belgium also sediment transport over land as a consequence of soil erosion is considered.

It must be clear for which type(s) of soil erosion indicators will be developed. We propose to consider the following sub-indicators for soil erosion:

- Soil loss by water erosion:
 - This is the most common indicator of soil erosion. The USLE or RUSLE equation is mostly used.
- Soil loss by tillage erosion.
 - Tillage erosion is the down-slope displacement of soil through the action of tillage. The process was recently identified as an important factor in the study of soil erosion (GOVERS et al., 1994; Lindstrom et al., 1992; Lobb et al., 1995; Montgomery et al., 1996; Poesen et al., 1997; Quine et al., 1999; Turkelboom et al., 1997; Van Muysen et al., 1999), of soil constituent and amendment dispersion (Kachanoski et al., n.d.; Monreal et al., 1995; Quine et al., 1996) and for quantifying spatial variability in soil quality for agricultural lands (Marques da Silva and Soares, 2001). Soil translocation is often expressed as the average length of displacement, which is equivalent to the volume of translocated soil per unit width of tillage divided by the depth of tillage. It is also expressed as a mass by multiplying the translocation volume by the bulk density of the tilled layer (Lobb et al., 2001).
- Soil loss by wind erosion.
 - Four types of indicators have been used by practitioners to support quantitative and qualitative assessments of wind erosion and blowing dust. These indicators include: 1) soil properties; 2) exposure to potentially erosive winds; 3) land health attributes based on observations and local/expert opinion; and 4) blowing dust occurrence and air quality measures (Webb et al., 2020).

Indicators on European and global level:

- ESDAC (<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/themes/indicators-soil-erosion>)
 - Mean soil erosion rate by water ($\text{ton ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$)
 - Share of agriculture area (%) under severe erosion:
- EU Soil Mission: Prevent erosion (1 of the 8 mission objectives)
 - Implementation Plan: reduce the area of land currently affected by unsustainable erosion from 25% to sustainable levels
- EEA: Actual rate of soil loss by water erosion ($\text{ton ha}^{-1} \text{y}^{-1}$)
- Global soil partnership: Global Soil Erosion Map (GSEMap): guidelines under construction
 - Water erosion
 - National water erosion map (showing erosion rates)
 - 5 water erosion factor maps (with associated uncertainty maps): rainfall erosivity, soil erodibility, slope-length, soil cover, and practice factors
 - Wind erosion
 - National wind erosion map (showing erosion rates)
 - 5 wind erosion factor maps (with associated uncertainty maps): weather, erodibility, crusting, roughness, and crop factors
 - Tillage erosion
 - National tillage erosion map (showing erosion rates)
 - 3 tillage erosion factor maps (with associated uncertainty maps): tillage erosivity, landscape erodibility and land erodibility

Translation to non-soil scientist/specialists

Due to soil erosion soil is lost from agricultural land. Soil erosion is a natural process defined as the wearing away of soil particles from the top layer of soil due to water, wind, ploughing and/or ice.

Soil erosion is measured and reported as amount (in kg or tons) of lost soil for a given area (ha) and often for a specific time (year).

Soil erosion has a large impact on both the environment and society, both on-site and off-site. On-site, soil erosion can result in the loss of the most fertile topsoil, decrease of organic matter content, loss of seeds and seedlings and increased costs of management (e.g. to remove erosion features like rills and gullies). In extreme cases this may lead to an irreversible loss of farmland, for example if the whole topsoil is eroded, which is a risk mainly for shallow soils. Off-site, soil erosion by water can cause severe damage by mud flows blocking roadways and inundating buildings, (European Commission, 2021b) filling of reservoirs and flooding. The sediment that enters the rivers can have a large impact on shipping. For wind erosion, off-site damage can include e.g. sand blasting, burial of crops and filling of small waterways. According to the (European Commission, 2021b) 24% of the land has unsustainable water erosion rates. The main factors that influence erosion are soil texture, soil cover, the amount and intensity of rainfall, wind and the concentration and the downflow of water on slopes. Even though this is a process which is mostly natural, it is often aggravated by human activities.

Interrelation with other soil threats or SES

Topsoil mostly has the highest content of soil organic carbon, edaphons and nutrients and is most exposed to erosion. When eroded, there are implications for other soil threats and SES like loss of soil organic carbon, nutrient imbalance and loss of diversity. For instance, it has been shown, that earthworm richness and abundance have an effect on soil erodibility values in European Soil Data Centre (JRC, 2018).

According to Stolte et al. (2015) the following soil threats are affected by soil erosion: SOM/SOC decline, contamination, salinization (for wind erosion), desertification, flooding and loss of soil biodiversity. Further, soil organic carbon loss, salinisation, contamination, compaction, sealing, loss of diversity and loss of the capacity of soil as habitat can all increase the likeliness of soil erosion (Stolte et al., 2015).

Figure 3-2 Soil erosion after a stormwater event (@ Foldal, C. 2021)

3.3 Soil organic carbon loss

Definition, information and remarks about soil threat

Definition

Soil organic carbon loss is defined as a process of decreasing soil organic carbon stocks or content of specific soil layers.

This definition is applied to different soil depth and time-intervals. For soil organic carbon (SOC) content mostly, the topsoil is considered. Considering SOC stocks both topsoil as well as soil depth up to 100 cm are common (FAO et al., 2017)^[OBJ].

Information

According to Global Soil Partnership (FAO) soil organic carbon (the carbon stored in soil organic matter) is crucial to soil health, fertility and ecosystem services, especially food production – making its preservation and restoration essential for sustainable development. SOC loss has been one of the most researched soil threats during last decade(s) (Stolte et al., 2015). Additionally, SOC decline has been identified as a threat in many general policy-related documents (i.e EU Soil Mission, Soil Thematic Strategy, Soil Framework Directive proposal; (European Commission, 2021b, 2006a, 2006b)).

Recent attention to SOC (e.g SOC stocks and their changes) has increased due to rising concentrations of atmospheric CO₂ (IPCC, 2019) and it is estimated to be both a threat and an opportunity to help meet the targets of the Paris Agreement, European Green Deal (European Commission, 2019) and European Soil Strategy for 2030 (European Commission, 2021a). The decline of SOC has been recognised a major threat for sustainable soil management because of the pivotal role played by the associated organic matter on many soil functions, like food and biomass production, storage and filtering, biological habitat and gene pool, etc (Stolte et al., 2015). Organic matter is an important component of soils due to its influence on soil structure and stability, water retention, cation exchange capacity, soil ecology and biodiversity, and as a source of plant nutrients (Huber et al., 2008).

It is estimated that C stock in soils from terrestrial ecosystems has decreased (Lal, 2004) with a significant decline of peatlands and their SOC status (Hooghoudt et al., 1960; Hutchinson, 1980). Since peat soils are one of the major SOC stocks in the world (Köchy et al., 2015) different aspects and the impact of peatland management in agriculture should be carefully analysed (Lehtonen et al., 2022; Rawlins, 2008). It is estimated that in the EU(27) the potential loss of C stock in peat soils in agricultural use is larger than the potential sequestration in mineral soils (Stolte et al., 2015). Furthermore, it is emphasized that sequestration of C in mineral soils is limited and potential reversible (Chung et al., 2010, 2008; Stolte et al., 2015). SOC sequestration and loss have been commonly analysed separately for mineral and peat soils (Heikkinen et al., 2022; IPCC, 2003; Stolte et al., 2015; Tanneberger et al., 2021).

As the New European Soil Strategy assumes, to control the loss of SOC, through the LUCAS soil surveys, EU-wide harmonised monitoring of the evolution in soil organic carbon content and carbon stocks will be provided. To prevent further negative changes, regular harmonized monitoring of soil organic carbon content and SOC stock evaluation must be carried out at the EU and local or regional level. In task 6.3 of the EJP SOIL project, a comparison is done between national/regional soil datasets and the European LUCAS dataset. During the 2022 LUCAS sampling, double samplings are

done both following the LUCAS as the national/regional protocol in order to be able to compare the results of national/regional and the LUCAS soil monitoring. In addition, maps of SOC stocks and SOC based on LUCAS and national/regional datasets are compared. Especially for soil organic carbon, this will provide us with necessary information about the influence of the sampling protocol and the allocation and density of sampling points of different soil monitoring networks in Europe on the conclusions about SOC content and stocks across Europe.

In line with the EU Green Deal objectives, Horizon Europe and its thematic clusters, the area of carbon sequestration and the preservation of carbon stocks have been prioritised also in research and innovation activities (European Commission, 2021c). In Farm to Fork strategy, carbon farming initiative under Climate Pact is recognised as a green business model for land managers. Furthermore, the European Commission has proposed to develop a regulatory framework forward the standardisation of monitoring, reporting and verification methodologies for carbon farming (EC, 2020a).

Remarks

Considering the definitions of SOC loss in SERENA, many of the countries do not have nationally accepted legal and/or scientific definitions on soil threats. Therefore, the definitions could be the interpretation of commonly used practice. Some of the countries have considered generalised definition of SOC loss as the decrease of soil organic carbon. Many of the countries defined soil organic carbon loss using an indicator of SOC stock or SOC content. Some countries have remarked that several indicators (i.e SOC stock as well as SOC content) are used in practice to evaluate soil organic carbon loss and that both indicators give an indication of different aspects of the soil threat soil organic carbon loss. SOC loss is frequently studied in nearly half of the countries participating in the current task of SERENA. Slightly fewer countries have indicated that there are some studies of SOC loss whereas only Portugal considered this threat as hardly studied on a national scale so far. There was no information provided for 3 countries.

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

INSURE is looking specifically at peat soils. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/insure>

TRACE-Soils aim to identify the mechanisms underpinning trade-offs and synergies of soil carbon sequestration, greenhouse gas emissions and nutrient losses in agricultural soils across Europe, and propose climate-zone specific indicators and measures to mitigate trade-offs. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/trace-soils/>

CarboSeq tries to quantify and map the potential carbon sequestration in soils. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/carboseq>

STEROPES exploits remote sensing for SOC monitoring, mapping and assessment, while ProbeField tests field spectroscopy for this purpose. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/steropes>

MIXROOT-C and **MaxROOT-C** value the plant roots as the source of SOC. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/mixroot-c> & <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/maxroot-c>

Road4Schemes is focused on the evaluation of various carbon farming practices. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/road4schemes>

Indicators

More than half of the countries participating in the current task of SERENA have considered **SOC concentration** (% or g/kg) as an indicator in evaluation of SOC loss whereas 1/3 of countries assess SOC decrease as the change of **SOC stock** (t/ha). Some of the member states have referred to SOC concentration as well as SOC stock as an indicator used for SOC analysis. Since both indicators refer to a different aspect of SOC loss, consideration of including them both in SERENA is outlined.

From the task literature review at global, European and regional scale, **SOC stock** (t/ha) and **SOC content** (% or g kg⁻¹) have been reported as the most represented SOC loss indicators. Other SOC loss indicators from reports and guidelines are as follows: **SOM content** (%), **humus content** (%), **land use change**, **decedance of optimal SOC** (%), **clay/SOC ratio** and **SOC sequestration potential** (t/ha).

The RECARE Project summarized key indicators on the decline of SOC in peat soils and concluded that above other potential indicators **peat stocks** are the most suitable for describing SOC decrease. Although topsoil **SOC content** (%) and **SOC stocks** (t/ha) are also described as potential indicators, Stolte et al. (2015) conclude that these may not be suitable for peat soils since there is no harmonised methodology of what should be considered as topsoil. In addition, SOC stock is the most relevant indicator for peat soils as it links to GHG emissions. Oxidation of peat may not result in a decrease of SOC content but rather in a decrease of the thickness of the peat, which is better expressed by SOC stock than by SOC content. Most appropriate indicators for evaluating SOC status in mineral soils are proposed as **topsoil SOC content** (%) and **SOC stocks** (t/ha). It is concluded that the **C:N ratio of the topsoil** (%) is a suitable SOC quality indicator whereas human-induced causes of SOC change were **land cover change** (km²), **wild fires** (km²), **crop residues burning** (km²), **exogenous organic matter additions** (t/ha) and **organic farming** (%) (Stolte et al., 2015).

Conserving SOC stocks is one of the Soil Mission objectives. The specific indicators described in the mission's Implementation Plan are **SOC stock** and **vegetation cover** in targeting SOC increase by 0.1-0.4% per year and reducing the area of peatlands and wetlands losing carbon accordingly (Soil Mission 2021; European Commission, 2021b). In the indicator assessment of SOC, the European Environmental Agency has reported variations of **SOC content** (%) in topsoil across Europe. European Soil Data Centre have assembled datasets of SOC with the indicators of **SOC stocks** and **SOC content** (%) of topsoil. Also, **GHG fluxes** and **N₂O emissions** for Europe have been presented. Additionally, FAO and ITPS (2018) represent the first Global Soil Organic Carbon Map (GSOCmap) with **SOC stock** (t/ha) in topsoil at global scale (FAO, 2022a).

Different aspects (incl. uncertainties) of SOC loss indicators should be considered. In terms of SOC (%), there are several methods used (i.e Dumas, wet chemistry, NIRS, LOI), however considering SOC stock, the variability of input parameters increases disparities between countries. Huber et al. (2008) concluded that there is great uncertainty in data collection for harmonised SOC stock analysis. Although measurements of SOC content are available from national soil inventories and soil monitoring data, bulk densities are often estimated using average values or statistical relationships (pedotransfer functions) with other available parameters. Variations in soil depths and bulk densities have been pointed out also in peat stock calculations (Huber et al. 2008). In addition to the difference of input parameters in calculating SOC stocks (e.g soil depths, bulk density, coarse fragments, etc.), Stolte et al. (2015) conclude that SOC stocks based on modelling contain a significant level of uncertainty, either because of the model used or uncertainties in the input datasets. Also, variation in the conversion factor between SOM and SOC (Heaton et al., 2016; Klingenuß et al., 2014; Pribyl, 2010) increase the level of uncertainty. Therefore, the harmonisation of methodology could provide significant improvement in SOC loss assessment between regions and member states. As an example, FAO Soil Organic Carbon Mapping Cookbook provides five different

methodological approaches for SOC mapping harmonisation (Yigini et al., 2018). However, there is still great variability in analysis and calculations at the regional and local levels.

It should be emphasised that regardless of SOC being the most required indicator parameter in European and global policies (Faber et al., 2022) with a proposition of threshold and reference values, these should be soil specifically analysed. The SIREN project concludes that based on the Project's questionnaire filled by participating countries reference, target, and threshold values (even per environmental zone) for SOC cannot be provided due to large variation between countries. For example, values can be dependent on soil type, soil layer (topsoil versus subsoil), land use, etc (Faber et al. 2022). Therefore, monitoring the direction rather than providing absolute values of indicators would be a possibility of analysing the sequestration or loss of SOC.

Translation to non-specialists

Long version of translation to non-specialists

Soil organic carbon loss is a soil threat with a decrease in soil organic carbon stock or soil organic carbon content of specific soil layers.

The decrease in soil organic carbon (SOC) is evaluated using different indicators, namely SOC content (%) and SOC stock (t/ha). They both refer to a different aspect of SOC decrease. The evolution of the SOC content of the top soil focusses more on the loss of soil fertility due to SOC decrease. The evolution of SOC stock refers to the total amount of SOC in a soil and is an indicator for the total loss of carbon and thus indicates whether the soil is a sink or a source regarding climate mitigation.

A mineral soil typically consists of approximately one half of mineral phase, the other half being air and water, and only a minority of soil is organic matter. But it is precisely this organic matter that largely determines the quality of our soils. In turn, that soil quality is related to what that soil does for us and can continue to do in the future.

The starting material of this soil organic matter is fresh organic material such as plant residues, compost, farmyard manure, etc. This organic material is made smaller by soil organisms such as earthworms and further decomposed by bacteria and fungi. When fresh organic material has become unrecognisable, we refer to it as soil organic matter. Soil organic matter is a mixture of complex chemical compounds and consists of approximately 50–60% soil organic carbon.

This organic matter is then slowly decomposed by soil organisms into simpler compounds and ions (phosphorus, potassium, etc.). Organic matter and living soil organisms are therefore inextricably linked. Soil organic carbon is an important component of soil fertility whereas the knowledge of SOC enables to quantify also the nutrient status of the soil (incl. fertilisation recommendations) and agricultural production accordingly.

SOC plays also an important role in climate regulation, and it affects the global carbon cycle. The soil can provide net removal of CO₂ from the air. To do so, the supply of organic carbon must be at least as great as its removal. If the decomposition of organic carbon is larger than its supply, the soil will release CO₂ and contribute to climate change.

The decrease of SOC stocks affects soil physical properties and soil fertility, diminishes the ability of soil to absorb water and attenuate the release of contaminants to other environmental compartments. SOC stimulates soil life and helps to build a stable soil structure with an optimal pore size distribution. This is important for the stability and water balance of a soil. A stable soil with an optimal amount of SOC acts as a sponge for water and is more resistant to compaction by heavy

agricultural machinery and erosion by run-off. This also means that there is a larger buffer for plant growth during long, dry periods that we can expect to occur due to climate change.

Short version of translation to non-specialists

Soil organic carbon loss is a soil threat with a decrease in soil organic carbon stock or soil organic carbon content of specific soil layers.

Soil organic carbon (SOC) is the largest single component of soil organic matter (SOM) also containing other elements vital for life (incl. biomass production). SOC is an important component of soil fertility whereas knowledge on SOC enables us to also quantify the nutrient status of the soil (incl. fertilisation recommendations) and agricultural production accordingly. SOC plays also an important role in climate regulation, and it affects the global carbon cycle through sequestration (increase in SOC) or mineralisation (decrease in SOC). The decrease of SOC stocks affects soil physical properties and soil fertility, diminishes the ability of soil to absorb water and attenuate the release of contaminants to other environmental compartments.

Commonly used indicators for evaluating SOC loss are SOC content (%) and SOC stock (t/ha).

Interrelation with other soil threats or SES

The loss of SOC does not only have an influence on other soil threats (e.g soil erosion, nutrient imbalance, drought, soil compaction, and loss of diversity) but also on soil provided ecosystem services (e.g biomass production, carbon sequestration, GHG and climate regulation). Conversely, soil erosion has been identified a major threat to SOC through different climate scenarios (Lin and Zhang, 2012; Mondal et al., 2016). The RECARE project has identified the effects of SOC decrease on ecosystem services/soil functions and to other soil threats. SOC stock has been integrated also in bundles analysis as an indicator of soil quality (e.g SDG Indicator 15.3.1 - Proportion of Land That Is Degraded Over Total Land Area) and included synergies and trade-off research in analysing SES (e.g Obiang Ndong et al., 2021).

Figure 3-3 Managing measures affect SOC content of soils (© Ungaro, F. n.d.)

3.4 Nutrient imbalance (macronutrients, micronutrients, deficiency/excess)

Definition, information and remarks about soil threat

Definition

Nutrient imbalance is a deficiency or excess of one or more macro- or micronutrients at a given time.

More generally, nutrient imbalance refers to situations when one or more essential plant nutrients are either deficient, sufficient but not available or available in excess of what plants take up at a given time. The first two situations cause plant stunting and reduced yield and quality, while the latter can lead to loss of nutrients from the soil and environmental degradation. The soil may have nutrients in both excess and deficient at the same time, and some nutrients can compete with others for plant uptake and cause deficiencies even when soil levels are sufficient (WSU, n.d.)

Information

Nutrient cycles link agricultural systems to their societies and surroundings; application of essential nutrients (macro-/micronutrients), in particular, are essential for high crop yields, but downstream and downwind losses of these same nutrients diminish the environmental quality and human well-being.

Agricultural nutrient balances differ substantially with economic development, from inputs that are inadequate to maintain soil fertility in parts of many developing countries, particularly those of sub-Saharan Africa, to excessive and environmentally damaging surpluses in many developed and rapidly growing economies. National and/or regional policies contribute to patterns of nutrient use and their environmental consequences in all of these situations. Solutions to the nutrient challenges that face global agriculture can be informed by analyses of trajectories of change within, as well as across, agricultural systems (Vitousek et al., 2009).

Harvested crops remove essential macro-/micronutrients from agricultural soils and sustaining agricultural production requires replacing those nutrients, whether through biological processes like nitrogen fixation or through the addition of animal wastes or mineral fertilizer to fields. Nutrient additions to intensive agricultural systems range from inadequate to excessive and both extremes have substantial human and environmental costs (Vitousek, 2018; Vitousek et al., 2009). Globally, fertilizer is the major pathway of nutrient addition; it has more than doubled the quantities of new nitrogen and phosphorus entering the terrestrial biosphere. These inputs have helped to keep world crop productivity ahead of human population growth and can enhance rural economic development. There is consensus that the global food system is not delivering as needed on several key metrics, including rates of hunger and malnutrition, decent agricultural livelihoods and the environmental impact of agriculture (HLPE, 2019). However, environmental costs of nutrient pollution from agriculture have been substantial, including the degradation of downstream water quality and eutrophication of coastal marine ecosystems, the development of photochemical smog, and rising global concentrations of the powerful greenhouse gas nitrous oxide.

The most relevant objective/target for nutrient imbalance in the Soil Health Law is to reduce nutrient losses by at least 50% (while ensuring that there is no deterioration of soil fertility) (Montanarella and Panagos, 2021). In fact, reducing losses are already an integral part of the Water Framework Directive and the Nitrates Directive (European Council, 1991). However, both directives do not mention a specific reduction percentage and only focus on nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P), while nutrient imbalance must be viewed from a broader perspective. Quantifying the nutrient inputs and outputs of a farm, watershed, or any other well-defined boundary advances our knowledge

of how to maintain a nutrient balance, which is an essential step toward sustainable nutrient management (Zhang et al., 2020).

Before focusing on nutrients themselves, it is important to concentrate on the optimisation of soil pH; a slightly acid environment favours plants nutrient availability (Figure 3-4; Boer et al., 2011).

Figure 3-4 Nutrient availability as a function of pH. (From Boer et al., 2011)

Some nutrients can be handled as ‘stand-alone’, as their optimisation mainly depends on plant’s demand and/or soil concentration (e.g. N and P). Other nutrients must be regarded in interdependence, even with soil properties themselves (Figure 3-5; Blgg, n.d.). One of the best-known examples is the need for a K/Mg relationship <2 in grass in order to reduce the risk of hypomagnesaemia.

Figure 3-5 Effect of nutrient occupation (%) of the soil sorption complex on soil structure (red: very bad structure; green: optimum structure (Blgg, n.d: <https://docplayer.nl/110093748-Welkom-themadag-blgg-akkerbouw-de-bodem-doorgrond.html>.)

Micronutrients, though required in relatively tracer amount (at 100 mg kg^{-1} dry weight) by plants, play a virtually significant role in a variety of cellular and metabolic processes such as, gene regulation, hormone perception, energy metabolism and signal transductions etc. Based on their precise requirement in higher plants, boron (B), chloride (Cl), copper (Cu), iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), molybdenum (Mo), nickel (Ni), and zinc (Zn) are typically classified under essential micronutrients (Hänsch and Mendel, 2009). These micronutrients can also be proven toxic when present at accelerated concentrations and such toxicity level endangers the plant growth (Tripathi et al., 2015)._Micro-nutrients are mostly regarded in view of specific plant demands (e.g. higher boron needs for sugar beets and cabbages) and/or human health problems (e.g. zinc, selenium).

Remarks

Though most countries have fertilizer advices in place, a lot of farmers still don’t make use of it or they continue doing things out of habit or don’t trust the recommended quantities.

Crop yields have not increased substantially in sub-Saharan Africa, and 250 million people remain chronically malnourished there. Nutrient additions to most fields do not replenish soil nutrients extracted in crop harvest. In contrast, agricultural production in China has increased dramatically since ~1975, with per-hectare yields of grain doubling in many areas. Policy-driven increases in fertilizer use contributed to rising crop yields as China strived for food security. Nutrient additions to many fields exceed far those in the United States and Northern Europe. In Western Europe, post-World War II national and, later, European Community policies to boost food security caused many areas to reach nutrient surpluses within integrated crop and animal production systems as large and damaging as those now observed in China. Since the 1980s, increasingly stringent national and European Union regulations and policies have reduced nitrogen surpluses and have improved indicators of environmental nutrient excess. Despite these steps toward nutrient balance, nitrogen pollution remains substantial in both the air and water of Northern Europe. However, the inefficiency level of EU countries' policy, is on average, relatively higher than what was reported in different regions of the world. The highest efficiency of environmental spending has been, therefore, achieved in Central-Eastern European and Scandinavian countries and Spain (Czyżewski et al., 2020).

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

It is related to the **TRACE-Soil** project which is targeted to identify the mechanisms underpinning trade-offs and synergies of soil carbon sequestration, greenhouse gas emissions and nutrient losses in agricultural soils across Europe. Soil management practices related to the reduction of the losses in particular of nitrogen (N) and phosphorous (P) is the topic of great interest at present. <https://eipsoil.eu/soil-research/trace-soils>

Indicators

There is no single indicator for nutrient imbalance because for each crop there is a specific interaction between soil nutrient content/concentration, soil texture and reaction (pH) and plants needs (in relation to variety and/or their use).

Yet not an indicator, but soil and crop specific fertilizer advice is the best possible proxy to have an insight into nutrient imbalances and at the same time to overcome the imbalance.

Translation to non-specialists

Nutrient imbalance has both an impact on plant production and the environment. Shortage or the unavailability of some nutrients (due to soil conditions) causes reduced plant growth. Overuse of nutrients gives rise to losses to the environment and to eutrophication of ground- and surface water.

Interrelation with other soil threats or SES

Soil erosion, loss of soil organic carbon, contamination, waterlogging, salinization and acidification as well as the loss of diversity all drive nutrient imbalance which have negatively consequences for biomass production.

3.5 Soil acidification

Definition, information and remarks about soil threat

Definition

Soil acidification is an increase in soil acidity leading to unfavourable conditions for plant growth and microbial activity. This involves a progressive loss of base cations from the soil exchange complex, which are replaced by aluminium ions and hydrogen ions with the consequent decrease in pH.

Soil acidity is a condition in which H⁺ protons dominate in soil solution while pH is a measure of H⁺ protons concentration expressed as a negative common logarithm. Soil acidification, i.e. increase of acidity, leads to unfavourable conditions for plant growth and microbes' activity. Soil acidification is often defined also as an increased input of acids to soil and/or increased acid production in soil. Another definition describes soil acidification as a decrease of soil acid neutralizing capacity (ANC) due to increased acid production or input a loss of base cations able to neutralize these acids (Breemen et al., 1984).

Information

Soil acidification is a natural process that occurs in favourable conditions, like acidic parent material usually penurious with clay content, high precipitation and low temperatures leading to strong leaching, and/or acidic nature of plant litter. Further, nitrification process, i.e. oxidation of ammonia to nitrate or nitrogen and plant acidic exudates, also influence the natural processes by producing protons in soils. However, the acidification process can be significantly accelerated and modified by human activity, particularly by acid deposition (acid rain), which is mainly caused by the emission of SO₂ and NO_x which react with water and chemical substances occurring in the atmosphere to form of mineral nitric and sulphuric acids (Gower et al., 1995). Soil acidification, if caused by nitric acid deposition, can cause nutrient imbalance, as the high amount of entering nitrogen is not balanced by other essential nutrients (particularly magnesium and phosphorus). Humus materials in soil can also lead to soil acidification. During organic matter decomposition, humus, organic acids and different acid salts may be produced and also concentration of CO₂ increased. The increased concentration of CO₂, hydrolysis of acid salts and various organic acids combinedly increased the total acidity of soil. Soil acidification occurs in forest soils, especially under coniferous trees (spruce, pine) causing podzolization process and formation of podzolic soils. Nevertheless, it can endanger also agricultural soils especially those formed on glacial and fluvioglacial sand deposits, where the acid input can be also caused, by improper (usually too high) nitrogen fertilizers doses, limited use of liming, fast organic matter decay and crop production absorbing lime-like elements.

Soil acidification can slow down biological processes in soil, leading to limited soil organic matter transformation and decomposition. The composition of soil microorganisms can be shifted in favour of fungi at the expense of bacteria, and the overall biological activity is reduced. The quality of developed organic matter is decreasing. From a chemical point of view, acidification can cause increased mobilization of aluminium, iron and several potentially toxic elements (for example Cd, Zn, Cu, Ni, Cr) (Mayer, 1998). Concentrations of bioavailable forms of these elements can reach levels toxic for soil organisms or plants. The higher portion of mobile forms of these potentially toxic elements can also lead to increased concentrations of them in surface and ground waters. In agricultural soils high levels of aluminium, iron and hydrogen can cause root hair dieback, limitation of nitrification bacteria activity, reduction of root nodules in legumes and availability of Mn to plants. Potentially toxic metals that may occur in acidic soils in high amounts may cause toxic effects to living organisms or may be taken up by plants entering the human food chain. Acidity also influences soil structure causing its deterioration due to peptization of organic matter

A common agricultural practice eliminating soil acidification is the regular liming (Goulding, 2016). However, it is not always sufficient and for some farmers affordable. Moreover, liming can increase biological activity which can cause a faster decomposition of SOM resulting in a loss of SOC and increase the CO₂ emission. The use of liming fertilizer depends on the soil origin. Calcium carbonate is used especially for sandy soils with low cation exchange capacity. An alternative practice dedicated to clay rich soils can be the application of fertilizers containing Ca or Mg (like calcium nitrate) instead of acidifying fertilizers (like ammonium sulphate). A proper selection of crops producing less acids to soil can be also helpful.

Remarks

Soil acidity is a threat influencing soils functions only in few European countries but was included in the delineation of Areas Facing Natural Constraints (resolution nr 1305/2013; EU, 2013) as one of biophysical factors.

Soil acidification is a much bigger issue in forest soils, particularly under coniferous trees, where the effect of acid deposition is increased by interception capacity of the trees and by acid litter (Menz and Seip, 2004).

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

It is related to the **CarboSeq** project, because it elucidates how SOC composition rate could be affected by soil acidification. Soil acidification could potentially be a management tool to mediate pH effect on SOC sequestration and allow the integration of pH on SOC modelling framework. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/carboseq>

Indicators

- pH-value (active – pH_{H₂O}, and exchangeable – pH_{KCl} or pH_{CaCl₂})
- Base cations in soil sorption complex – Bc or BC (Bc = Ca²⁺ + Mg²⁺ + K⁺; BC = Bc + Na⁺)
- BS – base saturation (BC*100%/CEC)
- Molar Ca/Al or BC/Al ratio in soil solution
- Exchangeable Al content
- Biophysical criteria for the delineation of less favourite areas facing natural constraints: soil acidity: pH≤5 (in water) in topsoil

Translation to non-specialists

Soil acidity is a condition in which H⁺ protons dominate in soil solution due to acid production and acid-like plant exudates and/or acid dry (acidic particles and gases) and wet (rain, snow) deposition. Soil acidification is a process of increased input of acids to soils or increased production of acids in soils. Acid deposition can accelerate this process. As a consequence of soil acidity, biological activity in soil is limited, crop yield is reduced, and mobility and bioavailability of some potentially toxic elements (like aluminium) is increased

Interrelation with other soil threats or SES

Soil acidity influences:

- The decrease of organic matter content due to instability of soil structure and lack of lime-like ions causing humic and fulvic acids coagulation,
- The intensity of soil erosion due to instability of soil structure,
- The soil biodiversity favouring the conditions to fungi and reducing populations of microorganisms participating in N transformations,

- Disturbance of plant physiological processes like nutrient uptake, division of cells, formation of DNA and respiration etc.,
- Plant root growing issues due to inhibition of root elongation by interfering with cell division at the root apex and lateral roots,
- Reduced biomass production limiting the assortment of cultivated plant species,
- The increase of mobilization and migration of potentially toxic elements through soil profiles causing potential pollution of soils and groundwater

3.6 Soil contamination (e.g. potentially toxic elements, organic pollutants)

Definition, information and remarks about soil threat

Definition

Soil contamination is the occurrence of contaminants in soil above a certain level causing deterioration or loss of one or more soil functions, which can be in the form of point pollution and diffuse pollution. Soil pollutants can consist of various forms, such as organic and inorganic or particulate pollutants.

In general, member states define soil contamination as a presence of harmful chemicals and consider the above definition from the RECARE project (Stolte et al., 2015).

Information

The most common inorganic soil contaminants are trace elements such as arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), copper (Cu), mercury (Hg), lead (Pb), manganese (Mn), nickel (Ni), zinc (Zn) and radionuclides (FAO and UNEP, 2021). Some of them (boron (B), Cu, Cr, Zn, molybdenum (Mo), selenium (Se)) are essential for normal metabolic processes, while others (Pb, Cd, Hg) have no physiological function and are toxic to living organisms and humans (Rodríguez-Eugenio et al., 2018). The most important organic contaminants include petroleum-derived substances, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), organochlorine compounds (OCPs), dioxins, polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and pesticides covering different groups of substances (FAO and UNEP, 2021; Swartjes, 2011; Swartjes and Cornelis, 2011).

Recently, the attention of the scientific community has focused on emerging contaminants, which include: perfluorinated compounds (PFAS), pharmaceuticals (human and veterinary drug residues and antibiotics), phthalates and other plasticizers (e.g., bisphenol A), disinfectant residues, artificial nanomaterials, rare earth elements, and plastics and synthetic polymers (FAO and UNEP, 2021; Gavrilesco et al., 2015).

In the case of agricultural areas, diffuse contamination dominates, the most important source being a long-distance transport of dust and atmospheric deposition of pollutants as well as long-term use of low-quality fertilisers, uncontrolled use of sewage sludge, intensive use of pesticides and manure containing e.g., residues of veterinary drugs (FAO and ITPS, 2015; Rodríguez-Eugenio et al., 2018; Stolte et al., 2015). Due to the complexity of diffuse sources, the magnitude and real extent of diffuse contamination at the EU level is difficult to evaluate (Rodríguez-Eugenio et al., 2018).

Point soil contamination may result from intensive industrial activities, inadequate waste and wastewater disposal, uncontrolled landfills, mining and smelting, military activities or accidents and spills of any types (Paya Perez and Rodríguez Eugenio, 2018; Stolte et al., 2015). A large part of the cases of point contamination is related to former historical industrial activities. It is estimated (FAO and UNEP, 2021) that in Europe about 2.8 million sites are potentially contaminated, of which about 650,000 sites have been identified and inserted in national and/or regional inventories.

Soil contamination was described as one of the main threats to soil in the Thematic Strategy for Soil Protection (European Commission, 2006a) The Status of the World's Soil resources report prepared by the Intergovernmental Technical Panel on Soil (ITPS) identified 10 global soil threats among which soil contamination was identified as one of the most worrying threats to soil health and provision of key soil ecosystem services (FAO and ITPS, 2015).

One of the main objectives of the new EU Soil Strategy (COM(2021) 699 final; (European Commission, 2021a)) is to prevent pollution by clean industry, sustainable product design, improved

recycling, waste management and nutrient recovery, more efficient fertilizer application or reduced pesticide use and risk, as well as reducing the use of antimicrobials and microplastics and the per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). This is built on the objectives of the European Green Deal, according to which, by 2050, soil pollution should be reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to human health and natural ecosystems and respect the boundaries our planet can cope with, thus creating a toxic-free environment (European Commission, 2021d). These objectives are also relevant for provisions in the future Soil Health Law. In view of the targets of the Green Deal, the crucial issue is to identify and maintain a register for contaminated sites, assess risks and finally remediate these sites in case of unacceptable risks.

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

The EJP soil project INSURE (2021 – 2024) focus on wet management with raised ground water table and flood-tolerant crops in order to reduce peat decomposition and the related greenhouse gas emissions and water contamination from cultivated peatlands while still providing income for the farmers. The projects are not directly interlinked.

Indicators

Soil contamination is assessed using direct indicators: **concentration of common contaminants**, both **inorganic (Al, As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Hg, Ni, Pb, Zn, Mn, Fe, Ba) and organic (PAHs, OCPs, PCBs) expressed in ppm or mg kg⁻¹ soil**. The content of contaminants is compared with the threshold values established in national soil legislations, above which action is required. It is also reported (EEA, 2021; Huber et al., 2008; Stolte et al., 2015) that other indicators can be used for local and diffuse pollution assessment (Table 3-1).

Table 3-1 Indicators for soil contamination (based on (EEA, 2021; Huber et al., 2008; Stolte et al., 2015)

Source of pollution	Types of contaminants	Indicators
Diffuse	inorganic contaminants	heavy metal content in soil
		critical load exceedance by heavy metals
	persistent organic pollutants (POPs)	concentration of POPs
	nutrients and biocides	area under organic farming
		gross nutrient balance
	acidifying substances	topsoil pH
		critical load exceedance by sulphur and nitrogen
	other diffuse sources	average pesticide consumption per unit area of agricultural land
		sewage sludge application per unit area of agricultural land
Local	point sources	progress in management of contaminated sites
		new settlement area established on previously developed land
		status of site identification
		number of contaminated sites
		expenditures on remediation
		groundwater incidents

Translation to non-specialists

Soil contamination is the presence of harmful chemicals, e.g. potentially toxic elements, petroleum-derived substances, a wide range of pesticides, pharmaceuticals and antibiotics. The indicator of soil contamination is a content or concentration of organic/inorganic compounds.

Some soil contaminants (metals) occur naturally in soil parent material, however, the presence of most contaminants is a result of a broad range of human activity, e.g. industrial activities, management practices in agriculture (fertilizers, pesticides, plastics) or inadequate storage and waste disposal. Soil contamination affects both human and ecosystem health. Long-term human exposure to pollution can result in a number of non-communicable diseases: cancer, heart and lung disease, diabetes or kidney disease. Furthermore, excessive use of antibiotics in human and veterinary medicine can cause the spread of antibiotic resistance genes in the environment.

Interrelation with other soil threats or SESs

Soil pollution degrades many of the ecosystem services provided by soil, such as food supply, habitat for soil organisms, carbon sequestration, water quality protection and nutrient cycling. Soil pollution largely affects soil biodiversity, decreases the number and activity of soil organisms as well as leads to changes in the soil community structure, which results in alteration of biochemical cycles, a reduction in organic carbon content and nutrient availability. This also affects soil productivity and the quality of the food produced, and thus the economics of agriculture and farmers' incomes, as well as food security. In addition, contaminated sites can be a secondary source of ground- and freshwater contamination as a result of contaminants leaching and off-site transport through wind and water erosion.

Figure 3-6 contamination occurs in so many ways (@ Foldal, C. 2017)

3.7 Waterlogging

Definition, information and remarks about soil threat

Definition

Temporary water inundation or undesired standing of water on the soil surface due to both precipitation and groundwater emerging on the surface, that can limit oxygen access to the soil and create anaerobic conditions with related negative consequences. Waterlogged soils can emit nitrous oxide (N₂O), a strong GHG and create anaerobic conditions in the soil root zone.

Information

Waterlogging occurs when the soil is saturated with water. This phenomenon is evident by the presence of water at or near the soil surface. Waterlogging may occur at any time of the year, especially after heavy rain events, inadequate soil drainage or excess land irrigation. Impervious layer(s) within the soil profile originated naturally or formed due to soil compaction may restrict water flow in the downward direction as well.

Global climate change causes waterlogging events to be more frequent, severe, and unpredictable (IPCC, 2014). Soils are susceptible to waterlogging when the amount of rainfall exceeds the ability of the soil to drain away soil moisture. This susceptibility is increased by the strong texture contrast between sandy topsoils and clayey subsoils: infiltration is higher through the topsoil than in the subsoil.

The excess water inhibits gaseous exchange with the atmosphere, and biological activity uses up the available oxygen in the soil air and water – also called anaerobiosis, anoxia or oxygen deficiency as well as pH (Parent et al., 2008). These conditions affect agricultural plants in several ways: nutrient deficiencies or toxicities root death, reduced growth or death of the plant. Waterlogging reduces the concentration of macro elements (K, Ca, and Mg), whereas effects on microelements concentration are mixed, with some elements increasing (Fe, Al, Mn, and Na) and others decreasing (Cu and Zn) (Sharma et al., 2018). Excessive water content in the soil upon waterlogging decreases O₂ diffusion capacity, leading to hypoxic or even anoxic environments that inhibit the activity of nitrifying communities, resulting in depleted soil N availability that will negatively affect N-dependent crop productivity (Nguyen et al., 2018). Most terrestrial crops are susceptible to waterlogging. The negative effects of waterlogging depend on soil and crop type, duration, timing and other factors (den Besten et al., 2021). Waterlogging remains a significant constraint to cereal production across the globe in areas with high rainfall and/or poor drainage (Manik et al., 2019). Waterlogging affects overall plant growth, which leads to a substantial yield loss (de San Celedonio et al., 2018).

Waterlogging increases the reduction potential of the soil and changes the chemical equilibrium of many elements which then enter the soil-water solution in their ionic forms. Depending on soil type, this change in chemical equilibrium can include transient toxicities of some soil nutrients that are normally safe when soil is freely drained. Examples of these are iron and manganese compounds which can be converted into free ions when reduction potential is high. The reduction potential can take several days or longer to return to normal levels after the waterlogged soil has drained. Regular rainfall can cause repeated waterlogging and drainage cycles, and the soil can have high reduction potential for long periods.

Nitrogen is lost from waterlogged soils by leaching and denitrification. These losses, together with the lowered ability of plants to absorb nutrients from waterlogged soil, cause the older leaves to yellow. Waterlogging also directly reduces nitrogen fixation by the nodules of legume crops and pastures.

Waterlogged soils tend to collapse quickly through the dispersion of clay particles. This is especially the case in soils with high sodium:calcium ratio; these soils are often called dispersive or sodic soils. Waterlogged, non-dispersive soils can also lose soil structure by collapsing under their own weight in the absence of additional strength generated by the soil moisture suction of unsaturated soil, or disturbance by machinery or livestock when saturated at the surface.

Waterlogging may damage soil structure in term of stability of aggregates even in short-term period. Aggregate stability decreased by about 20% during a 14-day ponding period (De-Campos et al., 2009).

Machinery passing across waterlogged soils will damage soil structure. The area of damage can be minimised by using a tramline or controlled traffic (CTF) farming system which also improves trafficability during seeding, fertilising, and spraying operations on waterlogged soils. CTF is a management system to control extensive unsystematic trafficking by farm machinery/vehicles and protect soil structure from indiscriminate change (Hamza and Anderson, 2005). The tramlines themselves are susceptible to water erosion, and surface water management structures are recommended to minimise the risk of damage.

Many farmers do not realise that a site is waterlogged until water appears on the soil surface. However, by this stage, plant roots may already be damaged and yield potential severely affected. Waterlogging is serious also as it does not have to be characterized by excess water on the surface, meaning it could be a continuing problem even without having to see the water on the surface. Unfortunately, as each plant is different, there is no universal level of soil oxygen that can identify waterlogged conditions for all plants. Additionally, a plant's demand for oxygen in its root zone varies with the plant's stage of growth.

To reduce soil waterlogging options might vary from shallow surface drains to more intensive drainage using wide-spaced furrows, vertical subsurface drainage, mole drains to the intensive drainage form of raised beds (Bazzoffi and Nieddu, 2011; Manik et al., 2019). Another option is soil decompaction, since it is necessary to avoid the formation of a plough pan - a compacted layer created by the ploughshare. Individual deep tillage (loosening, subsoiling) effects are highly site-specific. At sites with root-restricting, compacted soil layers, the crop yield response to deep tillage was 20% higher than at sites without such layers. Soils with >70% silt (labile soil structure) shows an increased risk of negative deep tillage effects (Schneider et al., 2017). In soils of glacial origin shallow tillage (no-till) application may lead to cultivation pan formation (dense top-soil layer) which is similar to plough pan (Feiziene et al., 2012).

Deep mouldboard ploughing should be avoided. To loosen compacted soil layers mechanically the farmers may adopt alternative tillage systems, such as chiselling or deep subsoiling. Rotary tillage should be limited, as this causes the partial pulverisation of the soil which can easily become compacted again and thus form a surface crust after rainfall (Bazzoffi and Nieddu, 2011).

However, high water levels in peat areas are beneficial as they reduce CO₂ emissions from peat areas. There is some consensus in peat literature that water levels of -20 cm are best from the point of view of GHG emission. At still higher levels CH₄ emissions might increase.

Remarks

Waterlogging causes root-tip death within days. Loss of root tips limits the uptake of nutrients (particularly nitrogen) and water after waterlogging. As a result, plants that have been waterlogged ripen early and grain is often pinched.

About 10% of the world's irrigated lands suffer from waterlogging (Bowonder et al., 1987)

Identification of areas with high risk of waterlogging requires spatial modelling, that is mapping of the natural hazard. Laborczy et al. (2020) applied hybrid spatial prediction approaches to predict waterlogging hazard, based on locally experienced waterlogging frequency observations, taking into account spatial auxiliary information, that represent the affecting environmental factors (soil, geology, topography, land use, climate). Pásztor et al. (2015) mapped risk of waterlogging, Bozán et al. (2018) mapped relative frequency of waterlogging carried out by Regression Kriging method, based on the relationship between the occurrence of waterlogging and its driving factors.

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

SoilCompaC The aim of the project is to quantify interactions between soil compaction and climate, and present information on how to assess, detect, recover and minimize soil compaction. Two goals of the project are related to waterlogging topic: 1) Quantify impacts of soil compaction on soil carbon stocks in a climate change context, and estimate impacts on greenhouse gas emissions, crop growth and water balance, for a range of European pedo-climatic zones; 2) Synthesize quantitative knowledge on mechanical, natural and biological recovery of compacted soils across Europe. <https://eipsoil.eu/soil-research/soilcompac>

Indicators

Frequency/or days of occurrences of inland excess water; %

The best way to identify problem areas is to dig holes (e.g. about 40 cm deep) in winter and see if water flows into them. If it does, the soil is waterlogged. Digging holes for fence posts often reveals waterlogging.

Translation to non-specialists

A soil is naturally capable to retain different amounts of water, but when such amounts exceed the soil capacity water fills all the pore spaces and finally accumulates over the surface. Waterlogging can be temporary or permanent. A possible solution to overcome this problem is to remove the excess water using different systems as porous pipes or ditches.

Interrelation with other soil threats or SESs

Compaction and salinization increases the probability of waterlogging. On the other hand, waterlogged soils have more likely nutrient imbalance. This affects directly the SES of biomass/primary production and increases the likelihood of GHG emissions from these agricultural fields.

3.8 Soil compaction

Definition, information and remarks about soil threat

Definition

The densification and distortion of soil by which total and air-filled porosity are significantly reduced, causing deterioration or loss of one or more soil functions.

Soil compaction refers to the physical degradation of the soil resulting in densification and distortion of soil where biological activity, porosity and permeability are reduced, strength is increased and soil structure is partly destroyed. Although soil compaction can be the result of natural processes, it is generally associated with force applied by mechanised agriculture or by pressure under the hooves of livestock (TEAGASC, 2017). The soil compaction involves the changes in physical properties of the soil (bulk density and soil porosity) and these modified physical parameters of the soil are determinants of the influence of the soil compaction on chemical properties of the soil, soil fauna, and diversity and plant growth (Nawaz et al., 2013).

Information

Unlike other soil threats, such as salinity, superficial water logging or soil erosion that can be remarked from the soil surface, soil compaction causes a hidden degradation of soil structure (Mc Garry and Sharp, 2003). About 68 million ha of the soils worldwide are estimated to be affected by soil compaction from vehicular traffic, of which 33 million hectares are in Europe (Hamza and Anderson, 2005).

Soil compaction can manifest itself in different ways: topsoil compaction, a plough pan or (deep) subsoil compaction. Topsoil compaction occurs when soil is subjected to pressure from the passage of heavy machinery or by repeated trampling of grazing animals, especially under wet conditions. In arable land with annual cultivation, a plough pan can be developed by a tractor driving directly in the furrow during ploughing. (Deep) subsoil compaction is often a cumulative effect due to e.g. the use of unsuitable tyres and/or tyre pressures, the use of excessively heavy machinery in unfavourable soil conditions, etc. Whereas a plough layer, and certainly topsoil compaction, can be rather easily (mechanically) remediated, subsoil compaction is very much a hidden problem and loosening the subsoil must be done in a well-considered way. The subsoil compaction has been acknowledged as a serious form of soil degradation by the European Union (Jones et al., 2003). According to European Soil Data Centre, recent research has showed that compaction is the most widespread kind of soil physical soil degradation in central and eastern Europe. About 25 million ha were deemed to be lightly compacted while a further 36 million ha were more severely affected (ESDAC, n.d.)

The effects of soil compaction on plant growth and grain yield under contrasting weather conditions in two years, the soil compaction increased shoot growth in the drier year, but decreased shoot growth in the wetter year. The seasonal dynamics of soil physical conditions and plant growth, we found that higher early vigor reduced grain yield, and this relationship was associated with the progressively deteriorating soil physical conditions during the entire cropping season (Liu et al., 2022). Cover crops not only reduce nitrogen leaching losses (Hansen et al., 2019; Kasper et al., 2019), but also provide other agro-ecosystem services, such as weed suppression, carbon sequestration in the soil, erosion reduction, reduction of soil compaction, better microbial properties (Blanco-Canqui, 2021).

Compaction leads to a reduction in biological activity, porosity and permeability. Compaction can affect water infiltration capacity and can lead to increased surface run-off, flooding, erosion and

transport of nutrients and agrochemicals to open water. Furthermore, a compacted soil impedes root development which means that nutrient uptake is suboptimal and the yield potential is not fully exploited (ScienceDirect, 2022; TEAGASC, 2017).

Soil compaction also influences a number of environmental parameters even at considerable distance from the original location at which the compaction occurred (Figure 3-3). Soane and van Ouwerkerk (1995) have reported that soil compaction can cause an increase in the denitrification rate and emissions of N_2O by about 400–500%.

Compaction may change the fluxes of greenhouse gasses from the soil to the atmosphere through mechanisms associated with effects on soil permeability, aeration and crop development. Compaction increases CO_2 emissions because the cultivation of compacted soils requires appreciably more energy than cultivation of uncompacted soils. Approximately 90% of the global N_2O emissions to the atmosphere comes from soils. Compacted soils tend to be wetter than noncompacted soils and denitrification is enhanced (van den Akker and Soane, 2005).

Figure 3-7 Implications of soil compaction for the quality of the environment (Soane and van Ouwerkerk, 1995)

The soil compaction results in energy costs increasing on arable land due to a greater tillage intensity requirement, fertilizer inputs increase, while the plant nutrients effectiveness in compacted soil is not always lower. Pot experiment with spring barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) revealed that the total root length of the crop was 59% lower at the higher compaction (90% of the standard degree of compactness) level mainly due to fewer roots with diameter <0.5 mm. However, both shoot growth and plant P uptake were reduced a lesser degree than root length. Even 69% more shoot dry matter per unit root length was produced in the compacted soil, and the P uptake per unit root length was 75% higher in the more compacted soil (Kristoffersen and Riley, 2005).

Soil compaction is a threat to crop yield, but mechanical decompaction operations increase soil degradation risk and crop costs. However, the relationship between soil compaction and crop yield is affected by rainfall pattern, which changes over the years. Long-term effect of soil compaction in crop yield is wide unknown, and fill this gap is crucial for adjust soil management to improve soil conservation and increase crop yield (Mulazzani et al., 2022).

Remarks

Contrary to other soil chemical properties, such as soil pH, and macro and micronutrients, far less attention is given to soil physical properties. Nevertheless, soil physical problems and especially compaction can have a serious impact on both crop yield and the environment. Compaction problems is likely a prolonged period of time, the best solution to avoid the problem altogether. Farmers have to plan operations, such as spreading fertiliser, to avoid working paddocks when wet. The soil should break easily and crumble at the deepest depth as it is being tilled. Dry soil will compact less than moist soil. Reduce secondary tillage passes as each additional tillage pass destroys aggregates and increases bulk density. Ideally, adopt minimum or zero tillage systems. Control traffic patterns using tramlines, as under conventional tillage systems as much as 90 % of the land area can be tracked at least once. Remove excess weight on machinery and use only enough ballast to reduce slippage. Reduce surface pressure by reducing tyre pressure or by using lighter axle loads.

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

SoilCompaC Although adverse impacts of compaction on soil properties and functions are relatively well documented, estimates of the extent and severity of compaction in Europe remain elusive. We have limited knowledge on how compaction changes the carbon cycle, and we lack information on compaction risks for different pedo-climatic zones and cropping systems in Europe and how the risks evolve due to climate change. SoilCompaC directly addresses these knowledge gaps. SoilCompaC will quantify interactions between soil compaction and climate, and present information on how to assess, detect, recover and minimize soil compaction, thereby providing a basis for sustainable soil management. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/soilcompac>

Indicators

Bulk density (dry soil mass per unit volume: g cm^{-3}) is a common parameter to express soil compaction. The soil penetration resistance (MPa) is also widely used to determine compaction. Soil water permeability (m s^{-1}), total and air-filled porosity (%), oxygen diffusion rate (μ Amper), redox potential (Volts), and air permeability (l min^{-1}) are valuable methods to measure soil compaction status in the field or in the lab.

Indicators and their respective limit values are manifold (Table 3-2), but most often it's not easy to distinguish soils with a good structure from those with a poor structure on the basis of only one indicator.

Table 3-2 Soil physical indicators and their limit values used to distinguish non-compacted from compacted soils

Indicator	Limit value
Bulk density (Huber et al., 2008)	BD $\leq 1,75 - 0,009\% \times \text{\%clay}$ (%clay > 17,5%) BD $\leq 1,60$ (%clay $\leq 17,5\%$)
Penetration resistance (Håkansson and Lipiec, 2000)	PR ≤ 3 MPa
Saturated hydraulic conductivity (Reynolds et al., 2008)	Ks ≥ 10 cm day ⁻¹
Air capacity (Reynolds et al., 2009)	AC $\geq 0,10$ m ³ m ⁻³
Macroporosity (Reynolds et al., 2008)	MacPor (pore dm >10 μ m) $\geq 0,04$ m ³ m ⁻³

Table 3-3 Soil physical indicators for soils with good quality (Sq = [1-3]) and bad quality ([3-5]) (CoreVESS method). Values with the same letter are not statistically different ($p < 0,05$) (Van der Bolt et al., 2020).

Sq	Average Sq	PR (MPa)	BD (g cm^{-3})	AC (m^3m^{-3})	MacPor (m^3m^{-3})	Ks (cm day ⁻¹)
[1-3]	2,5 (0,4)b	2,95 (1,6)b	1,418 (0,124)b	0,071 (0,04)a	0,022 (0,02)a	11,1 (9,3)a
[3-5]	3,6 (0,4)a	4,23 (2,2)a	1,508 (0,113)a	0,059 (0,04)b	0,017 (0,01)b	9,7 (6,5)a

The typical exception is the detection of a plough layer on the basis of penetration resistance (Figure3-4)

Figure 3-8 Change in penetration resistance (x-axis) with depth (y-axis) (van der Bolt et al., 2020)

Translation to non-specialists

Soil compaction is the increase in density of soil usually caused by crushing the soil (e.g., with machinery). It can happen more easily when the soil is wet. The heavier the soil texture of a soil is, the greater is the vulnerability to compact.

It is documented that the soil compaction acts as a wide-range soil threat. It increases soil strength, bulk density, while it reduces the volume of pores that have air thus decreasing porosity, soil aeration, water infiltration rate, and saturated hydraulic conductivity, negatively affects biological diversity, nutrient availability and finally results in a reduced crop yield.

Practical recommendations are valuable to implement to avoid, delay or prevent soil compaction: (a) reducing pressure on soil either by decreasing axle load and/or increasing the contact area of wheels with the soil; (b) working soil at optimal soil moisture content; (c) reducing the number of passes by farm machinery and the intensity; (d) to implement controlled traffic in a field; (e) increasing soil organic matter by implementing species rich crop rotations and crop residues returning; (f) removing soil compaction by deep ripping in the presence of an aggregating agent; (g) crop rotations that include plants with deep, strong taproots; (h) complete nutrition to meet crop requirements to help the soil/crop system to resist external stresses (Hamza and Anderson, 2005).

Interrelation with other soil threats or SESs

Soil compaction decreases soil biodiversity by decreasing microbial biomass, enzymatic activity, soil fauna, and ground flora. This has a negative influence on soil ecosystems service capability. Modified soil physical properties due to soil compaction can alter plant nutrient mobility and change nitrogen and carbon cycles towards more emissions of greenhouse gases under wet conditions (Nawaz et al., 2013). Stolte et al. (2015) considered that soil compaction has effects on water erosion, flooding, drought and soil biodiversity.

3.9 Soil sealing

Definition, information and remarks about soil threat

Definition

The permanent covering of soils by buildings, constructions and layers of completely or partly impermeable artificial material (asphalt, concrete, etc.). It is the most intense form of land take and is a hardly reversible process. Soil sealing is causing loss of essential soil ecosystem functions

(Huber et al., 2008; Prokop et al., 2011; Stolte et al., 2015)

Information

Soil sealing is the result of urbanisation whose impact on land is also referred to as land take or land consumption which is defined as any conversion of agricultural, natural or semi-natural area to an artificial land-use (FAO and ITPS, 2015; Marquard et al., 2020; Prokop et al., 2011), including sparse settlements, urban fringes, industrial estates and transport infrastructure. Not all the urbanised or transformed areas are sealed, as in the case e.g. of gardens, urban parks, or sporting leisure, where soils maintain part of their functionality, thus still potentially providing some wider ecosystem services.

Soil sealing is one of the most serious land degradation processes, firstly because several soil functions and ecosystem services are irrecoverable lost and secondly because soil sealing negatively affect numerous other services like hydrological or erosion control (Calzolari et al., 2016; Manna et al., 2017; Nestroy, 2006; Ungaro et al., 2014). Despite the small percentage of sealed soil, continuous land take and soil sealing are in several project member states leading to a fragmented agro-ecological landscape. This fragmentation implies indirect effects on today's and future primary and biomass production. Urban sprawl is the major driver, and since cities historically are sited on the most fertile soils the consequences are severe (Jancu et al. 2016). Gardi et al. (2015) calculated a loss of six million tons of wheat as a consequence of the loss of agricultural land area in 19 European states in the period 1990 – 2006.

In 2012, the European Commission published a report containing an overview of best practices for limiting soil sealing or mitigating its effects in the 27 EU member states (European Commission, 2012). It provides information on the magnitude of soil sealing in the EU, the impacts and examples of best practices for limiting soil sealing and mitigating and compensating for the impacts. This guideline will be re-elaborated under the European Soil Strategy implementation within 2024.

Remarks

As an important driver of soil sealing, land take assessment in Europe is provided periodically by the EEA. EU target a 'no net land take' by 2050, and the EU member states voluntary have set intermediary targets on net land take reduction by 2030 (European Commission, 2019). The last available report is dated December 2019, and reports land take dynamics for the years 2000, 2006, 2012 and 2018, in km²/y of each period from the Corine Land Cover Accounting Layers as changes from agricultural (CLC class 2xx), forest and semi-natural/natural land (CLC class 3xx), wetlands (CLC class 4xx) or water (CLC class 5xx) to urban areas (CLC class 1xx) are assessed at NUT3 level. The last estimates indicate that "despite a reduction in the last decade (land take was over 1000km²/year between 2000-2006), land take in EU28 still amounted to 539km²/year between 2012-2018" (EEA, 2022b).

According to M3.2, five MSs assessed soil sealing at national scale, namely Belgium, Czech Republic, Spain, Hungary and Italy, and in total 22 studies addressing sealing at different scales are reported.

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

Indicators

% sealed soil of total soil area or km² or hectares of sealed soil at a given date. The change is expressed as km² (or hectares) or percentage per year or years.

The project member states in SERENA assess the degree of soil sealing and the dynamics of urbanization by several approaches e.g.:

- **satellite images** are used in Hungary, Italy, and Spain for assessments at national scales. In Italy the high resolutions of images (sentinel 1, sentinel 2 and other sources) allow detailed estimates even at municipal level.
- **aerial photographs** are used in Belgium
- combination of aerial photographs and **cadastral data** are applied in Austria. Further, orthophotos and old maps are digitalised and used to assess land use change with high resolution and in order to engage with local stakeholders at regional scale.
- **Corine Land Cover multitemporal maps** are used in Czech Republic.

In Latvia **spatial planning documents at local scale** are available

At European level, the degree of sealing and its dynamics is based on **NDVI** (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) from satellite images (Landsat and Sentinel-2, 2006, 2009, 2012 and 2015), available through the **Copernicus Land Monitoring Service**. For the reference year, 2015, 1.5 % of the total EEA-39 area resulted sealed (EEA, 2022c).

The EEA indicator “Imperviousness in Europe” has been widely used as a soil sealing index (impervious soil coverage). The level of sealed soil (imperviousness degree 1-100%) is produced using a semi-automated classification, based on calibrated NDVI.

Several derived indicators are also calculated, such as annual rates, rates per capita, sprawl indexes, etc.

Translation to non-specialists

Soil sealing is the loss of soil resources due to covering the land for housing, pavements, terraces, roads or industry. It is the result of land take, or land consumption, due to urbanisation. Land take consumes agricultural land, reduces space for habitats and fragments the landscapes. Part of the urbanised land is converted to artificial (semi-)impervious surfaces, losing all its essential functions except hosting human activities, with impacts on agricultural production, water regulation and protection against floods, biodiversity, and microclimate regulation.

It is measured in terms of hectares of land lost at a given date or during a given period (e.g. in a year), and expressed in percentage of the considered territory.

Interrelation with other soil threats or soil ecosystem services

Soil sealing impacts on all the soil ecosystem services, causing the total loss of soil functionality. The increase of the extension of impervious areas is directly linked with waterlogging and flood risk and the loss of soil biodiversity. Also, erosion risk may be amplified in highly sealed areas due to increased runoff. Soil sealing and land take have indirect effects on soil compaction linked to urbanisation works (e.g. heavy machinery) and on soil contamination.

3.10 Salinization

Definition, information and remarks about soil threat

Definition

Soil salinization is the process of accumulation of water-soluble salts within the upper part of soil profile (particularly A and B horizons) and when the accumulation is above a certain threshold adversely affects crop production, environmental health, and economic welfare.

(From Ferreira et al., 2022; Rengasamy, 2006; Tóth et al., 2008)

Salt problems in soil originate from different sources but essentially result in the accumulation of soluble salts. Dominant cations are sodium (Na^+), potassium (K^+), magnesium (Mg^{2+}), and calcium (Ca^{2+}), whereas dominant anions are chloride (Cl^-), sulphate (SO_4^{2-}), carbonate (CO_3^{2-}) and bicarbonate (HCO_3^-) (Sposito, 2016; Tóth et al., 2008). Salinization can be due to natural processes because of a high salt content in the parent material or in groundwater, in which case it is called primary salinization. When it is caused by anthropic activities such as irrigation with salt-rich water or wastewater and in conditions of high evaporative demand or insufficient drainage, the salinization is called secondary. In coastal areas, salt sea water intrusion could occur with impacts on groundwater quality. Finally, when divalent cations are leached out of the soils and concentration of sodium ions increase, sodic soils develop.

Information

Salinization of soil negatively impacts plant development and induces land degradation. Saline soils show lower agricultural productivity, worsen farmers' wellbeing, and the economic situation in the region. Water uptake by plants depends on the level of salts in groundwater and the plant itself. Water is absorbed in the process of osmosis and flows from less salt-concentrated areas to more concentrated ones. When the salt concentration is too high, it means that the soil's osmotic potential is essentially negative. Plants suffer from **osmotic stress** when they fail to take up water, even when it is present in the soil. Basically, the process is similar to drought stress due to a lack of moisture in the ground. As a result, vegetation dies. Salinization tampers with nitrogen uptake too, which slows plant development and causes a yield loss.

Remarks

According to the member states' declaration about the state of the research on this topic, Italy mentioned that soil salinization is frequently studied, Hungary, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Spain declared that there are some studies on this topic, Belgium indicated that salinity is hardly studied. Seven out of sixteen countries did not list any studies on this topic.

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

SIREN project considers salinity as one of the soil quality indicators. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/siren>

Indicators

A soil is classified saline if the electrical conductivity (EC_e) of its saturation extract exceeds 4 dS m^{-1} (FAO, 2016) and this is based on the classification of electrical conductivity with regard to effects of salinity on crops shown in Table 3-4 (Richards, 1954):

Table 3-4 Class of electrical conductivity (ECe) and its effect on crop yield (from Richards, 1954)

EC _e (dS m ⁻¹)	Class	Effect
0-2	Non saline	Negligible
2-4	Mildly saline	Yield reduction of sensitive crops
4-8	Medium saline	Yield reduction of many crops
8-12	Very saline	Normal yields for salt tolerant crops only
>16	Extremely saline	Reasonable crop yield for very tolerant crops

Different indicators of soil salinity have been defined and the ones included in the review are the following:

- **Electrical conductivity of soil saturation paste (EC_e).** It is a measure of the concentration of all soluble salts in soil or water. Its unit of measurement is dS m⁻¹ at a temperature of 25°C.
- **pH (-).**

Also, the Sodium Adsorption Ratio (SAR) and Exchangeable Sodium Percentage (ESP), are used to indicate salinization. However, both SAR and ESP indices indicate the level of soil sodification as follows: **SAR (Sodium Adsorption Ratio)** is used to characterize the sodium status of soil water solution. This index is calculated based on the concentration of soluble sodium, relatively to the concentrations of calcium and magnesium cations, according to the following formula (Bohn et al., 2001):

$$SAR = \frac{Na^+}{\left[\frac{(Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+})}{2}\right]^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

ESP (Exchangeable Sodium Percentage) can be calculated based on the SAR values, according to the following formula (van Reeuwijk, 2002):

$$ESP [\%] = (1.475 \cdot SAR - 1.26) / (0.01475 \cdot SAR + 0.9874)$$

Another indication can be

- the **content of Cl⁻ ions** measured potentiometrically in soil-water suspension (Łuczak et al., 2021).
- **Occurrence of halophytic vegetation** (Furtado Bliss Ursula et al., 2019).

Translation to non-specialists

Soil salinization consists of the accumulation of soluble salts (potassium, magnesium, calcium, chlorides, sulphates, carbonates, bicarbonates and sodium) in the soil due to natural factors (parent rock, climate, etc.) or to human activities (irrigation with saline water, excessive abstraction of groundwater with sea water intrusion, over-fertilisation, etc.). Moreover, when the percentage of sodium ions dominates, soil sodification occurs.

Interrelation with other soil threats or SESs

Soil salinization is a serious problem itself, but it rarely comes alone. Salinity causes continuous wetness of land surface and a lack of cover due to poor plant growing conditions. These make lands highly prone to erosion.

Water table rise due to salinization reduces the soil's ability for water infiltration. With heavy rainfalls or river flooding, soils cannot cope with high amounts of water flows. Thus, insufficient absorption results in waterlogging, runoffs and floods.

Soil salinity and sodification have a negative effect on biomass production. Most crops tolerate low salinity, but with higher level of salinization and sodification (especially industrial origin), some of the soils may be excluded from agricultural use.

3.11 Loss of diversity

Definition, information and remarks about soil threat

Definition

A reduction of forms of life living in soils (both in terms of quantity and variety) and of related functions

(adapted from the RECARE project; same as the one in ENVASSO)

Information

Globally soils contain at least one quarter to one third of all living organisms on the planet and are an important reservoir of biodiversity (JRC and Joint Research Centre, 2010).

According to (EEA, 2022a) soil biodiversity commonly includes all organisms living in the soil (including the soil surface, e.g. the litter layer): macro, meso and microfauna, and microorganisms (bacteria, fungi, protists, archaea and algae). After Bloem et al. (2005) the main functional groups of the soil food web listed in this report (EEA, 2022a) are:

- *Earthworms consume plant residues and soil including (micro)organisms. Often, they form the major part of the soil fauna biomass with maximally 1000 individuals per m², 3000 kg fresh biomass per hectare, or a few hundred kg of carbon (C) per hectare.*
- *Enchytraeids (potworms) are relatives of earthworms with a much smaller size and a similar diet, densities of 10²-10⁶ per m², with a biomass up to 1 kg C ha⁻¹ (EEA, 2021).*
- *Mites (fungivores, bacterivores, predators) have a size of about 1 mm, densities of 10⁴-10⁵ per m², and a biomass up to 0.1 kg C ha⁻¹.*
- *Springtails or Collembola (fungivores, omnivores) also have a size of about 1 mm. They reach densities of 10³-10⁵ per m² and a biomass up to 1 kg C ha⁻¹.*
- *Nematodes (bacterivores, herbivores, fungivores, predators/omnivores) have a size of about 500 μm, densities of 10-50 per g soil, and a biomass up to 1 kg C ha⁻¹.*
- *Protists (amoebae, flagellates, ciliates) are unicellular animals with a size of 2-200 μm, densities of about 10⁶ cells per g soil, and a biomass of about 10 kg C ha⁻¹.*
- *Bacteria are usually smaller than 2 μm, with densities of about 10⁹ cells per g soil, and a biomass of 50- 500 kg C ha⁻¹.*
- *Fungi grow as networks of threads (hyphae) which usually have diameters from 2 to 10 μm, and reach total lengths of 10 to 1000 meter g⁻¹ soil, and a biomass of 1 to 500 kg C ha⁻¹.*

Soil microorganisms play an important role as regulators of major biogeochemical cycles and can significantly affect the ecosystem functioning (Bevivino et al., 2014)). Fungi, bacteria and archaea are involved in organic matter dynamics, nutrient cycling and decomposition processes. Different practices can alter the below-ground ecosystem, often leading to depletion of soil carbon and loss of biodiversity, and thus affecting the structure of the resident microbial communities (Lauber et al., 2013). A decline of soil biodiversity can significantly affect the ability of the soil to function and respond to disturbances. It also decreases the capacity to recover. A decline in soil biodiversity can be linked with other threats like erosion, organic matter depletion, salinization, contamination and compaction (Stolte et al., 2015).

The level of impact on soil biodiversity and function is not the same for all regions of the world, and the effects of global change on soil biodiversity may be direct or indirect – via altered vegetation and nutrient availability. Importantly, climate change and land use intensification drivers are not completely independent of one another and thus co-occur. For instance, soil erosion is a process that is particularly relevant in disturbed ecosystems like agricultural lands, with approximately 80% of the Earth's agricultural lands experiencing significant levels of soil erosion (Orgiazzi et al., 2016)

Due to intensive agriculture, soil erosion, contamination, salinization and soil sealing the habitat of soil biodiversity is threatened and destroyed. The threats posed by agricultural intensification are often multiplied due to the interactive effect of other threats. For example, losses of carbon, soil structure and soil biodiversity can reduce an ecosystem's ability to sequester carbon (Wiesmeier et al., 2019). It is however notable that even polluted or severely disturbed soils still support relatively high levels of microbial diversity at least. It has been observed that specific groups may be more susceptible to certain pollutants or stresses than others (ESDAC, 2022).

Furthermore, the recent COVID-19 pandemic has led to increasing doubts about possible impacts of intensive, non-sustainable agriculture on soil biodiversity and ecosystem services. The use of efficient inoculants, the so-called Plant Growth-Promoting Microbes (PGPM), is considered an important strategy for sustainable management and for reducing chemical inputs in agriculture favouring the soil fertility and plant health (Tabacchioni et al., 2021). The microbial consortia treatments, developed within the H2020 SIMBA Project, had a beneficial influence on the biodiversity of the indigenous rhizo-microbial community, reinforcing the connection between microbes and plants (Graziano et al., 2022)

Remarks

In Mediterranean environments unsuitable land management together with climatic constraints (scarce and irregular rainfall and frequent drought periods) can contribute to increased rates of erosion and other soil degradation processes of agricultural land (Caravaca et al., 2002). Further, different agricultural practices can alter the soil ecosystem, often leading to the depletion of carbon in the soil and consequent reduction of biodiversity. At the same time, the structure of microbial communities is also affected, which is the key element for the long-term storage of carbon. To understand the processes that regulate soil mineralization it is important to know the spatial distribution of the microbial community and its dynamics in response to different agricultural practices and climatic conditions (Bevivino et al., 2014).

The project MSs reported that the soil threat "Loss of diversity" was evaluated on all scales (99 studies) by direct measurements. Earthworms, microbial biomass and specific enzymes are the most frequent used indicators in these studies (Michel, 2022).

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

MINOTAUR: modelling and mapping soil biodiversity patterns and functions across Europe. The project is ongoing and in exchange with SERENA. They stress less the soil threat of diversity loss, anyway we here find complementary information on indicators and status in EU. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/minotaur>

Indicators

Soil invertebrate biodiversity index (QBS); Soil microbial biomass carbon and functional groups; Density of earthworm occurrence; biodiversity indices; CLPP indicators; CO₂ efflux; microbial biomass values; enzymes activity; potential mineralizable N etc.

Traditionally three key indicators to assess the threat of potential loss of soil biodiversity and associated ecosystem functions were proposed by the ENVASSO project (Huber et al., 2008), namely: i) diversity of earthworms ii) diversity of collembolans and iii) soil microbial respiration. Currently less cost-intensive DNA-based methods are developed. The challenge is to install a database with baselines and thresholds for soil communities of invertebrates as well as microorganisms covering different climatic zones in Europe (EEA, 2022a). This objective will be realized in parallel with

MINOTAUR project in order to optimize the data collection, harmonization and analyse at European level and fostering the adoption of common global standards and approaches at national level.

Translation to non-specialists

One teaspoon of healthy soil contains more living organisms than there are people in the world. Soil biodiversity regulates the main processes that make life possible on Earth, because of the multiple relations between above and belowground. The numerous species have their own functional speciality and interaction with other organisms. Soil organisms are fundamental for ensuring the provision of healthy food and the agricultural production improvement, as well as the carbon sequestration and the degradation of contaminants. These organisms, being part of a huge food web, can guarantee the energy and nutrient cycling and to stimulate plant growth and soil productivity (FAO et al., 2020). Without this “biological diversity” there would be no terrestrial life on earth.

Land use, and land use change as well as management have an impact on soil as a habitat and can decrease the diversity in soil (Bevivino et al., 2014). A decline in soil biodiversity can significantly affect the ability of the soil to function and recover to disturbances like drought, flooding or compaction.

Loss of diversity is measured by changes in amount of specific biomass, or specific species as well as the products of certain activities (e.g. CO₂ or enzymes). The combination of advanced Next-Gen sequencing (NGS) technologies and bioinformatics tools present a new approach to monitor the loss of diversity offering a complete view of microbial communities as indicators of soil health (Lehmann et al., 2020)

Interrelation with other soil threats or SESs

We summarise that the loss of biodiversity is highly correlated with other soil threats, such as soil erosion, carbon loss, compaction, waterlogging, contamination, salinization, soil sealing and nutrient imbalance. (Stolte et al., 2015; Tibbett et al., 2020)

In their study Orgiazzi et al. (2016) discuss the destructive potential of thirteen potential stressors like climate change, soil erosion, soil compaction etc. to soil microorganisms, soil fauna and to soil functions provided by soil organisms. They found that the highest pressure on diversity comes from intensive human exploration e.g. measured by the amount of fertilizer and pesticides used in arable and stocking density in grassland. Further, the losses of organic carbon and land use change (figure 3-5) have an impact on soil microorganisms, soil fauna as well as soil functions. Habitat fragmentation and the use of GMOs were regarded to cause at least harm to the soil diversity.

As a consequence of loss of diversity, the SESs like biomass production and the capacity to control erosion, pollution and pests and diseases are severely reduced. By means of their activities and interactions, soil organisms play a key role for the constant biomass land productivity and for the provision of other ecosystem services related to clean water or greenhouse gas mitigation. In fact, intensive agriculture, leading to habitat disturbance or, in the worst cases, to habitat destruction, has been linked to a substantial loss of soil biodiversity with potentially dramatic consequences for ecosystem service provision, but also global food security and human health (Pulleman et al., 2022).

3.12 Soil drought

Definition, information and remarks about soil threat

Definition

Soil drought is the short-term dryness of surface horizons that leads to agricultural drought, limiting the availability of water for crops and reducing their yields.

Information

Drought conditions during most of the growing season can have a profound impact on soil health. The effect of drought can be noticed very clearly on crop performance when the lack of water availability is severe. This water stress can affect soil chemical, physical, and biological activities that are essential for plant and soil health.

During drought, life in the soil slows down which slows the cycling of nutrients, the stability of soil aggregates can be reduced without the biological by-products produced by soil organisms, the surface of soils can become hard set, with bare powdery surface or cracked and hard, many soils will have high levels of nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) and, some herbicides may persist in the soil (Jenkins et al., 2020). Water is the major medium for up-take of nutrients in plants as a co-result of water uptake. Soil nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) and sulphur (S) may increase during drought as organic matter continues to mineralise after plant growth has become water-limited and fertiliser may carryover from previous applications (Jenkins et al., 2020). These nutrients are concentrated in the topsoil and if erosion occurs the nutrients and their benefits will be lost.

The increase in soil temperature associated with lack of soil moisture has an impact on microbial activities and nutrient processing, important both for biomass and grain production. Microbial activities in soil are generally controlled by soil moisture and temperature. The deviation from the optimum ranges of soil moisture (water field capacity) and soil temperature, which varies for different microbial communities in soil, can alter microbial activity. When soil temperature increases, the activity of soil microorganism increases (provided a minimum critical level of water is available). Hereby the CO₂ emissions increase.

This shift in biological and chemical processes interlinked with soil temperature and moisture during the growing season influences many other relationships that are essential for crop performance, quantitatively and qualitatively, by changing activities that are important to nutrient cycling such as, enzymatic activities, change in soil chemicals concentrations, etc. (Al-Khaisi, 2017).

Remarks

Drought is a natural phenomenon posing severe implications for soil and agricultural yield.

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

SoilCompac will quantify interactions between soil compaction and climate, and present information on how to assess, detect, recover and minimize soil compaction, thereby providing a basis for sustainable soil. The climatic assessment also includes regions prone to drought. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/soilcompac>

Indicators

A set of commonly used indices is reported in Masroor et al. (2022): Surface Water Supply Index; Rainfall Anomaly Index; Standard Precipitation – Evapotranspiration Index; Vegetation Condition Index (VCI) and Temperature Condition Index (TCI). The two latter were elaborated in the study.

Soil moisture index (SMI) and soil moisture anomaly (SMA) are implemented in the Copernicus European Drought Observatory (EDO). SMA is computed from SMI values and used for determining the start and duration of agricultural drought conditions. The main limitation of these indicators is the 5 km resolution.

Translation to non-specialists

Soil drought occurs when soil experiences a strong reduction of soil moisture due to the lack of adequate precipitation and/or irrigation with yield reduction (particularly if it occurs in critical crop stages) up to crop damage with plant death in extreme cases.

Interrelation with other soil threats or SES

Soil erodibility increases with drought duration and decreases after a long favourable precipitation and vegetative growth (Baumhardt and Blanco-Canqui, 2014).

Suggestion: Soil drought indirectly affects the SES hydrological control in terms of infiltration (e.g., due to the absence of vegetation cover that promotes infiltration and reduces evaporation) and the biomass production (plant-available water)

Figure 3-9 some soils are more prone to drought and need to be managed thereafter (@ Ungaro, F. n.a.)

4. Soil Ecosystem services and their indicators

4.1 General

SOIL ECOSYSTEM SERVICE (SES)

is the soil-related subset of Ecosystem Services, directly and quantifiably controlled or provided by soils and their chemical, physical and biological properties, processes and functions.

Adapted, after Paul et al. (2021)

SES are the capacity of natural processes and properties in soils from which we benefit (Calzolari et al., 2016). We recognize the SESs as providing, regulating, supporting or cultural services (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005), directly or indirectly fulfilling human needs (Haines-Young et al., 2012). The capacity of these services depends upon climate, geological, pedological and geographical site parameters, as well as land use and management measures.

In SERENA we focus on the providing SES 'Primary/biomass production' and 'Habitat for Diversity', and the regulating SES 'Climate regulation and soil organic carbon sequestration', 'Hydrological control', 'Erosion control', 'Environmental pollution control' as well as 'Pest and disease control'.

The following sub-chapters give an overview of seven SESs and their indicators discussed in SERENA. Each subchapter starts with a common harmonized definition of the specific SES followed by information about the SES and remarks that were expressed by some project partners related to the SES in their country. In a second part of each subchapter associated indicators to the SES are given. In a third part, the SES is translated to non-soil-specialist. Finally, each subchapter ends with the interrelation with soil threats or other SES. The prioritisation of the SESs within SERENA is the subject of chapter 6.4.

Figure 4-1 SES in summer (@ Ungaro, F. n.a.)

4.2 Primary/biomass production

Definition, information and remarks

Definition

The capacity of soils to supply humans with food, feed, fiber, fuel, wood, pharmaceuticals and biochemical.

Information

Increasing world's population require societies to provide more food for human nutrition. The food supply chain depends on soil quality hence it is necessary to maintain the ecosystems in their actual state or restore degraded soils that are currently not able to provide a wide range of ecosystem services and particularly biomass production. The new European Soil Strategy indicates that EU farmland and grassland provide €76 billion worth of ecosystem services each year and almost 1/3 comes from plant production.

According to CICES (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2019), this ecosystem service, related to the soil, can be divided into biotic and abiotic services. Biotic services are linked to biomass production, in the form of cultivated plants, fungi, algae and bacteria or reared animals for nutritional, material, or energy-source purposes. Abiotic services are related to water supply (groundwater and surface waters). Soils are indisputably an important element of water retention in the environment. However, considering the primary production, soil water can only be used to supply plants with water and to transport nutrients.

In SERENA project, the assessment of ecosystem services will concern agricultural areas. Conducting research on primary/biomass production, the scope of these studies should be clarified. The agricultural areas include not only arable land, but also permanent plantations (orchards, tree nurseries, etc.), meadows and permanent pastures, which are used for the production of biomass for various purposes, e.g. animal feed and organic fertilizer.

Remarks

Six out of sixteen Member States did not provide any information about the studies or experiences on primary/biomass production. Austria and Belgium declared that there are some studies about this soil ecosystem service, and Estonia, France, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, and the Netherlands mentioned that this topic was frequently studied in M3.2 (Michel, 2022).

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

i-SOMPE *“Documentation of innovative soil management practices in Europe will provide information on regional and local practices and conditions. Innovative soil management practices (SMP) and agricultural systems are promoted to enhance ecosystem services in order to minimise soil threats and sustain agriculture in a climate change context.”* Good agricultural soil management practices can have a significant influence on the primary production. Hence, the results of this project would be valuable and helpful to assess this soil ecosystem service. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/i-sompe>

EnergyLink *“Linking crop diversification to microbial energy allocation and organic carbon storage in soils (EnergyLink). EnergyLink aims to improve the understanding on how aboveground plant trait diversity can be used to manage belowground resource use efficiency of the soil microbiome and organic matter persistence in soil.”* This project links carbon sequestration and primary/biomass production and can provide stakeholders with a new approach/tool for the best soil management for efficient food production taking into account the soil conditions under climate change. (<https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/energylink>)

Indicators

According to the research review conducted in the various SERENA tasks, biomass can be calculated by the total amount of plant biomass (in tonnes) that is produced per hectare per year: **t/ha/year** (Ausseil et al., 2013; Dang et al., 2020).

The complex analysis of the primary/biomass production should also consider the biomass of other living organisms (animals, fungi, etc.). However, due to the lack of possibilities to analyse the full spectre of this issue, in SERENA we focus on plant biomass.

The next indicator is linked to the total prize (the currency can be different) of the obtained yields per ton per hectare per year: **€/t/ha/year** (Bastian et al., 2013).

The last indicator is linked to the total prize (the currency can be different) of the obtained yields/per hectare per year: **€/ha/year**.

To enable a yield comparison between crops, another indicator is to transform the biomass dry matter yield into an energy yield, by using energy content coefficients (Dittrich et al., 2017; Obiang Ndong et al., 2021). It is then expressed in 10^7 **kcal/ha/yr** or **J/ha/yr** (Mouchet et al., 2017).

Translation to non-specialists

Considering the functioning of soils in the ecosystem, the majority of people would mention their agricultural use and production of food. After all, soil is the biologically active part of the ecosystem. Hence, they support life growth and most of all, biomass production. Primary production is linked to the potential or possibilities to produce food (crops, wild fruits, feed for livestock, and livestock itself), fiber (timber, cotton, hemp, silk, wood fuel), genetic resources (seeds, etc.), biochemicals, natural medicines, pharmaceuticals, and fresh water. Biomass production is the total amount of living organisms that soils can produce or can support their growth (higher plants, phytoedaphone: bacteria, actinomycetes, fungi and algae, and zooedaphone), however in SERENA we focus on plant biomass.

From agricultural fields the capacity of biomass/primary production is most often given as tons of yield (sometimes as dry matter) or yielded energy within a period of time (year). In a market this can also be given as amount of sales profit per tons of yield. The most common indicators, according to the recent studies can be: tonnes [t], euro [€], kilocalories [kcal], joules [J] or megajoules [MJ] per hectare per year.

Interrelation with other soil threats or SESs

The soil ecosystem service of primary/biomass production might not be directly related to other soil threats or SESs considered within the SERENA project. However, *all soil threats* mentioned can pose severe threats to the primary/biomass production when they exceed certain limits. The SES *pest and disease control* also has a direct influence on the primary/biomass productions, as a too high pressure of pests and diseases will likely cause a reduction of primary/biomass production.

4.3 Habitat for biodiversity

Definition, information and remarks

Definition

An ecosystem able to sustain a community of living organisms which interact with one another, with plants, small animals and soil biota (micro-, meso- and macro-organisms) forming a biological network, controlling numerous soil functions and ecosystem services

Information

Soil is a complex habitat for above- and belowground organisms. It consists of mineral and organic particles where living organisms, including plant roots, microbes, and larger animals inhabit the pore spaces filled with air and/or water. The dynamic formation of soils depends on the interplay of climate, geology, soil life and plants. The process influences and is influenced by soil's chemical and physical properties (De Deyn and Kooistra, 2021).

The heterogeneity of soils across all scales, from nanometers to kilometers, provides an innumerable number of habitats for all kinds of living organisms in space and time. The soil biota is seen as key player in many soil functions, such as nutrient cycling and carbon sequestration (van Leeuwen et al., 2019). Further, it is not necessarily the most productive habitats which have the highest abundance and richness of biota (De Deyn and Kooistra, 2021), but productive soils are depending on a healthy soil habitat where soil biota can decompose and release plant available nutrients, build sustainable micro- and macro aggregates and retain and increase the soil water holding capacity.

FAO et al. (2020) highlight that 99% of world's food supplies depend on land-based production (Figure 4-1). Agricultural systems are designed for biomass production. Modern agricultural methods involve habitat modifying processes such as ploughing and application of fertiliser or/and pesticides.

Figure 4-2, 99% of our food supplies retrieves from soil habitats and mainly agricultural land. © EASAC 2022 (https://easac.eu/fileadmin/_processed_/9/a/csm_cover-bild-master-social-media-wo-logo-small_d029d30298.jpg)

Agricultural management practices affect the soil ecosystem to different degrees and to different extents (Birkhofer et al., 2016). In general, they alter soil environmental properties and disturb the soil structure, leading to loss of soil organic carbon and degrading micro-habitats. Agricultural intensification may impact soil organism abundance, biomass, community structure, species richness, species diversity, functional diversity and distribution (FAO et al., 2020). With increased management intensity the above- and belowground diversity declines. For example, grasslands host higher biodiversity and promote stronger soil organic matter build-up compared to arable fields. In their

study De Deyn and Kooistra (2021) also point out, that through diversification of the plants grown within and surrounding the fields, agricultural ecosystems can be biodiverse habitats and provide the multi-functionality needed for sustainable food production and resilient habitats.

Remarks

The MSs reported at least 41 studies at national and regional level. The goodness of soils as habitat for biodiversity was evaluated by measurements or expert judgment based on land cover, quantity and/or abundance of specific organism or soil parameters like soil pH-value, texture etc. (Michel, 2022)

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

Strongly linked with **MINOTAUR**: which focuses on soil biodiversity patterns and functions across Europe. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/minotaur>

EnergyLink: aims to understand how crop diversification can influence belowground resource of the soil microbiome and organic carbon storage in soils. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/energylink>

TRACE-Soils: focuses, among others, on how different management practices alter soil structure and soil biota, affecting nutrient cycles (carbon dioxide and nitrous oxide emissions, as well as N and P losses). <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/trace-soils>

Indicators

Microbial (Archea, Bacteria, Fungi) biomass (lipid extraction from soil), N, C, (Chloroform fumigation extraction), diversity sequencing, richness/Shannon (OTU or ASV-based diversity), microbial respiration (CO₂ evolution), Nematoda abundance and diversity, mesofauna and macrofauna abundance and diversity, soil feeding activity (bait lamina), litter decomposition (Litter bag).

Further, composition of above- and belowground organism, esp. presence or absence of invasive species and the rate of mortality. Also land use and land cover; soil pH-value, soil texture are used as indicators when describing soil as habitat.

Translation to non-specialists

Soils are habitat of plants and numerous animals, insects and microorganisms, like algae, fungi, bacteria and archaea. These organisms are interlinked with each other and can suppress or support each other. The organisms are dependent on soil as their habitat and affect the soil and thereby also soil ecosystem services (e.g. coarse pores left from roots and/or soil animals which increase water infiltration) by their presence and activities.

Next to presence and mass or number of specific organisms and species also land cover and land use as well as soil parameters like the pH-value or texture are used as indicator for soils as habitat for biodiversity.

Interrelation with other soil threats or SES

The capacity to sustain a biological network among living above and belowground organisms support the production service; erosion control; increases the likeability of a soil to suppress pests and diseases. On the other hand, soil as habitat for biodiversity is threatened by soil erosion, pollution, waterlogging and compaction (Tibbett et al., 2020).

4.4 Erosion control

Definition, information and remarks

Definition

Control of erosion rates is the reduction in the loss of soil material by virtue of the stabilising effects of the presence of plants and animal that mitigates or prevents potential damage to human use of the environment or human health and safety.

In the CICES classification, a general erosion control ES is the “Mass stabilisation and control of erosion rates” (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2019).

Information

Chapter 3.2 described the soil erosion threat. The definition of erosion control as an ES demonstrates the role that soil can play in preventing or limiting soil erosion. Such a reduction provides benefits both to the society – by limiting i) runoff and floods, ii) surface water quality and iii) stabilising mountains watersheds – and to the farmer – by maintaining soil capital necessary to biomass production.

This SES is about proper and sustainable management of soils which results in decreased erosion rate compared to situations where no sustainable management is applied, either through the living parts of the ecosystem (such as plants and soil biota) or through non-living parts of the ecosystem (such as physical soil properties), which may have an effect on the living part of the ecosystem. Purely technological solutions to soil erosion would therefore not be part of this ecosystem service, unless they indirectly result in changes in the ecosystem that do contribute to erosion reduction.

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

The **SCALE** project ‘Strategies for connected landscape elements to reduce water erosion’ focuses on water erosion. In SCALE the ‘connectivity’ principles are considered to identify key linkages between soil loss and associated impacts on carbon cycling, biodiversity and water resources. In addition, the project considers long-term soil erosion monitoring observations in multiple European environmental zones. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/scale>

Indicators

Daroussin et al. (2019), as well as Vari (2021) and Pásztor et al. (2021) considered the ecosystem service of water erosion control to be the amount of soil (as well as soil organic matter) that is retained in presence of vegetation, compared to the amount of soil that would be eroded in absence of vegetation. Daroussin et al. (2019) applied the MESALES model in France to evaluate soil loss in these 2 configurations, whereas Vari (2021) and Pásztor et al. (2021) applied the Universal Soil Loss Equation (USLE; Wischmeier and Smith, 1978) model with and without the C factor for the territory of Hungary; in both cases, the difference was considered as the amount of retained soil. Both the actual and maximum potential vegetation cover were taken into account, to evaluate the actual ES value, and the potential maximum ES value, the latter providing insights to promote some specific management practices. Soil organic matter retention was also calculated in the Hungarian case.

The evaluation of soil loss by water erosion (Universal Soil Loss Equation, USLE, or MESALES model) needs the following soil, climate and landscape properties:

- Clay-, silt-, sand-, organic matter-, CaCO₃ content (K factor)
- Yearly precipitation (R factor)
- DEM (LS factor) Hort

- Land cover (C factor)

Erosion rates values ($t \cdot ha^{-1} \cdot y^{-1}$) were calculated in 3 situations: i) erosion rate with the actual vegetation cover, ii) erosion rate with bare soil everywhere, iii) erosion rate with vegetation everywhere.

The actual SES was then calculated by subtracting i) and ii);

The maximum potential SES was calculated by subtracting iii) and ii): the actual erosion rate.

Capacity of vegetation to reduce erosion risk (adimensional gradient from 0 to 1)

Schulp et al. (2012) calculated the erosion protection ecosystem function as the decrease of erosion risk by vegetation, using indices ranging from 0 to 1 for the protective effects of each land-cover type as provided by Hootsmans et al. (2001). Natural vegetation such as forests provide a high degree of protection against rainfall erosion, while agriculture generally leads to the higher sensitivity of the land surface to the destructive action of intensive rainfall.

Decrease of erosion risk by vegetation (adimensional gradient from 0 to 1)

According to Schulp et al. (2012) the ecosystem service for erosion protection was defined as the decrease of erosion risk by vegetation in utilized areas with a high erosion risk. Erosion risk due to soil and landscape characteristics and rainfall intensity was mapped using a 0–1 index based on the Universal Soil Loss Equation (USLE) (Batjes, 1996). To calculate the ecosystem service for erosion protection, the erosion risk index was multiplied with data from the above mentioned erosion ecosystem function value.

Capacity of ecosystems to avoid soil erosion (adimensional gradient from 0 to 1)

Capacity for ecosystem service provision in a given place and time determine the actual ecosystem service provision, which is a fraction of the total potential soil erosion. This capacity for ecosystem service provision is calculated based on RUSLE model ($es = 1 - C$ factor). It is influenced by both internal drivers (including land management options, forest fires, and urban sprawl) and external drivers (including agricultural policy measures, spatial planning, and climate change) (Guerra et al., 2016). Rendon et al. (2022) refer to this indicator as 'Provision Capacity (PCAP)'. In the assessment of the ecosystem service control of erosion rates, provision capacity (PCAP) is defined as the fraction of the total potential soil erosion that is mitigated by the service provision (Guerra et al., 2014; Steinhoff-Knopp and Burkhard, 2018). Hölting et al. (2019) used the ESTIMAP (Zulian et al., 2014) to quantify the capacity of ecosystems to avoid soil erosion.

Total amount of soil not eroded ($t \cdot ha^{-1} \cdot y^{-1}$ (or equivalent))

Total of the actual ecosystem service provision corresponds to the total amount of ecosystem service provided, measured in ecosystem service providing units (tons of soil not eroded). It varies from season to season and year-to-year depending on the variation of the total potential soil erosion (Guerra et al., 2016). Rendon et al. (2022) used the soil retention indicator expressed by tons of soil not eroded according to (Maes, 2010).

Surface area of natural vegetation with a function of erosion control (ha (weighted area of natural vegetation) ha^{-1} (total NUTS area))

Weighting of the surface area of natural vegetation by the erosion risk estimated with MESALES Model (Modèle d'Evaluation Spatiale de l'ALéa Erosion des Sols - Regional Modelling of Soil Erosion Risk)

Translation to non-specialists

Erosion control is the practice of preventing or controlling wind or water erosion in agriculture, land development, coastal areas, river banks and construction. The erosive process can be mitigated and mostly avoided by protecting and preserving the fragile soil layer and creating a suitable support to vegetation. Effective erosion control measures handle surface runoff and are important techniques in preventing water pollution, soil loss, wildlife habitat loss and damages to human property. The controls often involve the creation of a physical barrier, such as vegetation or rock, to absorb some of the energy of the wind or water that is causing the erosion. Typical practices include planting of trees and quick growing grass on disturbed areas and other means to slow the movement of water across a disturbed site and trap the soil that does get transported by runoff. Indeed, vegetation has the potential to protect the surface against water (raindrop impact and runoff) and wind pressures, and to modify soil hydrology.

Interrelation with other soil threats or SESs

As this ecosystem service basically is a reduction of the soil threat soil erosion, the same links that were described in chapter 3.2 are valid here too. As water is one out of two drivers for erosion, the ES hydrological control is closely linked to soil erosion.

Figure 4-3 Erosion control by cover crops (@ Foldal, C. 2020)

4.5 Hydrological control

Definition, information and remarks

Definition

The capacity of a soil to receive, store, conduct and supply water for subsequent use while minimising the effects of prolonged droughts, flooding and erosion.

(Wall et al., 2020)

Information

Among the regulating soil functions, those affecting the water cycle contribute in providing fundamental ecosystem services, such as the control of floods and droughts (Daily et al., 1997). Hydrological control refers to the capacity of infiltrating rainfalls, storing water and releasing it for plants, and feeding groundwaters.

Soil regulates the fraction of precipitation water that infiltrates, thus regulating runoff, transport of nutrients, pollutants and sediments, and contributing to groundwater recharge. Soil infiltration depends on various factors and soil conditions, such as soil moisture, soil structure, soil stability, soil hydraulic conductivity, but also soil cover and the precipitation characteristics (duration and intensity) (Hillel, 1998). The capacity of the soil to retain water is mostly influenced by its physical properties, texture, porosity, structure, soil mineralogy and soil organic matter content.

Remarks

Indeed, there can be some confusion about the definition of hydrological control, as it can refer also to water purification, all MS use definitions or concepts which avoid this function. The approaches for assessing this service are different, being in some cases based on outputs of deterministic models or on empirical models.

Indicators

As for the retention of water for plant use, the water retention characteristics are used, either measured, modelled or derived with pedotransfer functions. The simplest of these storage-based indicators are available water capacity (AWC, also called plant available water capacity PAWC, mm m^{-1}) and field capacity (FC, mm m^{-1} or $\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$). Based on the retention characteristics, the fraction of functional pore size classes is often determined, based on different definitions and pore size thresholds. Wide-spread examples concentrated on soil drainage are macro-porosity, fraction of transmissive pores or air capacity ($\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$ for all).

Considering the **infiltration capacity and the groundwater recharge**, this is either measured, modelled or estimated with empirical approaches, as e.g. the sum of daily water drainage from the soil, which is assumed to reach the groundwater, as **the saturated hydraulic conductivity** (K_s , mm h^{-1}), or by means of modelled drainage classes.

Translation to non-specialists

Water is needed for plant growth but may cause harm and damage in case of floods. Soil is the interface medium which controls the cycle of precipitation water between these two pathways. Among the most important services soils provide, the hydrological control refers to the capacity of soils of regulating the water cycle. This includes the capacity of infiltrating precipitation, storing and supplying water to plants and crops, and providing water for groundwater recharge.

The indicators used to assess this SES refer to the amount of water (e.g. m^3) stored and eventually supplied, or to the water fluxes within the soil (e.g. mm h^{-1}) and out of soil (e.g., mm yr^{-1}) into groundwater and surface water.

Interrelation with other soil threats or SESs

The hydrological control provided by soil is linked to nearly all the soil ecosystem services, and soil threats. Most importantly in the light of agricultural production is the supply of water to plants, allowing a good primary production. Next to that, a well-drained soil, allowing the infiltration of water, has a direct positive impact on soil erosion risk (and erosion control), waterlogging and salinization. A well-drained soil may also reduce the risk of N_2O emissions from the soil, as these emissions are higher in anaerobic conditions. On the other side, an excessively drained soil may favour water contamination if contaminants are present in the soil environment (e.g. nitrates, nutrient imbalance).

4.6 Environmental pollution control

Definition, information and remarks

Definition

The capacity of soil to sorb, reduce or eliminate the release any content of pollutants from the environment.

(Greiner et al., 2017))

Information

“Soil is a finite resource, meaning its loss and degradation is not recoverable within a human lifespan. Soils affect the food we eat, the water we drink, the air we breathe, our health and the health of all organisms on the planet. Without healthy soils we wouldn’t be able to grow our food” (FAO, 2018).

Soils are able to filter and buffer pollutants like heavy metals and arsenic; organic substances and organic compounds, residues of non-biodegradable pesticides, pharmaceuticals and radionuclides, which, due to their properties and concentrations are considered as potentially hazardous to the environment and/or human health or to impair SESs. Different types of organic substances and compounds are degraded by a wide range of soil microorganisms. Some of the pollutants are safely retained in the soil, preventing their release to other environmental compartments, secondary emission to air and leaching into surface and groundwater. Soil capacity to retain, buffer, filter and degrade contaminants depends on the soil properties (e.g., pH, redox potential, clay content, organic matter content), contaminant physicochemical properties (e.g., polarity, water solubility) as well as environmental factors (soil moisture, temperature) (Biswas et al., 2018; FAO and UNEP, 2021). Generally, a low content of clay and organic matter promotes the bioavailability of contaminants due to limited sorption sites and thus increases the risks of leaching and distribution of contaminants to water and their absorption by plant roots. In the filtering process, pollutants are filtered out of percolation water and are bound by clay minerals or iron oxide in the soil. As for buffering, it neutralizes acidifying sulphur and nitrogen deposits, thus preventing eutrophication and a long-term pH decrease – assuming of course that the soil’s capacity in this regard is not exhausted (UBA, 2017).

The filtering and buffering capacity of soils make them a pollution sink that prevents pollutants from seeping into the groundwater or being taken up by plants. But the extent to which pollutants can be deposited and bound is determined by soil storage capacity. Once the soil’s filtering and buffering capacity is exceeded, the soil releases the stored pollutants, which end up in the groundwater or are taken up by plants – and thus enter the food chain (UBA, 2017).

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

SIREN highlights the buffer and filtering control function of soils as one of the important ecosystem services of soils also addressed by the Green Deal. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/siren>

Indicators

A direct indicator of environmental pollution control is the concentration of various soil contaminants expressed in ppm or mg kg⁻¹ of soil. In addition, the quality and content of soil organic matter, soil pH and clay mineral content, as well as the activity of soil microorganisms - a key factor in the degradation and transformation processes of contaminants in soils - are the most important factors determining the soil's ability to sorb contaminants and prevent their release into the environment.

Translation to non-specialists

The filtering, buffering and transformation of inorganic and organic pollutants is one of the main ecological services that prevent the negative effects of pollutants on the environment (release into the air, leaching into water) and human health (uptake by plants and transfer in the food chain).

Soils are able to absorb and/or decompose pollutants due to their texture, biological activity and chemical properties.

The capacity can be given by the amount or change of concentration of pollutants in a given area.

The capacity is limited by soil depth, soil texture, clay minerals and organic carbon content, as well as by soil biological activity and is greater in a deep fertile loamy soil compared to a shallow sandy soil.

Interrelation with other soil threats or SESs

With the capacity to milder contamination, this ecosystem service is correlated to the soil threat of soil contamination. The retention of contaminants in soils limits their bioavailability and may therefore have an impact on other threats (loss of soil diversity, soil acidification) or soil ecosystem services such as biomass production, habitat for soil biodiversity, water quality protection. The capacity decreases by soil erosion, loss of soil organic carbon or waterlogging as well as by compaction or loss of diversity,

Figure 4-4 agricultural soil with capacity of sorbing and eliminating contaminants (@ Foldal, C. 2012)

4.7 Greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration

Definition, information and remarks

Definition

Greenhouse gas (GHG) and climate regulation is defined as the capacity of a soil to reduce the amount of GHG emissions in the atmosphere (i.e., carbon dioxide, nitrous oxide and methane).

(Van de Broek et al., 2019)

Soil carbon (C) sequestration can be defined by the process of transferring CO₂ from the atmosphere into the soil of a land unit, through plants, plant residues and other organic inputs which are stored or retained in the unit as part of the soil organic matter.

(Lal et al., 2015)

Information

Climate regulation is an important ecosystem function performed by soils based on their key role in regulating global biogeochemical cycles of C and N through the exchange of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and other GHG such as nitrous oxide (N₂O) and methane (CH₄) with the atmosphere (Ciais et al., 2013; Paustian et al., 2016). This function is driven by the balance between the capacity of soils to sequester CO₂ and to promote soil organic C (SOC) storage, and the GHG emissions from soils, especially from agricultural soils.

Soil C sequestration represents a key process in climate regulation, as any ton of CO₂ assimilated by plants and subsequently stored in the soil is removed directly from the atmosphere, at least temporarily, is contributing to climate change mitigation (Amelung et al., 2020). On the other side, land management strategies strongly affect GHG emissions from soils to the atmosphere. Direct management measures, like improved crop rotations, manure and fertilizer management, liming, or indirect processes like T microbial decomposition of plant residues and soil organic matter, N₂O emissions from nitrification and denitrification processes in the soil and CH₄ emissions from peat soils and rice cultivation (McDonald et al., 2021; Oertel et al., 2016; Vermeulen et al., 2012). The abovementioned processes represent the main sources of GHG emissions from agricultural soils (Van de Broek et al., 2019). In EU-27, in 2020, the agricultural sector was responsible for 12.2 % of GHG emissions (EEA, 2020)

An adequate agricultural management strategy can minimize net GHG emissions from agricultural systems and enhance C sequestration, redirecting the net global warming potential balance towards agrosystems that could act as C sinks, or at least reducing GHG emissions associated with agriculture (ADVIENTO-BORBE et al., 2007; Ghimire et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2014; Six et al., 2004). In recent years this issue has received considerable attention in EU, as evidenced by the numerous initiatives that emerged, including the recent European Climate Law, which adopts the goal set out in the European Green Deal for a climate neutral European economy and society by 2050, setting an intermediate target of reducing net GHG emissions by at least 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels (European Climate Law reference). Soil C pool is an important component of the global C cycle, containing more than 3600 Pg of C at 2 m depth (including 2000 Pg of organic C), superior to that of the atmosphere (820 Pg) and biota (620 Pg) pools, but far from the ocean C pool of more than 38000 Pg (Lal, 2020). Historical land degradation, issuing from the conversion of natural ecosystems into managed ecosystems induced the depletion of soil organic carbon stocks by 60-70 %. According to this author, the global C storage potential of agricultural soils can be determined from this historical C loss and, depending on the severity and type of degradation, be estimated at around 178 Pg in soil (84 ppm of atmospheric CO₂ drawdown). Although its potential quantitative determination still represents a debated scientific issue (Janzen et al., 2022; Minasny et al., 2022), soil C sequestration represents an

opportunity to reverse this historical loss by removing C from the atmosphere and storing it back in the soil.

The possibility of increasing the SOC content through agricultural management is widely recognized (Chenu et al., 2019; Lal, 2020), and supported by international initiatives such as the well-known 4p1000 initiative (<https://4p1000.org/>; Minasny et al., 2017; Rumpel et al., 2020), which uses this potential as a basis for promoting management strategies that contribute to increased SOC stocks in agricultural land. In general, the possibility of C sequestration is related to practices where inputs of organic materials to the soil, such as the incorporation of crop residues into the soil after harvest, are modified and/or practices that can affect the sensitivity of organic matter to mineralization, such as planting cover crops in vineyards or converting crops to pasture (Dignac et al., 2017).

However, in some cases, the trade-off from these agricultural management strategies focusing on C sequestration are increased rate of GHG emissions especially those related to N₂O (Gao et al., 2018; Lugato et al., 2018; Van de Broek et al., 2019).

For instance, some meta-analyses on long-term studies have shown that the effect of contrasted tillage strategies on SOC can be dependent on the actual change induced by this practice on crop yields, and thereby C inputs from crop residues (Mary et al., 2020; Virto et al., 2012), but also on climate conditions (Dimassi et al., 2014), which can be inter-related. Despite the positive effect on SOC storage, crop residue incorporation can also increase losses of reactive N in the form of N₂O and NH₃ (Xia et al., 2018).

Furthermore, the C storage potential of soils is not unlimited, as soils have a maximum saturation capacity. This means that C sequestration rates will decrease as a new steady state in the soil C pool is approached, while the management has to remain equal. The determination and existence of the SOC saturation limit of soils is still an open scientific debate (Chenu et al., 2019; Follett, 2001). These authors also remark that the C storage process is reversible so that the C accumulated over the years in the soil can be re-emitted due to changes in management or climate. Therefore, increasing SOC stocks by C sequestration only provides a window of opportunity for reducing and offsetting GHG net emissions related to agricultural activities (Chenu et al., 2019).

Today, there are many efforts focused on the development of strategies to control and reduce GHG emissions associated to agriculture. They are mainly focused on optimization of mineral and organic fertilization strategies to reduce N₂O emissions, water and straw management on paddy soils concerning CH₄, and CO₂ losses by mineralization (Debaeke et al., 2017). For example, N₂O emissions can be reduced by adjusting and localising, in time and space, N doses to crop needs or increasing the proportion of N-fixing crops in crop rotations (Debaeke, Philippe et al., 2017; Sanz-Cobena et al., 2017). The latter allows reducing emissions upstream, as the manufacture of synthetic N fertilisers requires large amounts of energy.

Peat soils are a special case, especially when they are drained (which is needed for most forms of agriculture). In drained peat lands, it is not possible to sequester C, but by adapting management emissions might be reduced, so that a contribution to GHG mitigation is achieved. This usually involves re-wetting, e.g. through raising ditch levels or by using water infiltration systems. Paludiculture can provide a way to still use peat soils for agriculture when groundwater levels have (almost) been raised to surface level. Care should be taken to prevent that decreases in CO₂ emissions are replaced by increases in CH₄ or N₂O emissions.

In order to address this challenge, agricultural management strategies need to be developed, focused not only on promoting C sequestration, but also on reducing GHG emission associated with agricultural management, and must be scaled up and implemented to contribute to climate change mitigation. These strategies must be adapted to local edaphoclimatic conditions and local

management opportunities, where site-specific trade-offs must be considered (Amelung et al., 2020; Chenu et al., 2019; Costantini et al., 2020; Paustian et al., 2016). The site-dependence of the potential response for climate regulation of land-use strategies was indeed explained in detail in the latest IPCC report especially dedicated to land use, agriculture and climate change (Jia et al., 2019).

In the recent years, this question has received considerable attention at EU level through a number of initiatives focused on exploring the potential of agriculture to mitigate CC, within the concept carbon farming (McDonald et al., 2021). On the basis of different forms of farm management that aim to deliver climate mitigation, it proposes new business models aimed at achieving carbon neutrality of the European agricultural sector based on creating markets for carbon trading schemes.

Table 4-1, adapted from (McDonald et al., 2021) shows examples of different agricultural options which impact on the potential of soils in mitigating GHG emissions.

Table 4-1 Agricultural options for mitigating GHG emissions

	Peatland management	Agroforestry	Maintenance and enhancement of SOC in mineral soils	Nutrient Management in crop and grasslands	Livestock and manure management
Agricultural practices for carbon farming	Peatland rewetting and maintenance	Silvopastoral agroforestry; Alley-intercropping	Improved rotations (legumes, cover crops); no-tillage in grasslands; conversion from arable to grassland; grazing practices; organic farming	Improved nutrient planning and application methods of fertilizers	Increased herd and feed efficiency; manure management
Mitigation mechanism	Avoided emissions	Soil C sequestration	Soil C sequestration and avoided emissions	Emission reduction	Emission reduction
Type of change	Land use	Land use and management	Land use and management	Management	Management
Co-benefits for farmer	Potential for paludiculture	Product diversification; soil fertility; crop protection	Improved water holding capacity, soil structure and fertility	Lower input costs	Lower input costs, soil fertility,
Co-benefits for society	Biodiversity, water quality and regulation.	Provision of multiple ecosystem services	Improved soil health, biodiversity, water retention.	Decreased nutrient run-off and N ₂ O and ammonia emissions;	Decreased nutrient run-off, N ₂ O and ammonia emissions.
Risks	Increase of CH ₄ emissions	Non-native species impacts on biodiversity	Impacts on soil health/biodiversity due to biochar and off-farm compost use.	Impacts of nitrification inhibitors on water quality; farmers lock-ins due to investment costs of technology	Animal welfare; impacts on water quality due to feed additives; rebound effects of purely efficiency measures; carbon leakages at different production stages

Furthermore, the Global Soil Partnership released in 2022 the first ever country-driven [Global Soil Organic Carbon Sequestration Potential Map \(GSOCseq\)](#). This map allows for the estimation of topsoil (0-30 cm) soil organic carbon sequestration potential in agricultural areas under four soil management scenarios: a Business as Usual (BAU) scenario and three Sustainable Soil Management (SSM1, SSM2 and SSM3) scenarios. The SSM practices considered in this approach are directly translated into three levels of C input to the soil. The C input of the SSM scenarios was estimated as a

percentual increase over the business as usual (BAU) C input. The use of pre-defined percentages in C input increase allowed the global application of the RothC model. C input increases over the BAU scenario were set at:

- Low (SSM1): 5 percent increase in C input
- Medium (SSM2): 10 percent increase in C input
- High (SSM3): 20 percent increase in C input

The untapped potential of sequestering Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) in agriculturally managed soils as one of the most cost-effective nature-based solutions for climate change mitigation and adaptation has been widely described in recent years. However, unlocking this potential relies on the establishment of strong mechanisms to monitor, report and verify (MRV) changes in SOC stocks.

This GSOCseq map does not take into account technical and economic constraints which implies that it is less useful as a policy instrument or as a basis for indicators.

In contrast to GSOCseq, EJP SOIL project CarboSeq (2021-2025) does take into account these technical and economic constraints in the calculation of the feasible SOC sequestration potential. This is an important difference between GSOCseq and CarboSeq and implies that the resulting maps of CarboSeq are more relevant as indicators and policy instruments.

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

CarboSeq There is a strong link especially to WP 9: Modelling SOC-sequestration potentials. The aim of the CarboSeq project is to estimate the feasible SOC sequestration potential considering technical and economic constraints. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/carboseq>

INSURE is looking at re-wetting of peat soils and the effects of this on emissions of GHG in order to improve the understanding of element cycling controls in rewetted ecosystems. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/insure>

SOMMIT (Sustainable Management of soil Organic Matter to Mitigate Trade-offs between C sequestration and nitrous oxide, methane and nitrate losses) aims to evaluate trade-offs and synergies between soil C sequestration, nitrous oxide, methane and nitrate losses as affected by soil management options aimed at increasing soil C storage. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/ommit>

MINOTAUR (Modelling and mapping soil biodiversity patterns and functions across Europe): aims to provide indicators for monitoring soil biodiversity and associated functions and for evaluating the vulnerability of soils to climate change. These indicators will help to understand how agricultural practices can contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation at regional and national levels across the EU. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/minotaur>

Road4Schemes: Assess of different opportunities for developing schemes for carbon farming and additional ES payments and outline a roadmap for their implementation at local and regional level. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/road4schemes>

Indicators

Feasible SOC-sequestration potentials resulting from the EJP Soil CarboSeq project: estimation of topsoil (0-30 cm) SOC sequestration potential in agricultural areas under four soil management scenarios. ($\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{y}^{-1}$)

GHG emissions from agricultural soils (CO_2 , N_2O and CH_4). ($\text{Mg CO}_2 \text{ eq. ha}^{-1} \text{y}^{-1}$)

Indicators applied in the assessment of climate regulation ecosystem services are commonly associated to the net balance of atmospheric carbon fluxes, and to monitoring and modelling soil organic carbon changes.

Positive changes in SOC stocks. ($\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{y}^{-1}$)

Translation to non-specialists

Climate regulation is an important ecosystem function performed by soil based on the influence that ecosystems have on the global climate by emitting GHG and by extracting carbon dioxide from the atmosphere through C sequestration.

On the one hand, agriculture represents a source of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, by emitting CO_2 , N_2O , and CH_4 . These emissions take place mainly from agricultural soils, due to natural processes that are enhanced by land management for agricultural production, such as intensive fertilization and livestock strategies. On the other hand, soils can sequester C from the atmosphere, so when the C input into the soil (from plants and other organic residues) is greater than the loss of soil organic carbon (SOC), the stock of SOC increases, improving soil quality and fertility.

One of the challenges of the agricultural sector and policies is to minimize GHG emissions from agriculture while promoting C sequestration to turn agricultural soils into net C sinks. A better understanding of soil processes and, therefore a further optimization of land-uses and agricultural management at field and farm levels can certainly play an important role in exploring the climate regulation function of agricultural soils. For instance, agricultural peat soils are a special case as it is not possible to store more carbon in drained peat soils. However, a reduction of emissions is possible, thus contributing to climate mitigation.

Indicators and methods used in the assessment of climate regulation ecosystem services are commonly associated to the net balance of atmospheric carbon fluxes, normally expressed as annual carbon sequestration rate ($\text{Mg C ha}^{-1} \text{y}^{-1}$) or in annual emissions rate ($\text{Mg CO}_2 \text{ eq. ha}^{-1} \text{y}^{-1}$), and to monitoring actual and modelling potential C stocks (Mg C ha^{-1}) and/or C stocks changes ($\text{Mg C ha}^{-1} \text{y}^{-1}$).

Interrelation with other soil threats or SESs

There is a strong correlation between the SES of 'Greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration' with the ST 'Soil organic carbon loss'. Carbon sequestration will bend the curve of soil organic carbon loss. Next to that, an increase in SOM, and thereby SOC, has the potential to improve several aspects of soil quality, such as an improved soil structure, water holding capacity, nutrient binding and soil biodiversity. This can thereby contribute positively to the soil threats of 'soil erosion', 'nutrient imbalance', 'waterlogging', 'soil compaction', and 'loss of diversity'. Additionally, it can positively contribute to all of the mentioned soil ecosystem services. However, it must be said that this can be beneficial, but certainly does not solve these issues on its own and an integrated approach is required for that.

There is also a negative correlation (that is, a trade-off) between the SES 'Greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration' and the SES "Biomass Provisioning". For example, the supply of nutrients to crops from soil due to the decomposition of soil organic matter, leads also to CO_2 emissions from the SOC pools. Moreover, the mineralised N is not only a source of plant nutrients but also a substrate for the processes of nitrification and de-nitrification, leading to a potential increase of N_2O from soils.

4.8 Pest and disease control

Definition, information and remarks

Definition

Capacity of soil to prevent or control pests and diseases through soil biological activities and/or chemical/physical soil properties

(adapted from FAO, 2022b)

Information

Plant pests and diseases represent an enormous problem for agriculture production, causing both quantitative and qualitative damages to crop production (Gardi and Jeffery, 2009). However, a complex set of soil organisms can compete directly or indirectly with pests and disease-causing organisms. In general, plants surrounded by a greater diversity of microbes in their root structure have greater fitness and resilience against pests and pathogens (FAO et al., 2020).

The use of chemical pesticides has a significant impact on air and water quality, natural ecosystems and causes human health problems. Therefore, the European Union recently assigned to reduce the use of chemical pesticides in Europe by 50% within 2030 (EC, 2020b). Hereby, restoring agricultural soil to support beneficial organisms that attack, repel, or otherwise antagonize disease-causing pathogens will be of uppermost importance. Beneficial organisms can be added directly, through inoculation or the soil environment can be made more favorable for them, through correct agronomic management (Gardi and Jeffery, 2009).

Plant diseases result when susceptible hosts and disease-causing pathogens meet in a favorable environment. If any one of these three conditions is not met, the disease does not start or spread (Gardi and Jeffery, 2009). The interactions of soil organisms, directly and indirectly through competitive, facilitative, mutualistic, pathogenic or predatory effects, affect the overall structure of the soil food web; these interactions are self-reinforcing and self-regulating processes that lead to emergent community properties such as community stability and biological control or biocontrol (FAO et al., 2020).

The mechanisms by which soils are suppressive to different pathogens are not always clear but may involve biotic and/or abiotic factors and may vary with the pathogen. For instance, strains of *Fusarium oxysporum* that are non-pathogenic can be superior competitors for carbon and root colonization sites (FAO et al., 2020). In most cases, however, it appears that they operate primarily by the presence in such soils of one or several microorganisms antagonistic to the pathogen. Such antagonists, where volatile or non-volatile substances produced by one organism, such as enzymes or other metabolites, kill or inhibit the growth of another organism or through competition for food, or by direct parasitizing of the pathogen, hinder the pathogen to reach high enough populations to cause severe disease. Many types of organisms are involved in creating and maintaining the soil structure that is important to water dynamics in soil (AGRIOS, 2005).

The Figure 4.2 from Stavi et al. (2016) describes how chemical pest control measures effectively control pest and diseases and simultaneously improve water availability and yield. The tradeoffs are reduced environmental pollution control and a decline of soil organic carbon in the long term. Organic farming on the other hand, has to rely on mechanical and soil-born suppression of pests and pathogens.

Fig. 5 Spider chart of pest management's impact on soil functions and ecosystem services. Impacts are separately presented for the three levels of intensity of pest management, including chemical, integrated, and organic. The major soil functions and ecosystem services are graded for each of the pest management intensities according to the scale of the following: 1 for low score, 2 for moderate score, and 3 for high score

Figure 4-5 Impact of different intensities of pest management on ecosystem services (form Stavi et al. 2016)

Stavi et al. (2016) concluded, whereas the organic farming system strengthens the environmental pollution control and content of soil organic carbon, the risk of crop failure due to pests and weeds are quite likely. At last, the integrated system preformed the best in this study. This integrated system relies on a flexible use of mechanical, cropping (crop rotations, catch crops etc), as well as biological and chemical (low toxic) measures (Stavi et al., 2016).

The interactions of soil organisms, directly and indirectly through competitive, facilitative, mutualistic, pathogenic or predatory effects, affect the overall structure of the soil food web; these interactions are self-reinforcing and self-regulating processes that lead to emergent community properties such as community stability and biological control or biocontrol. Biocontrol of plant disease is the reduction in the numbers and activity of a plant pathogen or pest, using one or more organisms. This process often occurs below ground within plant roots, at the rhizosphere, or more generally within bulk soil (FAO et al., 2020).

Under the auspices of the iSQAPER project, Bongiorno et al. (2019) compared the pathogen-suppressiveness (with a bioassay protocol targeting *Phytophthora ultimum*) action of soils subjected to different management practices in several soils from Europe belonging to different pedoclimatic conditions. They found that although pathogen-suppressiveness was more strongly related to site conditions, the influence of practices such as non-tillage and organic farming increased pathogen suppressiveness. This highlights two things, one the importance of soil management to provide such service and how it could have a positive effect on the reduction in the use of pesticides, secondly that we need to improve the understanding of the mechanisms related to soil pest suppressiveness in order to be able to better operationalise this ecosystem service (Bongiorno et al., 2019)

Link with other EJP SOIL projects

MINOTAUR aims to provide models, maps and policy-relevant indicators with validated reference values for monitoring soil biodiversity and associated functions. The project will collaborate with relevant EU research projects, international soil biodiversity networks and programs to harmonize and integrate soil biodiversity data and contribute to support long-term harmonized EU soil information and international reporting. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/minotaur>

TRACE-Soils analyses existing knowledge on how management practices shift soil structure and soil biota, how trade-offs and synergies link to structural and biological factors in long-term experiments. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/trace-soils>

SOMMIT is aiming on Sustainable Management of soil Organic Matter to Mitigate Trade-offs between C sequestration and nitrous oxide, methane and nitrate losses. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/ommit>

AGROECOSeqC is working on studying the main actors involved in main biogeochemical processes. The challenge to investigate the underlying mechanisms promoting the synchrony between plant demand and nutrient supply by soil microbiome, with the aim to build sustainable agricultural systems where plant, soil fauna and microbial diversity are key drivers to reduce nutrient losses, GHG emission, and increase C sequestration in soil. <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/agroecoseqc>

Indicators

diversity/richness, abundance, composition of pests or antagonist and Plant Growth Promoting Organisms (PGPOs); fungi:bacteria; presence/absence of invasive species; mortality

Translation to non-specialists

Numerous soil organisms interact as supporter and suppresser of each other. Moreover, soil chemical and physical properties can be better or worse for pests and pathogens. In a healthy soil pests and pathogens are suppressed by the soil organisms and soil properties.

Evaluation of soil organism abundance and composition as well as soil parameters like e.g. soil pH-value or bulk density are used to describe the capacity of soils to control pests and diseases.

One out of 7 major soil functions listed in the Thematic Strategy for Soil Protection of the European Union (European Commission, 2006a) is related to boosting the biodiversity pool. Soil is a living system. The variety of life below ground always exceeds that above. Soil organic matter content is of great importance for abundance of soil inhabitants. The more fertile the soil, the more favourable conditions for a diversity of living organisms are encountered. Unfortunately, not all soil living organisms are favourable for human. The most damage for agricultural activity is caused by soil-born fungal pathogens which are responsible for wilt, root rots, club rot and blight disease. Bacteria are less common pathogens, while viruses are rare. Nematodes are prevailing on or inside plant roots. To control diseases, pests and parasites by soil biological activity and other living organisms is one of the most important ecosystem services provided by natural soil ecosystem function.

Interrelation with other soil threats or SESs

This SES is strongly connected to biomass production, soil physical state improvement-soil porous space networking, soil aggregate formation, soil as habitat and the soil threats soil erosion, loss of soil carbon, loss of diversity, soil pollution and to a lesser extent also to physical and chemical impacts of salinization; waterlogging and compaction. Of course, soil sealing terminates also this SES. Soil-born microorganisms are the source of unique medical products of natural origin as well.

5. Soil bundles and their indicators

5.1 General

SOIL ECOSYSTEM SERVICE / SOIL THREAT BUNDLE

A set of ecosystem services, soil threats, or the combination of the two, that appear together repeatedly in time or space, as related to a specific context.

Adapted, after Potchin-Young et. al., 2018, MAES initiative

The way in which the term ecosystem service bundle (and terms related to them such as SESs synergies or tradeoffs) is used in the literature is rather vague (Berry et al., 2016). This comes in part from the loose way in which spatio-temporal co-occurrence of SES can be interpreted (for a recent review on interpretations of the term SES bundle and methods to define them see Saidi and Spray (2018)). In general, the term makes reference to the fact that SES interact at space and time. Mouchet et al. (2014) have highlighted that the definite criteria to define bundles should be the observation of patterns or regularities in the way such SESs relations occur in space and time. With respect to causes and drivers, two general kinds of these SESs interactions are often described: one where SESs co-occur spatio-temporally, but with no causal link or common driver (one can think of situations where cultural SES depend on historic context rather than common biophysical drivers); and the other where the SESs have a causal link or share a common driver (e.g., a negative relationship or trade-off where harvest of wood in a forest that in turn reduces soil C in the long-term). On the other hand, with respect to the co-variation in SESs, the interactions more commonly highlighted are either synergistic (e.g., the increase in the provision of one ES enhances the provision of other SESs) or trade-offs (the increase in the provision of one SES reduces the provision of other SESs). It is important not to confound the bundle term with that of multi-functionality, the latter referring to the supply of several SESs in a certain spatial unit or by certain ecological system.

Methodologically, Mouchet et al. (2014) divides the bundle analysis process in 3 stages: (1) spatially-explicit determination of SESs (a temporal approach would be desirable to make relationships dynamic, but these kinds of exercises are rare given data availability), (2) analysis of relationships among SESs at focus, and (3) bundles' "detection" and interpretation. There is no current consensus regarding what techniques to apply during these different stages of bundle analysis. For instance, (leaving stage 1 aside), SESs relationships (stage 2) have been analysed with very different methods, from simple spatial congruence analysis (e.g., percentage of space where SESs co-occur) or correlation coefficients, to spatially explicit tools such as spatial indexes which define hotspots or multivariate dimension reduction techniques such as principal component analysis (Mouchet et al., 2014; Saidi and Spray, 2018; Schröter and Remme, 2016). The third stage, that of bundles detection, has been performed usually with multivariate clustering techniques (e.g., k-means, self-organising maps) or radar charts (Mouchet et al., 2014; Raudsepp-Hearne et al., 2010; Saidi and Spray, 2018). As part of the bundle's detection/interpretation step, it is key to determine the drivers of those identified bundles (either socio-economic, biophysical, or both). For this purpose, techniques such as multiple regression, or their multivariate equivalents (canonical correspondence analysis or redundancy analysis) have been employed to establish causal relationships (Mouchet et al. 2014).

Nonetheless the lack of clear definitions, it has been shown that the concept has potential to be incorporated in the kit of tools to evaluate land management and environmental policy decision-making. Part of the attractiveness of the concept lies in its capacity to provide insights on both how management/policy strategies can enhance the provision of multiple SESs (by focusing on synergistic

SESs in a bundle) or can identify situations where the enhancement of one SES is detrimental to the provision of other SESs (by focusing on trade-offs or SESs in a bundle).

It is also worth noting that there are very few studies which have focused on relationships and identification of bundles in SESs (Greiner et al., 2017) and even fewer that have set to analyse the relationships between SES's and soil threats (see below for soil threats).

Non-technical description of bundle

The concept of soil bundles likely has its origins in the economic literature. In economics, a bundle of goods or services refers to the case when multiple goods/services are sold as if they were only one (as when one buys a meal and a drink and gets both as a single unit or pack). In this sense, a soil bundle can be thought as soil threats and/or SES occurring together on a regular basis, but not always in the same amount (rate). Thus, they can occur either synergistic or antagonistic (trade-offs).

In their review of soil threats in Europe, Stolte et al. (2015) also provided information on which soil threats are affecting each other and are thus likely to occur together. In SERENA terminology these soils threats can then be considered to be bundles of soil threats. Table 5-1 indicates the interrelationships between soil threats that were identified by Stolte et al (2015). The table shows how a certain soil threat impacts other soils threats (in the rows) and how it is being impacted by other soil threats (in the columns). For example, the table shows that soil erosion has a strong impact on desertification, and is strongly impacted by compaction. It can be seen that different soil threats are linked to other soil threats to different degrees. For example, soil biodiversity decline is impacted by all other soils threats, while soil sealing is not impacted by any of the other soil threats (which make sense as sealing does not result from soil processes, but solely from human action)

Table 5-1 Interactions between soil threats. The size of the dot indicates whether the impact is small, medium or large. Red indicates that the threat is worsened, while green indicates it is reduced (from Stolte et al 2015).

Soil threat	Water erosion	Wind erosion	SOM decline peat soils	SOM decline mineral soils	Compaction	Sealing	Contamination	Salinization	Desertification	Flooding and landslides	Biodiversity decline
Water erosion			●	●			●		●	●	●
Wind erosion			●	●			●	●	●		●
SOM decline peat soils	●	●								●	●
SOM decline mineral soils	●	●			●				●		●
Compaction	●									●	●
Sealing	●				●		●	●		●	●
Contamination	●	●									●
Salinization	●	●	●	●			●		●		●
Desertification		●		●				●			●
Flooding and landslides	●			●	●		●	●			●
Biodiversity decline											

As information on soil bundles is very scarce, only a few examples of soil bundles and their associated indicators are given in the following chapters.

5.2 SDG indicator 15.3.1 : land degradation

Definition, information and remarks about soil bundle

All information about the SDG indicator 15.3.1 is given in the metadata repository of the UN sustainable development goals: <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/metadata/>. This chapter gives the most relevant information relevant for the SERENA project.

The goal of the SDG indicator 15.3.1 is to protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss.

The target of the SDG indicator 15.3.1 is to combat desertification, restore degraded land and soil, including land affected by desertification, drought and floods, and strive to achieve a land degradation-neutral world by 2030.

Land degradation is defined as the reduction or loss of the biological or economic productivity and complexity of rain fed cropland, irrigated cropland, or range, pasture, forest and woodlands resulting from a combination of pressures, including land use and management practices. This definition was adopted by and is used by the 196 countries that are Party to the UNCCD (United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification. 1994. Article 1 of the Convention Text) (Figure 5-1).

Land Degradation Neutrality (LDN) is defined as a state whereby the amount and quality of land resources necessary to support ecosystem functions and services and enhance food security remain stable or increase within specified temporal and spatial scales and ecosystems (decision 3/COP12) (2 http://www2.unccd.int/sites/default/files/sessions/documents/ICCD_COP12_20_Add.1/20add1eng.pdf).

Figure 5-1: Operational definition of land degradation and linkage with the sub-indicators (<https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/metadata/files/Metadata-15-03-01.pdf> as modified from Dominati et al. 2010)

Indicators

Indicator 15.3.1: Proportion of land that is degraded over total land area

SDG indicator 15.3.1 is a binary - degraded/not degraded - quantification based on the analysis of available data for three sub-indicators to be validated and reported by national authorities. The sub-indicators (Trends in Land Cover, Land Productivity and Carbon Stocks) were adopted by the UNCCD's governing body in 2013 as part of its monitoring and evaluation approach.

The method of computation for this indicator follows the “One Out, All Out” statistical principle and is based on the baseline assessment and evaluation of change in the sub-indicators to determine the extent of land that is degraded over total land area.

The One Out, All Out principle is applied taking into account changes in the sub-indicators which are depicted as (i) positive or improving, (ii) negative or declining, or (iii) stable or unchanging. If one of the sub-indicators is negative (or stable when degraded in the baseline or previous monitoring year) for a particular land unit, then it would be considered as degraded subject to validation by national authorities.

The measurement unit for this indicator is the spatial extent (hectares or km²) expressed as the proportion (percentage or %) of land that is degraded over total land area.

Sub-indicator Land cover

Land cover refers to the observed physical cover of the Earth's surface which describes the distribution of vegetation types, water bodies and human-made infrastructure. It also reflects the use of land resources (i.e., soil, water and biodiversity) for agriculture, forestry, human settlements and other purposes. This sub-indicator serves two functions for SDG indicator 15.3.1: (1) changes in land cover may point to land degradation when there is a loss of ecosystem services that are considered desirable in a local or national context; and (2) a land cover classification system can be used to disaggregate the other two sub-indicators, thus increasing the indicator's policy relevance.

Sub-indicator Land productivity

Land productivity refers to the total above-ground net primary production (NPP) defined as the energy fixed by plants minus their respiration which translates into the rate of biomass accumulation that delivers a suite of ecosystem services. This sub-indicator points to changes in the health and productive capacity of the land and reflects the net effects of changes in ecosystem functioning on plant and biomass growth, where declining trends are often a defining characteristic of land degradation.

Sub-indicator Carbon stock

Carbon stock is the quantity of carbon in a “pool”: a reservoir that has the capacity to accumulate or release carbon and is comprised of above- and below-ground biomass, dead organic matter, and soil organic carbon. In UNCCD decision 22/COP.11, soil organic carbon (SOC) stock was adopted as the metric to be used with the understanding that this metric will be replaced by total terrestrial system carbon stocks, once operational. SOC is an indicator of overall soil quality associated with nutrient cycling and its aggregate stability and structure with direct implications for water infiltration, soil biodiversity, vulnerability to erosion, and ultimately the productivity of vegetation, and in agricultural contexts, yields. SOC stocks reflect the balance between organic matter gains, dependent on plant productivity and management practices, and losses due to decomposition through the action of soil organisms and physical export through leaching and erosion.

Evaluation

(Schillaci et al., 2022) evaluated the performance of the SDG 15.3.1 indicator for the European Union. They concluded that its further improvement can benefit the evaluation of the impact of EU policy outcomes toward the LDN, by providing a standard tool for every Member State to analyse their situation and trends in a systematic way. A country-scale assessment (Akinyemi et al., 2021) reported that although the essential data for SDG 15.3.1 are freely available, they are not suitable to report policy action at the country-level because of their coarse spatial resolution.

5.3 EU indicator soil health

Definition, information and remarks about soil bundle

Definition

“Soils are healthy when they are in good chemical, biological and physical condition, and thus able to continuously provide as many of the following ecosystem services as possible:

- provide food and biomass production, including in agriculture and forestry;
- absorb, store and filter water and transform nutrients and substances, thus protecting groundwater bodies;
- provide the basis for life and biodiversity, including habitats, species and genes;
- act as a carbon reservoir;
- provide a physical platform and cultural services for humans and their activities;
- act as a source of raw materials;
- constitute an archive of geological, geomorphological and archaeological heritage”

Source : EU Soil Strategy for 2030 (European Commission, 2021a)

Indicators

The Soil Mission implementation plan provides some information about how to determine the overall soil health of a given soil. Once indicators have been measured for a given soil they have to be compared with threshold or standard values that separate healthy from unhealthy conditions. Such considerations are land use and climate specific and cannot be generalized. Work will be needed to define such thresholds or standards for each indicator for each soil type set within a land use and climate context using an agreed standard approach.

Methods for their integration to determine if a soil meets or falls below the threshold / standard and thus if a soil can be defined as ‘healthy’ or “unhealthy’ also requires further testing and a standard method agreed upon. Different health categories above or below this threshold / standard can also be defined to indicate the relative state of soil health to help inform the urgency and magnitude of action needed. This integration into an overall measure of soil health is critical to be able to monitor the improvements in soil health by 2030.

Different approaches for this integration are already used operationally for other natural resources e.g. the one out/all approach for surface waters in the Water Framework Directive, with various new potential approaches also proposed for soils (e.g. Bonfante et al. 2020). The suitability of options needs to be robustly tested and an approach agreed.

When thresholds for any indicator are exceeded, a soil is below the agreed threshold / standard context-specific management actions have to be considered to improve conditions relating to the specific issue(s) which has caused failure. Evidence from experiences obtained at living labs or lighthouses in the area can be helpful here. Continuation of monitoring can then be used to track success of actions taken.

The concept and an indicator of soil health are still under construction by the European Commission. It will be part of the Soil Health Law which is foreseen for mid-June 2023.

5.4 Examples of concepts for soil bundles from the national/regional level

France: evaluation of bundles of SES over the agricultural production zone in Northern France

Analysis of trade-offs and synergies between SES and their underlying drivers is a main issue in SES research. The analysis is complex and requires innovative analytical approaches. To analyse bundles of soil ecosystem services in order to define trade-offs and synergies, France developed an original approach by using both a multivariate regression tree (MRT) and spatial mapping. This approach was developed on the main cropping region in France (mainly the Paris basin of production), over 15296 situations of productions, by combining soil, climate, crop sequences and management data from the French National Ecosystem Assessment. The methodological approach is based on a crop modelling during 30 years over each situation of production (Figure 5-2). SES evaluation were mean values over 30 years.

By using this methodology, the relationships between 6 SES were determined:

- **Agricultural production** which corresponds to the ‘biomass production’ SES in SERENA;
- **Water provision to crops** and **blue water provision** which can be considered as 2 sub-ecosystem services of the ‘hydrological control’ SES of SERENA;
- **Climate regulation** which corresponds to the ‘Greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration’ SES of SERENA;
- **Nitrogen provision to crops**;
- **Water quality regulation**;

Figure 5-2 Method used to evaluate relationships between SES in Northern France (from Obiang Ndong et al. (2020))

Several soil and production characteristics enabled to create homogeneous groups throughout the investigated region: i) the frequency of cover crops in the rotation, ii) the soil pH, iii) the frequency of sugar beet in the rotation.

The results demonstrated that water quality regulation, nitrogen provision to crops, and climate regulation have synergistic relationships in production situations in the North-eastern region of the

study area due to the types of crop rotation, frequency of cover crops in the crop rotation, the soil pH, and the soil available water capacity (Figure 5-3).

We also identified that cover crops, while promoting water quality regulation, nitrogen provision to crops and climate regulation, can also drive a trade-off between two key water-related services: water provision to crops and blue water provision.

By capturing non-linear relationships and threshold effects, the MRT-based approach overcomes the main limitations of classic statistical approaches, and provides spatially explicit, simple and intuitive results to interpret, especially for non-scientists

Figure 5-3 bundles of ecosystem services and associated maps for the 6 SES evaluated (from Obiang Ndong et al. (2021))

Belgium: Brussels Soil Quality Index (BSQI) a soil bundle for local conditions

The Brussels Soil Quality Index is a tool to heighten awareness of the importance of soil and the roles it plays in the proper function of our environment and ultimately of our society. The soil provides the society and the environment with a whole range of services, such as the substrate used to cultivate plants at the bottom of the food chain, the filtration of rainwater and the storage of atmospheric carbon. This index is part of the Good Soil strategy, which aims to protect and improve soil quality in the Brussels-Capital Region.

Soil quality in the BSQI is the condition of the soil that enables it to perform the ecosystem functions it supports. This quality incorporates chemical, physical and biological considerations.

The BSQI is calculated on the local level and it is based on a quantitative analysis of about ten soil parameters. For each study zone, which may include one or more plots, the expert in charge of defining the BSQI must comply with the following procedure:

- a. Definition of on-site homogeneous zones from the soil perspective based on the geophysical, pedological and historical characteristics of the zone in question;

- b. Soil sampling and field observations within each homogeneous area of the site;
- c. Field measurements and laboratory analysis of soil samples;
- d. Calculation of BSQI for each zone and interpretation of the BSQI;
- e. Calculation of the global BSQI for each parcel;
- f. Analysis of on-site ecosystem services and threats based on the data collected.

For each homogenous zone separately, points from 1 to 5 are allocated to each observation or measurement. Starting from these points, the global Brussels soil quality Index is calculated as:

$$BSQI_i^{Pro} = \frac{\sum(P_i)}{N_p} * \frac{100}{5}$$

Where

- $BSQI_i^{Pro}$: Indicator of the quality of Brussels soils within a homogeneous zone i
- P_i : Points allocated to each parameter of the homogeneous zone i
- N_p : Total amount of measured parameters

A penalty factor is applied to the soil quality per homogeneous zone if low quality backfill or pollution is present.

This BSQI is an awareness-raising tool that allows project managers to integrate the concept of soil quality into their urban development project designs from the outset. A map is generated with the BSQI of each homogeneous zone (Figure 5-4). Already sealed areas or not included in the BSQI (purple areas on the map).

Figure 5-4 typical representation for a fictitious case with 5 homogeneous zones

In addition to the global Brussels soil quality index and based on the field measurements and observations made, the performance of each ecosystem service within each homogenous area is calculated. The services are grouped into the following classes:

- Supply services (production of drinking water, food);

- Regulation services (surface water filtration, atmospheric carbon sequestration);
- Cultural services (preservation of archaeological assets, support for green spaces)
- Support services (sheltering fauna and flora, supporting constructions)

The information is condensed in a summary table for the whole area. In this table, a colour-coded system allows the reader to quickly identify which ecosystem services are affected by soil and which are not. The expert will also produce one or more maps of the study zone to show the spatial variability (between homogeneous zones) of SES.

Finally, also a table of the threats affecting soils in the study zone is attached to the BSQI report.

More information can be found on the website of the BSQI index

(<https://leefmilieu.brussels/themas/bodem/good-soil/index-voor-bodemkwaliteit-brussel/de-brusselse-bodemkwaliteitsindex-voor-0>) or in the English summary of the BSQI index (<https://alfresco.environnement.brussels/share/s/2Kg7K5zqSLi0nHpqo4biCQ>).

Lithuania, Latvia and Estonia: LIFE Viva Grass

The LIFE Viva Grass project (<https://vivagrass.eu/>) was done from June 2014 until April 2019, involving researchers and practitioners from the Baltic countries. The resulting Viva Grass tool offers the spatial visualisation SES bundles and trade-offs as well as hotspot and coldspot areas, which provides an added value in the land-use planning.

In LIFE Viva Grass, the trade-offs, bundles and hotspots analyses constitute the core of Tier 2 and allow for a holistic evaluation of the impacts of management decisions and policies in multiple ES provided by grasslands. The aim of displaying ES bundles in the Viva Grass viewer is to help the tool users to identify specific locations where several ES (bundles) are likely to respond similarly to different management options.

To find out how ES bundle together, a Principal Components Analysis was applied to the ES matrix. The principal components analysis revealed 3 main components which correspond to three bundles:

Habitats bundle: 4 ES interact in this bundle: Herbs for medicine, pollination and seed dispersal, maintaining habitats and global climate regulation. The increase in one of the services in this bundle usually means an increase in the other two services. For example, in species rich grasslands, we are also likely to find a wide range of herbs with a medicinal value. Moreover, grassland management practices that aim to increase biodiversity, such as the reduction or complete elimination of ploughing and fertilization, also increase the carbon sequestration capacity of soils, which is a key service for the regulation of climate.

Production bundle: This bundle is formed by 4 ES closely related to the productivity of ecosystems: reared animals and their outputs, fodder, biomass for energy and cultivated crops. In this particular bundle, the underlying ecosystem function that drives the production of the four ES is the net primary production, or biomass production. Therefore, the increase in one of the services in this bundle usually means an increase in the other two services. However, biomass for energy not only depends on the productivity of grasslands, but also on the calorific potential of grassland species. At the same time, it shall be noted, that even the potential of the four services is based on the same underlying function - productivity, the actual use of ES can exclude each other (i.e. biomass for energy and cultivated crop production can exclude grazing or fodder production)

Soils bundle: The 5 ecosystem services that form this bundle are related with the role of soil functions in ecosystem processes: Control of erosion rates, chemical condition of fresh waters, bio-

remediation, filtration/storage/accumulation by ecosystems and weathering processes-soil fertility. The increase in one of the services in this bundle usually means an increase in the other two services.

Beyond simply identifying ES bundles, it is important to visualise their spatial configuration in order to incorporate the concept into planning processes. In LIFE Viva Grass, grassland was mapped as belonging to a certain bundle if all ES in the bundle in that particular grassland scored above average (Figure 5-5).

Figure 5-5 Grassland ES bundles in a Viva Grass pilot area: Lääne County (West Estonia)

Lithuania: SOC as super indicator or bundle

Soils exhibit a variety of functions. They are related to inherent (soil texture, mineralogy) and dynamic soil properties (physical, chemical, biological etc.) which, in turn, are the result of natural factors and anthropogenic activity (Bongiorno, 2020).

Most of the soils in Lithuania are morainic by origin. The low organic matter content in the soil is the main feature and remains the most relevant problem to improve the productivity of agricultural soils. The content of humus ($\text{humus}/1.724=\text{SOC}$) within 0-20 cm layer of mineral soils rarely exceeds 3-4 % (totals to 7.2 % of the area of mineral soils). One third of soils in Lithuania has very low (<1 %) and low (1.1-2.0 %) content of humus. It generally ranges from 1.0 % to 3.0 %. SOC loss is of great importance on morainic soils. According to our research data, SOC within 10 cm layer in tillable land is about 3.1-3.4 times lower than in the forest soil. Reduced tillage application increases SOC in the topsoil only, while 10-25 cm layer is more in favour for SOC accumulation under ploughing (Kochieru et al., 2020). Long-term field experiments revealed CT or NT practices, in combination with straw removal or return, governed a more pronounced superiority of NT over CT for SOC sequestration rate within the topsoil layer on loam than on sandy loam (Feiziene et al., 2018).

In Lithuania about 68 % of the area is hilly-rolling. The important feature of mineral soils in Western part of Lithuania and on hilly relief is their high natural acidity ($\text{pH KCl} \leq 5.5$) and a need to be limed periodically due to maintaining a suitable soil environment for some agricultural crops to be grown.

Other features of Lithuanian soils are the original low status of plant available macronutrients, unstable soil structure due to a low amount of SOC content in soil and high amount of sand particles (2.0-0.005 mm in diameter) in soil textural composition. Under this situation the nutrients loss and imbalance have to be monitored and taken into account considering nutrition strategy for crop biomass production. Soils with low amount of OM are also sensitive to compaction, which in turn inhibits biomass production and increases the risk of waterlogging.

Lithuanian stakeholders (farmers, advisers, agriculture journalists, scientists, officials from ministry of Agriculture) had ranked the SES and soil threats may be concluded that in Europe, under moderate climatic zone (Nemoral) and morainic pedological conditions, soil organic carbon loss is the most important soil threat. It is both the reason and consequence for manifestation the others STs and governing SESs. **Due to this the soil organic carbon loss may be devoted to as a superior (i.e., a super-indicator) soil threat.** Based on this situation, three suggestions from SERENA project for Lithuania may be drawn:

1. **The most promising recommendation from SERENA project for stakeholders and politicians of EU would be to proceed further SOM and C sequestration strategy on agricultural soils.**
2. **To develop the hierarchical structure of soil threats for agriculture soils at EU level in the future.**
3. **To develop classification system for SOM content in agricultural soils linked to pedo-climatic conditions.** Reference values may be as a baseline to compare SOC changes in contrasting climate zones as well as in individual MS over time. The EJP Soil LUCAS sampling programme may be of great importance for the such service.

Humus content classification used in Lithuania is presented in Table 5-2.

Table 5-2 Classification of humus concentration in mineral soils of Lithuania (Staugaitis and Vaišvila, 2015)

Soil group	Humus %		Description
	Sandy soils	Loamy and clay soils	
I	< 0.5	<1.0	Very low content
II	0.6 – 1.5	1.0 – 2.0	Low content
III	1.6 – 2.5	2.1 – 3.0	Moderate content
IV	2.6 – 3.5	3.1 – 4.0	High content
V	>3.5	>4.0	Very high content

Lithuania has a set of recommendations for practical farming on how to reduce soil threats encountered on agricultural land. Renewed [Code for Good Agricultural Practice for the Protection of Soil, Water, Air and Climate](#) has been issued in 2019. It contains crop, soil and livestock management recommendations and advice on how to control soil erosion, reduce nutrient imbalance, GHG emissions and environment pollution, to increase soil OM content, biomass production and biodiversity etc.

Finally, the bundles are identified by set of indicators and services. Soil organic carbon may be considered as a bundle because of its change may be identified by using different physicochemical and biological indicators at specific location for long-term soil management. It is important, that this bundle could also be monitored and managed by stakeholders and by implementation of policies and/or planning decisions. These requirements fulfil the concept of a bundle.

6. Selection of soil threats, soil ecosystem services

6.1 General

The final selection of soil threats and SES in SERENA has to be defined in accordance with end-users' requirements, project member states requirements and EU expectations. In the following sub-chapters, we present the methodology and results for the selection of soil threats and SES in the SERENA project.

6.2 Methodology of selection

Project partners assessed the prioritisation of the soil threats and SES in agricultural soils in their countries. It was up to each member state to define the method for the assessment. In some countries the results were based on literature review and/or expert judgment, whereas others undertook a survey among experts or organised stakeholder workshops (see details in Appendix A 1 and Appendix A 2).

The question was to prioritise the 11 soil threats and 7 SES into 4 categories:

- A: very important and must definitely be discussed in SERENA;
- B: important, must preferably be discussed in SERENA;
- C: nice to have in SERENA, but not important;
- D: not important or not relevant and must not be prioritised in SERENA.

Points were allocated to these different categories (A = 3 points, B = 2 points, C = 1 points, D = 0 points). These points were summed up over all the countries for each specific soil threat or SES and a ranking was made. Soil threats and SES which archived more than 75% of maximum points are ranked as 'A: very important soil threats and SES which must definitely be discussed in SERENA'. Those reaching 50-75% of the points are classified as 'B: important, must preferably be discussed in SERENA', those between 50-25% of the maximum points as 'C: nice to have in SERENA, but not important' and those reaching only 25-0% are classified as 'D: not important or not relevant and must not be prioritised in SERENA'.

It is important to notice that this prioritisation was done only for agricultural soils (cropland and grassland) as EJP SOIL focuses on agricultural soils. When also the soil under other land uses (forest, nature, built-up areas) would be taken into account, this would most likely result in a different prioritisation.

The results based on this ranking are shown in chapter 6.3 and 6.4. In addition to this ranking in D2.2 the following aspects will be taken into account for the final selection in the SERENA project:

- WP1 user needs
- Availability of the data
- Limited number of soil threats and SES that can be developed in SERENA
- Developments in policy needs

6.3 Prioritisation of soil threats in European countries

Prioritisation between the different soil threats

When summarising the results for all countries, it is clear that soil organic carbon loss, soil erosion and soil compaction and are regarded as very important soil threats which must definitely be discussed in SERENA (Figure 6-1) Further, drought, nutrient imbalance, soil sealing and loss of diversity are evaluated as important and preferably to be discussed in SERENA. Soil acidification, soil contamination, waterlogging and salinization are considered as the less important soil threats according to this assessment.

The reasoning and methodological approach of each project member state for the prioritisation of each soil threat separately is given in Appendix A 1.

Soil threats	S			W				N	C							Sum	Prioritisation	
	Italy	Spain	Portugal	France	Belgium	Netherlands	Ireland	Denmark	Estonia	Latvia	Lithuania	Poland	Czech	Slovakia	Austria			Hungary
Soil organic carbon loss	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	2	3	3	2	3	3	3	44	A
Soil erosion	3	3	3	3	3	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	3	40	A
Soil compaction	2	2	1	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	1	3	2	2	3	37	A
Drought	2	3	2	2	2	1	0	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	3	3	34	B
Nutrient imbalance	1	3	1	3	0	3	2	1	2	2	3	0	1	1	2	3	28	B
Soil sealing	3	3	0	3	3	1	0	0	2	1	1	0	2	1	3	3	26	B
Loss of diversity	2	3	1	1	2	3	2	1	2	1	2	0	1	0	2	2	25	B
Soil acidification	0	1	0	0	1	0	2	0	3	3	2	3	1	2	2	1	21	C
Soil contamination	2	2	1	2	3	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	2	2	2	21	C
Waterlogging	0	1	0	1	0	1	3	1	2	1	2	0	1	0	0	3	16	C
Salinization	2	2	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	11	D

Figure 6-1 Prioritisation of soil threats by project member states, listed by regions, S = southern Europe, W = western, N= northern and C = central Europe according to the environmental zones after Metzger et al. (2005).

Regional trends

The most important soil threats were of top priority in all regions. Soil acidification is of higher importance for central European countries, whereas soil salinization is considered more important in Southern European countries. For the other soil threats no clear regional trend is detected.

Soil threat specific prioritisation

For each soil threat, you find below an overview of the prioritisation and the main reasons given by the project member states and a link is made with the objectives and indicators of the mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' (Soil Mission) given in chapter 2. The soil threats are listed in order of the ranking as presented above.

Soil organic carbon loss:

Overall score = 'A: very important and must definitely be discussed in SERENA'

All participating countries marked SOC loss priority class for SERENA as very important or important. Main reasons for the high prioritisation are the importance of SOC as key soil property correlated to many other soil properties, soil threats and SES and the importance in relation to both soil fertility

and climate change. In addition, some countries recorded already declining or low SOC contents and the soil threat is particularly relevant for agricultural soils.

This soil threat is one of the specific objectives of the Soil Mission, namely 'Conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks'.

It is clear that indicators for this soil threat have definitely to be calculated in the SERENA as it is a top priority for both the project partners as for the EU Commission.

Soil erosion:

Overall score = 'A: very important and must definitely be discussed in SERENA'

Project member states regard soil erosion as one of the most severe soil threats especially for areas with specific characteristics of the relief, soil, climate and management practices. They scored soil erosion with an 'A: very important and must definitely be discussed in SERENA' or a 'B: important, must preferably be discussed in SERENA'. Only the Netherlands considered soil erosion as 'nice to have in SERENA, but not important' due to the fact that soil erosion is mostly a local problem in parts of the generally flat country.

In all the countries of southern Europe, soil erosion was scored with the highest score because soil erosion by water is of big concern. The trend towards shorter and more intense rainfall exacerbates the problem. Water erosion is more severe when periods of drought are broken by intense rain falling on bare or poorly vegetated and steeply-sloping soil surfaces.

In the Soil Mission this soil threat is assessed as one of the specific objectives, namely 'Prevent erosion' with a focus on water erosion.

Soil erosion must definitely be taken into account in SERENA. Many countries have already experience with the modelling of water erosion.

Soil compaction:

Overall score = 'A: very important and must definitely be discussed in SERENA'

Soil compaction is considered an important or very important soil threat in 14 countries out of 16 surveyed. For Ireland, soil compaction is the main soil threat. Two countries indicated this topic as 'C: nice to have in SERENA but not important' but this was because they have no available data at national level. Also, many other countries mentioned the lack of data related to this soil threat.

Many cropland areas are already damaged especially by heavy machinery. The threat is increasing for example due to 'harvesting-firms' that harvest by calendar and not by soil condition causing soil compaction under wet conditions. Also overgrazing and trampling in grassland contributes to soil compaction.

This soil threat is addressed in the objectives of the Soil Mission as 'Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops'.

The survey among project member states exhibits that soil compaction is widely recognized as a problem on agricultural soil in Europe and an indicator for soil compaction is needed and must definitely be taken into account in SERENA. The calculation of this indicator will be a challenge due to lack of related data in many participating countries.

Drought:

Overall score = 'B: important, must preferably be discussed in SERENA'

Most participating countries reported drought as important or very important due to more frequent drought periods due to climate change and its impact on agricultural production. Only Ireland considered it as not relevant for SERENA.

However, there is no consensus over what has to be considered as type of indicator for the soil threat drought. Some countries proposed some meteorological data as basis for the indicator. Belgium proposed to calculate rather an indicator for a sensitivity of soil for drought than for drought itself because the latter is more climate related than soil related. Also, the Netherlands considered drought itself as an important threat, but they don't see this specific for soil as a soil threat, but more for the whole farming system so they gave it a low score of C. Denmark reported that drought is mainly a problem on very sandy soils but that the problem is expanding to more loamy soils.

Drought is not part of a specific objective of the Soil Mission. It is not a specific soil threat but the results of different soil threats and weather conditions.

It can be concluded that drought is an important threat but that soil related aspects have to be considered when defining an indicator related to drought as a soil threat.

Nutrient imbalance:

Overall score = 'B: important, must preferably be discussed in SERENA'

Nutrient imbalance is regarded among member states in the range from 'D: not important or not relevant – must not in SERENA' to 'A: very important – must definitely in SERENA'. This is due to the fact that on the one hand no single indicator for nutrient imbalance exists because nutrient imbalance is a complex and very broad soil threat, but on the other hand nutrient losses by over-fertilization must be tackled. For Hungary, nutrient imbalance is one of the leading soil threats in their country.

In most participating countries nutrient excesses are reported. Other countries mentioned both soils deficient in nutrients due to specific soil characteristics as soils with excess of nutrients due to management practices.

Nutrient imbalance is part of the objective 'Reduce pollution and enhance restoration' of the Soil Mission. However, only nutrient losses are considered. In addition, essential nutrients are proposed as an indicator for soil health associated with the objectives 'Reduce land degradation relating to desertification' and 'Increase soil literacy in society across Member States'. This means that in the Soil Mission lack of nutrients and excess of nutrients are not regarded as one specific soil threat. The excess of nutrients is also topic of a specific legislation (Nitrate Directive).

Nutrient imbalance is regarded as important but is recommended that nutrient excess and nutrient shortages are considered separately.

Soil sealing:

Overall score = 'B: important, must preferably be discussed in SERENA'

There are no regional differentiations in the prioritisation for soil sealing. Half of the participating countries considered soil sealing as a very important or important soil threat. Here, soil sealing is considered one of the most threatening degradation processes for the permanent loss of all soil

functions, except that of hosting human settlements responsible for a significant loss of agricultural soils. They considered this soil threat as the most important soil threat for most fertile soil in most regions.

However, the other half of the countries considered the soil threat soil sealing as not relevant or only nice to have for SERENA. They argued that soil sealing is not a problem of agricultural soil management or that is not related to or relevant for agriculture. Other countries have a small degree of soil sealing and therefore do not consider it as relevant.

This soil threat is addressed in the objective 'No net soil sealing and increase the reuse of urban soils' of the Soil Mission.

The soil threat soil sealing is scored as important and must preferably be discussed in SERENA. It is recommended to define for SERENA if soil indicators calculated in SERENA will be limited to soil threats influenced by agricultural management or if soil threats influenced by other factors will also be considered.

Loss of diversity:

Overall score = 'B: important, must preferably be discussed in SERENA'

For the soil threat loss of diversity very different scorings were given ranging from 'D: not important or not relevant – must not in SERENA' to 'A: very important – must preferably in SERENA'.

9 Countries out of the 16 considered this soil threat as 'A: very important – must definitely in SERENA' and 'B: important – must preferably in SERENA'. Loss of soil biodiversity was reported as a specific problem for intensive cropping systems that becomes more important in the (near) future.

The low scorings 'C: nice to have in SERENA but not important' and 'D: not important or not relevant – must not in SERENA' were mainly based on the fact that data is missing on national level. France reported that loss of diversity is important for intensive cropping systems when biodiversity is known as low, but that there are not enough data and therefore scored it as a C. Therefore, France scored it as C. This means that the overall scoring for this soil threat is biased by a lack of data.

Loss of diversity is not a specific objective of the Soil Mission. But the Soil Mission proposes 'soil biodiversity' as an indicator for soil health. The indicator is associated to the objectives 'Reduce land degradation relating to desertification' and 'Increase soil literacy in society across Member States'.

The soil threat 'loss of diversity' was overall scored as important and must preferably considered in SERENA. The lack of data related to loss of diversity lowered the overall score for this soil threat, however, there is a great interest in indicators for it. Therefore, we recommend to define indicators with their methodology for 'loss of diversity' so that countries have guidelines to collect missing data.

Soil acidification:

Overall score = 'C: nice to have in SERENA, but not important'

The soil threat soil acidification was considered as more important in Central- Europe compared to the other regions. The questionnaire indicated soil acidification as a very important threat in Estonia, Latvia and Poland and Estonia while important for Ireland, Austria, Lithuania and Slovakia. The soil threat is often limited to specific soils within the country. In Latvia around 50% of arable land has low pH levels.

In 9 of the 16 participating countries soil acidification was scored low as 'C: nice to have in SERENA but not important' or 'D: not important or not relevant – must not in SERENA'. The main reason for a low score was the fact that liming can solve the soil threat or that it was not a problem in agricultural soils.

Although the Soil Mission proposes the soil pH value as an indicator for soil health, soil acidification is not a specific objective of the Soil Mission. The indicator is associated to the objectives 'Reduce land degradation relating to desertification' and 'Increase soil literacy in society across Member States'.

The soil threat soil acidification received an average score of 'C: nice to have in SERENA, but not important'. Although for central Europe, the average score was 'B: important – must preferably in SERENA'.

Soil contamination:

Overall score = 'C: nice to have in SERENA, but not important'

As the survey showed, soil contamination is not the highest priority soil threat for half of the participating countries. Nine of sixteen countries considered the soil contamination as not important or not relevant (scores C and D), explaining this mainly by the local/regional nature of its occurrence in hotspots and often not an issue in relation to agricultural soils.

Other six countries (Austria, France, Hungary, Italy, Slovakia and Spain) indicated that soil contamination is an important threat and must be preferably included in the SERENA analysis. And only Belgium ranked soil contamination as 'A: very important – must definitely in SERENA'. Countries for which soil contamination is very important or important pointed out the occurrence of many contaminated sites and the need to assess especially the diffuse pollution in agricultural soils. .

Soil contamination is part of the objective 'Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration'.

The soil threat soil contamination was on average scored as 'C: nice to have in SERENA, but not important' with a high variety of scores among the countries.

Waterlogging:

Overall score = 'C: nice to have in SERENA, but not important'

Most of the participating countries gave a low score (C or D) to the soil threat 'waterlogging'. Some of the reasons for these low scorings are:

- waterlogged cropland has often been drained;
- observed waterlogging in agricultural soils is due to soil compaction (another soil threat in SERENA);
- mostly only a local problem;
- not relevant for the country and
- waterlogged soils have often another land use than agriculture

Only Hungary and Ireland considered the soil threat as very important and Estonia and Lithuania as important. Waterlogging (inland excess water) causes significant damages to agriculture in flat areas of Hungary almost every year and 40-45% of the soils in Ireland are gleysols potentially subjected to waterlogging.

Waterlogging is not a specific objective of the Soil Mission and not proposed as an indicator for soil health.

Waterlogging is overall considered as nice to have in SERENA but not important. Although some countries, do considered it as very important due to the significant area of specific soil types like gleysols. Waterlogging is not part of the Soil Mission.

Salinization:

Overall score = 'D: not important or not relevant and must not be prioritised in SERENA'

As the survey showed, the problem of soil salinization is not a priority for most partners of SERENA. Indeed, eight out of sixteen countries rated that this issue is not important or not relevant for SERENA, two partners indicated that it would be nice to have in SERENA, but not important.

Hungary, Italy, Portugal and Spain rated the issue of salinization important and must be preferably considered in SERENA. The issue of salinization is rather a bigger problem in arid, semi-arid, and dry sub-humid regions, coastal areas, or in the hotspots where soils were influenced by the industry (soda factories, salt mines).

Soil salinization is part of the objective 'Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration' of the Soil Mission.

As salinisation is regional limited, the overall score for this soil threat was only 'C: not important or not relevant and must not be prioritised in SERENA'.

6.4 Prioritisation of soil ecosystem services in different European countries

Prioritisation between the different SES

Most assessed SES are either ‘A: very important – must definitely in SERENA’ or ‘B: important – must preferably in SERENA’. The SESs “Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration” is of uppermost importance (Figure 6-2). Additional, “Primary/biomass production” and “Hydrological control” as well as “Erosion control” are also very important and must also definitely be discussed in SERENA. Soils as “Habitat for biodiversity” and the “Environmental pollution control” are important and must preferably be discussed in SERENA. Only the SES “Pest and disease control” is regarded of least importance for the project member states in SERENA.

The reasons and the approach of assessment are given in Appendix A 2 at the level of project member state

Soil-based ecosystem services	S			W				N	C						Sum	Prioritisation		
	Italy	Spain	Portugal	France	Belgium	Netherlands	Ireland	Denmark	Estonia	Latvia	Lithuania	Poland	Czech	Slovakia			Austria	Hungary
Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	47	A
Hydrological control	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	47	A
Primary/biomass production	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	45	A
Erosion control	2	3	3	3	3	0	2	1	2	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	39	A
Habitat for biodiversity	2	3	1	2	2	3	2	1	2	2	2	0	2	1	2	3	30	B
Environmental pollution control	3	3	1	2	0	2	0	3	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	28	B
Pest and disease control	1	3	1	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	2	2	2	16	C

Figure 6-2 prioritisation of SES in project MS listed by regions, S = southern Europe, W = western, N= northern and C = central Europe according to the environmental zones after (Metzger et al., 2005).

Regional trends

For the SESs there are no regional trends in the prioritisation.

SES specific prioritisation

Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration

Overall score = ‘A: very important and must definitely be discussed in SERENA’

Fifteen countries, out of 16 within the SERENA project, considered ‘Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration’ as a very important soil ecosystem service, thereby saying that it must definitely be included in SERENA. Only Czech considered this SES as important, meaning it should preferably be considered in SERENA. The latter justifies this by explaining that it is a crucial issue, but that there is not enough data available in the corresponding country.

Some of the countries remarked that the role of soils in the control and mitigation of GHG and climate regulation is essential, and that it can also affect the ecosystem health and other important soil functions such as crop life cycle functioning and nutrient and water use efficiency. Others highlighted the positive aspects of C sequestration, but also the negative aspects, such as N₂O and CH₄ emissions. The EJP SOIL project CarboSeq is focussing on modelling related to this SES.

Hydrological control

Overall score = ‘A: very important and must definitely be discussed in SERENA’

15 out of 16 SERENA countries scored the soil ecosystem service ‘Hydrological control’ as ‘A: very important – must definitely in SERENA’. Belgium scored it as ‘B: important – must preferably in SERENA’.

Some reasons for this high scoring of the SES hydrological control:

- basis for a lot of soil functions, soil processes and SES;
- essential role of soils in the hydrological cycle;
- requirements to manage hydrology through better soil management and
- crucial for agricultural production.

Primary/biomass production

Overall score = ‘A: very important and must definitely be discussed in SERENA’

Agricultural soils fulfil a wide range of ecosystem services, however their primary function is to produce biomass, especially for nutrition purposes. This was confirmed by the prioritisation of the participating countries in SERENA. Most of the countries (13) indicated that primary/biomass production is very important and must definitely be considered in SERENA. Denmark, Latvia and Ireland declared that this soil ecosystem service is important and must preferably be considered in SERENA. This topic, according to the Member States declaration, is not widely studied in Europe.

Erosion control:

Overall score = ‘A: very important and must definitely be discussed in SERENA’

Ten participating countries found erosion control very important and 4 important. Only Denmark and the Netherlands considered soil erosion as not important for SERENA. The Netherlands commented that soil erosion control is more a solution for a soil threat than a real SES. Also, for other countries the reasons for priority revealed soil erosion control was rather regarded as solution for the soil threat erosion instead of a real soil ecosystem service.

Habitat for biodiversity

Overall score = ‘B: important, must preferably be discussed in SERENA’

The majority of the countries found it important or very important to discuss, model or/and map the SES of agricultural soils as habitat for biodiversity within the SERENA project. However, most countries remarked that national data are missing for this SES. It is recommended to co-construct indicators for this SES with the EJP SOIL MINOTAUR project.

Environmental pollution control

Overall score = ‘B: important, must preferably be discussed in SERENA’

Denmark, Italy and Spain find this soil ecosystem service in SERENA as very important to assess within SERENA. Eight countries found the SES important to take into account in SERENA. Spain pointed out that pollutants are deposited and distributed in the soil and in the water and that this affects the entire trophic chain. However, the majority of project member states find this ecosystem

service as important; however, due to lack of data it would not be possible to map this ecosystem service at national or European scale within SERENA.

Five countries attributed low scores (C and D) because soil pollution control is seen rather as a solution for a soil threat and not as a soil ecosystem service, they lack data or they have no soil pollution problems.

Pest and disease control:

Overall score = 'C: nice to have in SERENA, but not important'

Only Spain found this SES very important for SERENA because its occurrence decreases agricultural production: crops and the biodiversity associated with them decrease or even die off. Austria, France, Hungary and Slovakia considered pest and disease control important to take into account in SERENA.

The other 11 countries scored this SES low with a score of C or D. They explained their low score due to lack of data at national level, which makes any implementation of this topic in SERENA impossible. Other found that it is more a plant related ecosystem system than a SES or that this SES indirectly is covered by the SES primary/biomass production and habitat for biodiversity.

6.5 Interactions between soil threats, SES and indicators

Top soil contains the highest content of nutrients and soil organic carbon and the highest biological activity. At the same time top soil is at most exposed to soil erosion, contamination and soil acidification.

We know from literature that soil threats are affecting each other (FAO and ITPS, 2015; Stolte et al., 2015) and changes in biological, chemical or/and physical soil properties modifies SES (EEA, 2022a). Figure 6-3 shows how single soil processes can affect the soils biological, chemical and physical functions at once. According to Stolte et al. (2015) e.g. soil acidification affects the accumulation of SOM (SOC sequestration), plant supply of nutrients, and the cation exchange capacity of soils, whereas soil sealing affects almost all soil functions for plant production.

In the assessment of soil threats, SES and bundles, chapter 2, 3 and 4 list some of the interrelations given for the specific soil threat or SES. For instance, the loss of SOC consequently increases the probability of physical changes like soil erosion or compaction, and reduces the water holding capacity and thereby the biomass production at site (chapter 3.3); and vice versa, SOC sequestration is affected by compaction or erosion and reduced biomass production, which also reduces the C input in soil (chapter 3.8 and 3.2)

Figure 7.5 | Direct impacts of soil threats on specific soil functions of relevance to plant production.

Figure 6-3 different soil threats affects more soil properties and soil functions (FAO and ITPS, 2015)

Chapter 5 gives an overview of several approaches at different scales and the status of the search of any super-indicator or bundles of soil threats and SES. For instance, the SDG indicator 15.3.1 differs between degraded and not degraded land by the sub-indicators Trend in Land Cover, Land Productivity and Carbon Stocks at global scale and Lithuania proposing the super-indicator SOC content. However, by time, the project partners are not able to agree upon one or a set of super-indicator(s). For this we need the results of the on-going in-depth discussion about the indicators and their thresholds. What we can provide is a list of indicators for soil threats and SES.

In Table 6-1 an overview of the proposed indicators from chapter 2, 3 and 4 are listed.

Table 6-1 Summary of indicators from the chapters 2, 3 and 4

soil threat or SES	Indicator
Soil erosion	Soil loss $t\ ha^{-1}$ or $t\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$; exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water; soil surface phenomena; aggregate stability of surface soil (%); soil cohesion; share of agriculture area (%) under severe erosion
Soil organic carbon loss	decrease of SOC concentration (% or $g\ kg^{-1}$); SOC stock ($t\ ha^{-1}$); SOM content (%); humus content (%); land use change; clay:SOC ratio; SOC sequestration potential ($t\ ha^{-1}$); C:N ratio of the topsoil (%); land cover change (km^2); wild fires (km^2); crop residues burning (km^2); exogenous organic matter additions ($t\ ha^{-1}$); organic farming (%); GHG fluxes and N_2O emissions
Nutrient imbalance	soil nutrient content/concentration; soil texture; bulk density; pH value; C:N ratio; N:P ratio; NO_3^- leaching; plant nutrient content/concentration;
Soil acidification	pH-value; base cations in soil sorption complex (BC); base saturation; molar Ca/Al or BC/Al; content of exchangeable Al; change of acid neutralizing capacity ($mol_c\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$)
Soil contamination	concentration of common contaminants, both inorganic and organic, expressed in ppm or $mg\ kg^{-1}$ soil; gross nutrient balance; area under organic farming; sewage sludge and average pesticide consumption per unit area of agricultural land; expenditures on remediation; groundwater incidents
Waterlogging	Frequency/or days of occurrences of inland excess water (number or %); regional drainage (canals, dams, pumping stations)
Soil compaction	Bulk density ($g\ cm^{-3}$); the soil penetration resistance (MPa) ; saturated hydraulic conductivity/soil water permeability ($m\ s^{-1}$), total and air-filled porosity (%), oxygen diffusion rate ($\mu\ Amper$), redox potential (Volts), and air permeability ($l\ min^{-1}$); macroporosity;
Soil sealing	% sealed soil of total soil area or km^2 or hectares of sealed soil at a given date. The change is expressed as km^2 (or ha) or % per year or years; Further indicators are annual rates of land take, rates per capita, sprawl indexes; imperviousness degree 1-100%
Salinization	the electrical conductivity (EC_e); pH value; soil structure; extractable salts contents ($mg\ kg^{-1}$); Sodium Adsorption Ration (SAR); Exchangeable Sodium Percentage (ESP);
Loss of diversity *	Soil invertebrate biodiversity index (QBS); Soil microbial biomass carbon and functional groups; diversity and density of earthworm occurrence; biodiversity indices; CLPP indicators; CO_2 efflux; microbial biomass values; enzymes activity; potential mineralizable N etc. currently less cost-intensive DNA-based methods are developed.
Soil drought	Soil moisture index (SMI) and soil moisture anomaly (SMA); Surface Water Supply Index; Rainfall Anomaly Index; Standard Precipitation – Evapotranspiration Index; Vegetation Condition Index (VCI) and Temperature Condition Index (TCI).
Primary/biomass production	the total amount of plant biomass in $t/ha/year$; yields as $\text{€}/t/ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$; yields/ $ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$: $\text{€}/ha/year$; energy yield expressed in $10^7\ kcal\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$

or $\text{J ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$;

Habitat for biodiversity *	Microbial (Achaeta, Bacteria, Fungi) biomass (lipid extraction from soil), N, C, (Chloroform fumigation extraction), diversity sequencing, richness/Shannon (OTU or ASV-based diversity), microbial respiration (CO_2 evolution), Nematodes abundance and diversity, mesofauna and macrofauna abundance and diversity, soil feeding activity (bait lamina), litter decomposition (Litter bag). Presence or absence of invasive species and the rate of mortality. Also land use and land cover; soil pH-value, soil texture are used as indicators when describing soil as habitat.
Erosion control	Capacity of vegetation to reduce erosion risk (based on land cover); decrease of erosion risk by vegetation (calculated by RUSLE); capacity of ecosystems to avoid soil erosion (calculated by RUSLE) defined as the fraction of the total potential soil erosion that is mitigated by the service provision; Total amount of soil not eroded ($\text{t ha}^{-1} \text{y}^{-1}$ (or equivalent)); Surface area of natural vegetation with a function of erosion control (ha (weighted area of natural vegetation) ha^{-1} (total NUTS area)); Weighting of the surface area of natural vegetation by the erosion risk estimated with MESALES Model (Modèle d'Evaluation Spatiale de l'ALéa Erosion des Sols - Regional Modelling of Soil Erosion Risk
Hydrological control	available water capacity (AWC, also called plant available water capacity PAWC, mm m^{-1}) and field capacity (FC, mm m^{-1} or $\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$). Further, fraction of transmissive pores or air capacity ($\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$ for all); soil depth; soil bulk density (g cm^{-3}); texture;
Environmental pollution control	the concentration of various soil contaminants expressed in ppm or mg kg^{-1} of soil. Further, the quality and content of soil organic matter, soil pH and clay mineral content, as well as the activity of soil microorganisms
Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	GHG emissions from agricultural soils (CO_2 , N_2O and CH_4). ($\text{Mg CO}_2 \text{ eq. ha}^{-1} \text{y}^{-1}$); Positive changes in SOC stocks. ($\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{y}^{-1}$)
Pest and disease control	diversity/richness, abundance, composition of pests or antagonist and Plant Growth Promoting Organisms (PGPOs); fungi:bacteria; presence/absence of invasive species; mortality

*EEA conclude –defiantly need to be developed (EEA, 2022)

7. Conclusions

This report resulted in a ranking of soil threats and soil ecosystem services (SES) for agricultural soils. In the prioritisation process by the individual countries of the SERENA project it rapidly became clear that harmonised common definitions were required for all soil threats and SES over all the European participating countries.

An intense harmonisation process between the SERENA partners resulted in harmonised common definitions which can be found in chapters 2 and 3. As indicators for the soil threats and SES are to be used by non-soil experts as well, a translation for non-soil experts was included for all soil threats and SES. These translations will be reviewed by different stakeholders in WP1 of the SERENA project.

From the literature review it became clear that in general a lot of literature is available for soil threats but that there is weak knowledge about SES and information about bundles is scarce.

Soil threats and SES were ranked from high to low importance to be taken into account for the elaboration of soil threat or SES indicators in the SERENA project (see chapter 6.3). This overall ranking was based on the prioritisation done by each different countries participating in the SERENA project.

The prioritisation per participating country was mainly based on the following criteria:

- Importance of soil threat or SES in the country
- Relevance for agricultural soils
- Data availability
- Soil threat/SES not already covered by other soil threat/SES
- Soil threat/SES not too complex for one indicator

As stated by EEA (2022a), the development of adequate and broadly applicable indicators and thresholds is challenged by the great diversity of European soils, biota and climate, as well as different political, economic, and social conditions which lead to different priority settings for targets and indicators among countries. This was reflected in the different scorings for many soil threats and SES over all the participating countries for a specific soil threat or SES in the SERENA prioritisation process.

In addition to this ranking the following aspects will be taken into account for the final selection in the SERENA project:

- User needs / stakeholder consultation (WP 1 in SERENA)
- Data availability
- Number of soil threats and SES that can be developed in SERENA
- Reporting obligations related to soil health defined in the new Soil Health Law foreseen mid-June 2023.

The selection of specific indicators and the assessment of thresholds for soil threats and SES of interest in SERENA will be done by WP2 T2.3 of the SERENA project.

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9. Appendix

Appendix A 1: Details of the prioritisation of the soil threats of the participating countries. Priority class for SERENA = A: very important and must definitely be discussed in SERENA; B: important, must preferably be discussed in SERENA; C: important, must preferably be discussed in SERENA and D: not important or not relevant and must not be prioritised in SERENA.

member state	soil threat	priority for SERENA	reason for priority class	approach and detail combined
Austria	Soil erosion	A	We need to improve the existing methods;	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Austria	Soil organic carbon loss	A	Has been intensive studied and calculated by different approaches at regional and national level, that means we have data. However this data is static - we are missing the overview of the development above field scale over time. The soil threat is very important, especially in agricultural soil.	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Austria	Nutrient imbalance	B	Important, data available at field scale, excess of N (NO ₃ -) at regional scale (thanks to N directive!)	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Austria	Soil acidification	B	Only an issue at agricultural soils on silicat bedrock in Mülviertel (region). Controlled by liming.	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Austria	Soil contamination	B	Maps already exist; due to the longlivity of heavy metal and POP; likely still actual, there is a national guideline for heavy metals that should be followed, thresholds could be looked up there	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Austria	Waterlogging	D	We have no data above field scale; certain soils prone to waterlogging, (due to soil type; position in landscape) often a result of management measures. More an issue at field scale.	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Austria	Soil sealing	A	Land take esp. urban sprawl a daily threat to ESS; this was the only soil threat which everyone found A) very important	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)

Austria	Soil compaction	B	is a problem at field scale, also in grassland soils! We have no data on this. Everybody knows... but ..still a problem due to the increasing trend of 'harvesting-firms' who are scheduled and do the harvesting by calendar and not by soil condition.	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Austria	Salinization	D	Regional limited, only small are in Austria	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Austria	Loss of diversity	B	Loss of biodiversity is a problem also in Austria, there are data available but not at national scale. since MINOTAUR will focus on biodiversity, the experts prioritised this soil threat lower	One stakeholder survey (September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Austria	Drought	A	Drought is a 'new' soil threat in Austria, affecting more and more regions . The seasonal precipitation pattern has changed and agricultural measures have to be adopted. To learn form other countries it is seen as very important.	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Belgium	Soil erosion	A	A lot of problems with soil erosion in the more hilly regions in Belgium.	Expert workshop: national hub meeting with experts from administrations and statistical offices of different regions
Belgium	Soil organic carbon loss	A	Soil organic carbon is the key to soil fertility and important in view of climate change.	Expert workshop: national hub meeting with experts from administrations and statistical offices of different regions
Belgium	Nutrient imbalance	D	This soil threat is is a complex and very broad topic with a lot of indicators needed. Nutrient imbalance is not specific enough. Also topic of specific legislations (for example nitrate directive).	Expert workshop: national hub meeting with experts from administrations and statistical offices of different regions
Belgium	Soil acidification	C	There is already a well known indicator: pH (only relevant for the local scale)	Expert workshop: national hub meeting with experts from administrations and statistical offices of different regions
Belgium	Soil contamination	A	A lot of polluted soils in Belgium (also diffuse pollution).	Expert workshop: national hub meeting with experts from administrations and statistical offices of different regions
Belgium	Waterlogging	D	Waterlogged cropland has often been drained or more specifically currently observed waterlogging in cropland/grassland is due to soil compaction (other soil threat in SERENA). Naturally waterlogged soils have often another land use than agriculture in Belgium.	Expert judgement

Belgium	Soil sealing	A	Belgium and especially Flanders have a large amount of soil sealing which has several consequences also for agricultural soils.	Expert workshop: national hub meeting with experts from administrations and statistical offices of different regions
Belgium	Soil compaction	A	Very important, but not many data available about it.	Expert workshop: national hub meeting with experts from administrations and statistical offices of different regions
Belgium	Salinization	D	Only relevant for a small part of Belgium.	Expert workshop: national hub meeting with experts from administrations and statistical offices of different regions
Belgium	Loss of diversity	B	Important, but not many data and reserach available about it in Flanders.	Expert workshop: national hub meeting with experts from administrations and statistical offices of different regions
Belgium	Drought	B	We propose rather sensitivity for drought (=bundle: combination of different other soil threats related to soil structure and organic carbon): Important, large impact, more frequent drought periods due to climate change.	Expert judgement
Czech	Soil erosion	A	Biggest threat, endangering about 50% of arable land	Stocktaking of existing research, models
Czech	Soil organic carbon loss	B	Not much long term data available for reliable evaluation	Stocktaking of existing research
Czech	Nutrient imbalance	C	Rather a problem in forest soils	
Czech	Soil acidification	C	Problem in forest soils, not in agricultural ones	
Czech	Soil contamination	C	Just a local or regional issue (hotspots)	Stocktaking of existing research
Czech	Waterlogging	C	Mostly just a local problem	Stocktaking of existing research
Czech	Soil sealing	B	Big issue, but impacted rather by political decisions and economical needs than by climate and other environmental change	Stocktaking of existing research
Czech	Soil compaction	A	Many cropland areas are damaged	Stocktaking of existing research
Czech	Salinization	D	Not a problem in the Czech Republic	
Czech	Loss of diversity	C	Lack of available data	Stocktaking of existing research
Czech	Drought	A	Factor strongly limiting agricultural production in some years	Data inventarisation, stocktake, studies and needs from policy
Denmark	Soil erosion	B	The main concern in relation to erosion relates to leaching of nutrients into the aquatic environment. Farmers do not consider erosion as an important factor in relation to yield.	Expert assessment
Denmark	Soil organic carbon loss	A	Soil organic carbon is important in relation to soil fertility as well as in the scope of climate change.	Expert assessment

Denmark	Nutrient imbalance	C	The imbalance is mainly related to a excess of applied manure at risk at being leached out of the root zone	Expert assessment
Denmark	Soil acidification	D	The farmers lime the soil	Expert assessment
Denmark	Soil contamination	C	This is not an issue in relation to agricultural soils (hot spots only)	Expert assessment
Denmark	Waterlogging	C	A detailed map of natural drain classes exists. Agricultural soils at risk of water logging are all artificial drained	Expert assessment
Denmark	Soil sealing	D	Soil sealing is not considered as a big problem in Denmark.	Expert assessment
Denmark	Soil compaction	A	Denmark is heavily agricultured and soil compaction by the farmers vehicles is a major threat to the quality of the soil	Expert assessment
Denmark	Salinization	D	Due to excess precipitation soil salinization is not a problem in Denmark	Expert assessment
Denmark	Loss of diversity	C	For agricultural soils the biodiversity is expected to be low	Expert assessment
Denmark	Drought	B	During the change in climate, Denmark some times (but not every year) experiences drought during the growing season. Most problems relate to the western part of Denmark (western part of Jylland) where we have alluvial outwash planes from the last glaciation periodes. These areas contains very sandy soils that need to be irrigated after only a few days without precipitation. However, the need for irrigation is moving also to more loamy soils.	Expert assessment
Estonia	Soil erosion	B	Continuous research in soil erosion is important	Expert assessment
Estonia	Soil organic carbon loss	A	Soil organic carbon is important considering soil fertility as well as the scope of climate change	Expert assessment
Estonia	Nutrient imbalance	B	An important theme considering agricultural production as well as environmental issues in general	Expert assessment
Estonia	Soil acidification	A	An issue in part of agricultural areas, partly due to acidic bedrock	Expert assessment
Estonia	Soil contamination	C	Soil contamination is not typically an issue in agricultural soils	Expert assessment
Estonia	Waterlogging	B	Waterlogging is hardly studied so far but is receiving increasing attention considering the relationship to other soil threats and soil ecosystem services	Expert assessment

Estonia	Soil sealing	B	Soil sealing is an increasing issue considering agricultural land take to other purposes.	Expert assessment
Estonia	Soil compaction	B	Sensitivity to soil compaction most of the soils is high. Soil compaction as a threat to be analysed for example, to other threats and soil ecosystem services.	Expert assessment
Estonia	Salinization	D	No problem with that in our region	Expert assessment
Estonia	Loss of diversity	B	There is lack of data considering loss of soil diversity	Expert assessment
Estonia	Drought	B	Climate extremes including drought periods has been increased	Expert assessment
France	Soil erosion	A	Important, especially for Northern of France; maps already available at the national scale (only on water erosion somehow)	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
France	Soil organic carbon loss	A	Very important for evaluation of soil quality, health, fertility, and role in mitigation of climate change	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
France	Nutrient imbalance	A	Very important in relation with the soil fertility and the biomass production	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
France	Soil acidification	D	Not a specific problem on agricultural soils	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
France	Soil contamination	B	Maps of some contaminants already available; emerging pollutants have to be evaluated	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
France	Waterlogging	C	Should start to be a problem in some regions due to climate change and modification of rainfall regimes	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
France	Soil sealing	A	Important in some regions where "good" agricultural soils are sealed	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
France	Soil compaction	A	Important for some crops in agricultural soils	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
France	Salinization	C	Not a problem actually, but could start to be important with climate change (?)	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
France	Loss of diversity	C	Important for intensive cropping systems when biodiversity is known as low, but not enough data	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
France	Drought	B	start to be important recently in relation with climate change	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
Hungary	Soil erosion	A	One of the leading soil degradation processes in Hungary	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject

Hungary	Soil organic carbon loss	A	Key property in terms of water retention, fertility, and buffer capacity	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Hungary	Nutrient imbalance	A	One of the leading soil threat in Hungary	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Hungary	Soil acidification	C	Only relevant for a small part of Hungary	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Hungary	Soil contamination	B	Contaminated soils are being localized, surveyed and partly remediated, but these are typically local contaminations. However, the number of the contaminated sites is in the 10,000 range.	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Hungary	Waterlogging	A	Waterlogging (inland excess water) causes significant damages to agriculture in flat areas of Hungary almost every year	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Hungary	Soil sealing	A	The area of sealed soil is growing year by year in Hungary	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Hungary	Soil compaction	A	A major problem in most agricultural areas in Hungary	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Hungary	Salinization	B	Important in main grain producing area; Since irrigated areas are increasing due to the aridification caused by climate change, risk of human-induced, secondary salinization is also increasing	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Hungary	Loss of diversity	B	Important on arable lands (43 % of Hungarian territory)	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Hungary	Drought	A	More frequent drought events affect food security in Hungary	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Ireland	Soil erosion	B	90% of land is covered with permanent grasslands changes of rainfall intensity in the future	
Ireland	Soil organic carbon loss	B	Peat soils drainage	
Ireland	Nutrient imbalance	B	15% of soils have optimum nutrient balance	
Ireland	Soil acidification	B	33% of soils have suboptimal soil pH	
Ireland	Soil contamination	D		
Ireland	Waterlogging	A	40-45% of the soils in Ireland are gleysols potentially subjected to waterlogging	

Ireland	Soil sealing	D		
Ireland	Soil compaction	A	Compaction is the main threat for Ireland associate with mgt regimes and geo-climatic conditions	
Ireland	Salinization	D		
Ireland	Loss of diversity	B	Biodiversity decline announced by government	
Ireland	Drought	D		
Italy	Soil erosion	A	Important issue for all the Italian regions	Workshops with stakeholders; survey for D2.5 EJP
Italy	Soil organic carbon loss	A	Important issue for intensively cultivated agricultural soils	Workshops with stakeholders; survey for D2.5 EJP
Italy	Nutrient imbalance	C	Some over fertilization is reported in Po plain agricultural soils	Workshops with stakeholders; survey for D2.5 EJP
Italy	Soil acidification	D	Not relevant for Italy	Workshops with stakeholders; survey for D2.5 EJP
Italy	Soil contamination	B	Relevant for heavy metals for some regions and for contaminated sites not recovered	Workshops with stakeholders; survey for D2.5 EJP
Italy	Waterlogging	D	Flooding is relevant for Italy, waterlogging not	Workshops with stakeholders; survey for D2.5 EJP
Italy	Soil sealing	A	The first soil threat for most fertile soils in most of the regions	ISPRA yearly national assessments; workshops with stakeholders; survey for D2.5 EJP
Italy	Soil compaction	B	Not enough data available on soil compaction; limited to compaction related to construction sites, assessed as reversible consumption by ISPRA but still relevant;	ISPRA yearly national assessment
Italy	Salinization	B	Relevant in coastal areas: data available for Italy	Workshops with stakeholders; survey for D2.5 EJP
Italy	Loss of diversity	B	Relevant for many regions, but we have only scattered data	Workshops with stakeholders; survey for D2.5 EJP
Italy	Drought	B	Relevant in mediterranean regions	Not discussed wit stakeholders, to be checked
Latvia	Soil erosion	B	The increase of arable land area and plowing of steep slopes which incese soil erosion	consultation with relevant experts
Latvia	Soil organic carbon loss	B	Disbalanse of OM loss and addition in arable land	consultation with relevant experts
Latvia	Nutrient imbalance	B	Approx. 50% of arable land lacks P and 25% lacks K	consultation with relevant experts
Latvia	Soil acidification	A	Approx. 50% arable land has low pH levels	consultation with relevant experts
Latvia	Soil contamination	D	Not relevant for Latvia	consultation with relevant experts
Latvia	Waterlogging	C	No data available	consultation with relevant experts
Latvia	Soil sealing	C	Expansion of cities on surrounding arable land	consultation with relevant experts
Latvia	Soil compaction	B	No data available, but soil analysis show signs of soil compaction	consultation with relevant experts

Latvia	Salinization	D	Not relevant for Latvia	consultation with relevant experts
Latvia	Loss of diversity	C	No data available for the whole country	consultation with relevant experts
Latvia	Drought	B	No data available for the entire country	consultation with relevant experts
Lithuania	Soil erosion	B	32 percent is flat land and 68 percent the area of Lithuania is hilly-rolling. It is an important factor originating many others soil quality parameters and soil threats.	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Lithuania	Soil organic carbon loss	A	Morainic soils prevail in Lithuania. The feature of these soils is a low amount of OM by origin.	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Lithuania	Nutrient imbalance	A	Rather low nutrient status is inherited from glacial originated soils. High amount of sand particles in textural composition (sand, sandy loam, loam) is favourable for nutrient loss and imbalance.	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Lithuania	Soil acidification	B	Acid soils prevail in the Eastern and Western part of the country. Periodic liming must be performed.	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Lithuania	Soil contamination	D	Only small spots of agricultural land deal with this problem. Soil contamination status along highways is more related to this issue	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Lithuania	Waterlogging	B	It is increasing problem in now days as it is related with soil compaction and surface standing water problem.	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Lithuania	Soil sealing	C	It is related not so much with agricultural land.	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Lithuania	Soil compaction	B	Increasing problem due heavy weight machinery use.	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Lithuania	Salinization	D	This problem is not relevant for Lithuania	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Lithuania	Loss of diversity	B	It is relevant for intensive agricultural farming area (Central part of the country).	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject

Lithuania	Drought	B	Drought is related with heat waves. Drought is spontaneous meteorological phenomenon. In Lithuania such situation is registered once in two years. It exhibits local character of manifestation. In Lithuania the drought situation is officially announced if the average air temperature during 24 hrs was higher than 10 degr C, and the ratio of sums of rainfall and air temperature amounts to 0.5 for longer than 30 days in succession. The longest lasting drought (73 days) was registered in 1992.	Information by prof. Algimantas Česnulevičius (geographer)
Netherlands	Soil erosion	C	Relevant, but will mostly be local problems (and solutions) in parts of the Netherlands	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Netherlands	Soil organic carbon loss	B	Soil C storage is relevant in terms of climate mitigation and adaptation (soil quality), but carbon loss is not as large in NL as in other countries	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Netherlands	Nutrient imbalance	A	Better fertilizer use can prevent many problems of nutrient pollution in agriculture	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Netherlands	Soil acidification	D	There are solutions for this by liming	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Netherlands	Soil contamination	C	Not the biggest issue in NL, but relevant	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Netherlands	Waterlogging	C	Mostly local issues, and there are partial solutions for this with drainage	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Netherlands	Soil sealing	C	The agricultural area in the NL is declining, certainly since we have a big housing problem in NL and many houses are being built. But you can argue whether this is a problem of agricultural soil management, maybe this is more a problem on a higher level of governance. Depends on definition.	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Netherlands	Soil compaction	A	Big issue in NL	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Netherlands	Salinization	C	Mostly local issues (in NL), but getting bigger. In NL more a water issue instead of soil related.	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Netherlands	Loss of diversity	A	Will become more important in the (near) future	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Netherlands	Drought	C	Drought is an important threat, but we don't see this specific for soil, but more the whole farming system	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Poland	Soil erosion	B	Important issue for some regions of Poland	Expert workshop; survey for 2.5 EJP SOIL

Poland	Soil organic carbon loss	A	Important for monitoring of soil fertility and maintain C stock in organic soils	Expert workshop; survey for 2.5 EJP SOIL
Poland	Nutrient imbalance	D	Not relevant for Poland	Expert workshop
Poland	Soil acidification	A	Important for soil productivity and nutrients and trace elements availability	Expert workshop; survey for 2.5 EJP SOIL
Poland	Soil contamination	C	Relevant in hotspots; data are available	Expert workshop
Poland	Waterlogging	D	Not relevant for Poland	Expert workshop
Poland	Soil sealing	D	Not relevant for Poland	Expert workshop
Poland	Soil compaction	C	We do not have relevant data	Expert workshop
Poland	Salinization	D	Not relevant for Poland	Expert workshop
Poland	Loss of diversity	D	We do not have information	Expert workshop
Poland	Drought	A	Important issue for Poland; we have available data for mapping this soil threat	Expert workshop
Portugal	Soil erosion	A	Soil erosion by water in Portugal is a big concern. The trend towards shorter and more intense rainfall exacerbates the problem. Water erosion is more severe when periods of drought are broken by intense rain falling on bare or poorly vegetated and steeply-sloping soil surfaces.	Expert judgement, stakeholders surveyed for D2.5 EJP
Portugal	Soil organic carbon loss	A	Many soils in Portugal have already a low organic matter content.	Expert judgement, stakeholders surveyed for D2.5 EJP
Portugal	Nutrient imbalance	C	Associated with others threats, lack of data at national scale	Expert judgement
Portugal	Soil acidification	D	Not relevant for Portugal	Expert judgement, stakeholders surveyed for D2.5 EJP
Portugal	Soil contamination	C	Have some data available at national level, mainly for the heavy metals: Cr, Cu, Hg, Pb	Expert judgement, direct measurements: Cr, Cu, Hg, Pb
Portugal	Waterlogging	D	Not relevant for Portugal.	Expert judgement
Portugal	Soil sealing	D	Not relevant for Portugal	Expert judgement
Portugal	Soil compaction	C	Lack of data on national level	Expert judgement
Portugal	Salinization	B	The increasing need of irrigation in Portugal (and in all the south countries) may promote soil salinization. We can't forget that the irrigation water quality tends to deteriorate.	Expert judgement, stakeholders surveyed for D2.5 EJP
Portugal	Loss of diversity	C	Lack of data on national level	Expert judgement, stakeholders surveyed for D2.5 EJP

Portugal	Drought	B	With Mediterranean climate we deal with water shortage.	Expert judgement
Slovakia	Soil erosion	A	Important, especially for areas with higher slopes ; maps already available at the national scale (only on water erosion somehow)	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Slovakia	Soil organic carbon loss	A	Important for evaluation of soil quality, health, fertility, and role in mitigation of climate change	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Slovakia	Nutrient imbalance	C	Rather a problem in forest soils	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Slovakia	Soil acidification	B	Problem in forest soils and in naturally acidic agricultural soils	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Slovakia	Soil contamination	B	Relevant in hotspots; data are available	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Slovakia	Waterlogging	D	Mostly just a local problem	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Slovakia	Soil sealing	C	Expansion of cities on surrounding arable land	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Slovakia	Soil compaction	B	Important for some crops in agricultural soils	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Slovakia	Salinization	C	Mostly local issues	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Slovakia	Loss of diversity	D	We do not have information	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Slovakia	Drought	B	Factor limiting agricultural production in some years	Data inventarisation, stocktake, studies and needs from policy
Spain	Soil erosion	A	Due to the characteristics of the relief, the climate and the management practices of agricultural soils. Also to processes associated to agricultural land abandonment.	Expert judgement
Spain	Soil organic carbon loss	A	Erosion problems aggravate the loss of organic carbon, which affects the physical, chemical and biological deterioration of the soil.	Expert judgement

Spain	Nutrient imbalance	A	Agricultural soils are deficient in nutrients in an important part of the country, due to the physical characteristics of the territory, or they present an excess of them, due to management practices.	Expert judgement
Spain	Soil acidification	C	Only present in certain areas of the extreme north-west of the country.	Expert judgement
Spain	Soil contamination	B	Due to the use of fertilizers, pesticides, low-quality organic amendments, and industrial and urban discharges into channels used for irrigation. And diffuse pollution.	Expert judgement
Spain	Waterlogging	C	Located at the floodable margins of river courses.	Expert judgement
Spain	Soil sealing	A	Important soil sealing processes, which have been increased due to the expansion of the urban areas and the construction of second homes, due to tourist pressure since Spain is one of the destinations that receives the largest number of tourists in the world.	Expert judgement
Spain	Soil compaction	B	Due to the introduction on a significant scale of agricultural machinery, and also by surface crusting processes. Overgrazing and trampling in grasslands.	Expert judgement
Spain	Salinization	B	Present in certain agricultural landscapes of the country (South-East and Ebro Valley), due either to the properties of the soil, the low quality of irrigation water due to contamination of nitrates, chlorides and sulfates, or to the over-exploitation of aquifers and the consequent intrusion of seawater into irrigation wells.	Expert judgement
Spain	Loss of diversity	A	Due, among others, to the significant change in land use, the consequences of climate change, or the modification of the biogeochemical cycle.	Expert judgement
Spain	Drought	A	Dry periods are recurrent in Spain. Given that more than 60% of the country's water resources are used for agricultural land, years of drought are a priority issue in Spain. In October 2022, for example, the water reserve in the dams was only 32% of their capacity.	Expert judgement. Information provided by AEMET (Agencia Estatal de Meteorología)

Appendix A 2: Details of the prioritisation of the soil threats of the participating countries. Priority class for SERENA = A: very important and must definitely be discussed in SERENA; B: important, must preferably be discussed in SERENA; C: important, must preferably be discussed in SERENA and D: not important or not relevant and must not be prioritised in SERENA.

member state	soil ecosystem services	priority for SERENA	reason for priority class	approach and detail combined
Austria	Primary/biomass production	A	Important in Austria. Statistical data available.	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Austria	Habitat for biodiversity	B	SES of biodiversity still has to be studied. Few data available only at local/farm scale.	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Austria	Erosion control	A	Only a regional problem esp. in cropland	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Austria	Hydrological control	A	Data available, important for Austria	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Austria	Environmental pollution control	B	SES of environmental control, we rely on soils to purify our drinking water, the ground water is controlled regularly, the SES is important but we don't have explicit data on service	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Austria	Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	A	Very important, data already exist	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Austria	Pest and disease control	B	No data available.	Two stakeholder surveys (May and September 2022) and expert judgment from project partners (AGES; BAW and BFW)
Belgium	Primary/biomass production	A	Important in Belgium and data available	Expert workshop: national hub meeting with experts from administrations and statistical offices of different regions
Belgium	Habitat for biodiversity	B	Important but not many data and research already available	Expert workshop: national hub meeting with experts from administrations and statistical offices of different regions

Belgium	Erosion control	A	Important in Belgium and data available	Expert workshop: national hub meeting with experts from administrations and statistical offices of different regions
Belgium	Hydrological control	B	Important because the basis for a lot of soil functions, soil processes and soil ecosystem services	Expert workshop: national hub meeting with experts from administrations and statistical offices of different regions
Belgium	Environmental pollution control	D	In Belgium, soil pollution is seen rather under soil treat and not as an ecosystem service.	Expert workshop: national hub meeting with experts from administrations and statistical offices of different regions
Belgium	Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	A	Very important, involved in Carboseq (Flanders and Wallonia) and Sommit	Expert workshop: national hub meeting with experts from administrations and statistical offices of different regions
Belgium	Pest and disease control	C	More related to plant science.	Expert workshop: national hub meeting with experts from administrations and statistical offices of different regions
Czech	Primary/biomass production	A	Food production is very important task	Data inventarisation, studies and needs from policy
Czech	Habitat for biodiversity	B	Important, but not enough data available	Data inventarisation, studies and needs from policy
Czech	Erosion control	A	Erosion is the biggest problem in soil degradation	Data inventarisation, studies and needs from policy
Czech	Hydrological control	A	Drought is a problem in dry periods	Data inventarisation, studies and needs from policy
Czech	Environmental pollution control	B	Prevention of soil pollution is very important	Data inventarisation, studies and needs from policy
Czech	Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	B	Crucial issue, but not enough data	Data inventarisation, studies and needs from policy
Czech	Pest and disease control	C	Important, but not only a soil issue	Data inventarisation, studies and needs from policy
Denmark	Primary/biomass production	B	An important ecosystem service provided by agricultural soils	Expert assessment
Denmark	Habitat for biodiversity	C	Lack of soil biodiversity data on agricultural soils	Expert assessment
Denmark	Erosion control	C	The main concern in relation to erosion relates to leaching of nutrients into the aquatic environment. Farmers do not consider erosion as an important factor in relation to yield.	Expert assessment
Denmark	Hydrological control	A	Denmark depends on groundwater abstraction for drinking water purposes. Also leaching of nutrients to the aquatic environment is a threat	Expert assessment

Denmark	Environmental pollution control	A	This mainly relates to the soils ability as filter in relation to groundwater protection as well as eutrofication of the aquatic environment	Expert assessment
Denmark	Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	A	Organic soils are responsible for 50% of the total CO2 loss from the agricultural production	Expert assessment
Denmark	Pest and disease control	D	No known investigations of this. Not considered harmful	Expert assessment
Estonia	Primary/biomass production	A	Primary/biomass production is very important task in agriculture	Expert assessment
Estonia	Habitat for biodiversity	B	Important soil ecosystem service, but still rarely studied	Expert assessment
Estonia	Erosion control	B	Maintaining and developing erosion control considering water, wind and tillage is important for preventing soil degradation processes (e.g SOC and nutrient losses)	Expert assessment
Estonia	Hydrological control	A	Important soil ecosystem service considering the role of soils in the hydrological cycle.	Expert assessment
Estonia	Environmental pollution control	B	Environmental pollution control of soils is important, however the inclusion of this ES to analysis is rather scarce	Expert assessment
Estonia	Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	A	Important soil ecosystem service in European as well as national scale. The potential of soils in greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration should be soil-specifically clarified.	Expert assessment
Estonia	Pest and disease control	C	Not with high importance considering nationwide assessment in SERENA project	Expert assessment
France	Primary/biomass production	A	primary production in agricultural areas	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
France	Habitat for biodiversity	B	Should be done to be compared with "loss of biodiversity" threat	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
France	Erosion control	A	Important especially in the loessic region in Northern area of France, in the Mediterranean regions due to heavy climate events	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
France	Hydrological control	A	Very important to evaluate both the water provided to plants by soils, and the water transferred to groundwater	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants

France	Environmental pollution control	B	should be very important in non-agricultural areas due to industrial pollution, and in some agricultural areas due to diffusive pollution	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
France	Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	A	Very important to evaluate the ability of soil to store carbon, and to propose innovative agricultural practices which may mitigate climate change	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
France	Pest and disease control	B	Important especially in areas with agroecological practices to evaluate soil suppressiveness	Expert assessment from SERENA French participants
Hungary	Primary/biomass production	A	Essential for healthy and safe food production	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Hungary	Habitat for biodiversity	A	Soil biodiversity is important in organic matter decomposition	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Hungary	Erosion control	A	Maintaining and developing erosion control is essential, because erosion is one of the leading soil degradation processes in Hungary	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Hungary	Hydrological control	A	The role of soils in the hydrological cycle is essential	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Hungary	Environmental pollution control	B	The role of soils is basically important, however the assessment of this ES is problematic	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Hungary	Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	A	The role of soils in the control and mitigation of greenhouse gases and climate regulation is essential	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Hungary	Pest and disease control	B	The role of soils is basically important, however the assessment of this ES is problematic	Consultation with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Ireland	Primary/biomass production	B	Maintainance of productivity while improving other ESs	
Ireland	Habitat for biodiversity	B	Protection of habitats	
Ireland	Erosion control	B	Response to future changes in weather patterns	
Ireland	Hydrological control	A	Requirements to manage Hydrology through better soil management	
Ireland	Environmental pollution control	D		

Ireland	Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	A	35% of total GHGs from agriculture	
Ireland	Pest and disease control	D		
Italy	Primary/biomass production	A	One of the principal ES provided by agricultural soils	Workshops with stakeholders
Italy	Habitat for biodiversity	B	To be co-constructed with MINOTAUR	Workshops with stakeholders
Italy	Erosion control	B	Must be defined in SERENA; usually assessed jointly with erosion as threat	Workshops with stakeholders; survey for D2.5 EJP
Italy	Hydrological control	A	Highly relevant both for plain areas and hilly regions	Workshops with stakeholders
Italy	Environmental pollution control	A	Relevant for national and EU regulations	Workshops with stakeholders
Italy	Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	A	Agriculture as source and sink of GHGs	Workshops with stakeholders
Italy	Pest and disease control	C	Relevant for Farm-to-fork strategy; however, not enough knowledge and data to assess at National level	National strategy for Biodiversity 2030
Latvia	Primary/biomass production	B	Important for food production	consultation with relevant experts
Latvia	Habitat for biodiversity	B	Important for the protection of landscape biological diversity	consultation with relevant experts
Latvia	Erosion control	A	Intensification of agriculture and climate changes raises the importance of the soil erosion in Latvia	consultation with relevant experts
Latvia	Hydrological control	A	More than 60% of agriculture land is drained	consultation with relevant experts
Latvia	Environmental pollution control	C	Nutrient loss from agricultural lands	consultation with relevant experts
Latvia	Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	A	10% of area is peatlands	consultation with relevant experts
Latvia	Pest and disease control	D	Not relevant for Latvia	consultation with relevant experts
Lithuania	Primary/biomass production	A	Biomass production is important for soil C increase and soil fertility in general	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject

Lithuania	Habitat for biodiversity	B	Soil biological environment is related also to soil productivity and soil C turnover process	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Lithuania	Erosion control	A	Lithuania has recommendations and Code for Good Soil Management Practices to control soil erosion.	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Lithuania	Hydrological control	A	Soil water and its cycling within soil horizons and ground water is crucial for agricultural production	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Lithuania	Environmental pollution control	B	This is important on intensively managed soils	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Lithuania	Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	A	GHG emission is up to date important issue for Serena	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Lithuania	Pest and disease control	D	We do not use much pesticides per ha in Lithuania. This is a crop protection topic as concerns plant production and management. This is a hardly soil related topic for SERENA.	Workshops with relevant experts, researchers on the subject
Netherlands	Primary/biomass production	A	Very important, as this is the reason for agriculture	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Netherlands	Habitat for biodiversity	A	Important (soil) ecosystem service that stands under big pressure, in which agriculture plays a big role	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Netherlands	Erosion control	D	Not as important in NL, as in some other places. Can also be included in other services, like primary production, hydrological control and/or environmental pollution. Maybe also more a threat that can be solved than an ecosystem service (?)	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Netherlands	Hydrological control	A	Important soil ecosystem service, certainly in scope of climate change. Also much based on the local water management (drainage, canals, irrigation), so not only affected by the soil itself.	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Netherlands	Environmental pollution control	B	Mostly the cycling and pollution of nutrients is relevant in the scope of agriculture.	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Netherlands	Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	A	Important soil ecosystem service globally, look at positive sides of C sequestration, but also negatives like N ₂ O and CH ₄ emissions	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion

Netherlands	Pest and disease control	D	Important, but not relevant to name separately in our view. The effect of production will be included in primary production, the (functional) agrobiodiversity can be included in habitat for biodiversity.	Expert judgement, no elaborate discussion
Poland	Primary/biomass production	A	Important for food production chain	Expert workshop
Poland	Habitat for biodiversity	D	Data not available	Expert workshop
Poland	Erosion control	B	Important issue for some regions of Poland	Expert workshop
Poland	Hydrological control	A	In Poland we have several issues due to the water cycling: drought, local flooding, decrease of the area with a strong capacity of water storing (organic soils), locally - the problem of water erosion.	Expert workshop
Poland	Environmental pollution control	C	The pollution problem is local and the values of the content of organic pollutants and trace elements does not exceed the requirements according to the Polish law.	Expert workshop
Poland	Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	A	Important soil ecosystem service in the European and national scale as well. We have enough data for mapping and modelling this SES.	Expert workshop
Poland	Pest and disease control	D	Data not available	Expert workshop
Portugal	Primary/biomass production	A	Is the SES more important for agricultural soils	Expert judgement
Portugal	Habitat for biodiversity	C	Lack of soil biodiversity data on national level	Expert judgement
Portugal	Erosion control	A	As an ES, there is no data at national level. It is studied associated with soil erosion by water	Expert judgement
Portugal	Hydrological control	A	Very relevant for agricultural soils in the Mediterranean climate conditions	Expert judgement
Portugal	Environmental pollution control	C	It is an SES of environmental control and regulation. In our country we have data mostly for the concentration of nitrates in vulnerable agricultural regions and also the groundwater is controlled. We do not have data on the SES as a regulator for pollution.	Expert judgement

Portugal	Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	A	Lack of data at national level for agricultural soils, we have LULUCF at country level	Expert judgement
Portugal	Pest and disease control	C	Scarce information on national level referring to soil	Expert judgement
Slovakia	Primary/biomass production	A	Very important for food production chain	Expert judgement
Slovakia	Habitat for biodiversity	C	Lack of soil biodiversity data on national level	Expert judgement
Slovakia	Erosion control	A	Maintaining and developing erosion control is essential, because erosion is one of the leading soil degradation processes in Slovakia	Expert judgement
Slovakia	Hydrological control	A	The role of soils in the hydrological cycle is essential	Expert judgement
Slovakia	Environmental pollution control	B	Prevention of soil pollution is very important	Expert judgement
Slovakia	Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	A	Very important soil ecosystem service globally	Expert judgement
Slovakia	Pest and disease control	B	Data not available	Expert judgement
Spain	Primary/biomass production	A	Due to the extension of the agrarian sector in Spain, which affects the country's GDP; to the ancient tradition of dedication of the territory; to the impact that its abandonment presents in rural areas, among a long etcetera of reasons.	Expert judgement
Spain	Habitat for biodiversity	A	Its impact on the health of living organisms; due to the loss of genetic resources and their influence on biogeochemical cycles; the connectivity of landscapes, etc.	Expert judgement
Spain	Erosion control	A	Necessary to preserve soil and water resources, and productivity, in agricultural landscapes.	Expert judgement
Spain	Hydrological control	A	Due to off-site effects, to the deterioration of surface and groundwater.	Expert judgement
Spain	Environmental pollution control	A	Pollutants are deposited and distributed in the soil and in the water and this affects the entire trofic chain.	Expert judgement

Spain	Greenhouse gas and climate regulation/carbon sequestration	A	The ecosystems health depends on these important issues. Also changes occur in the functioning of the life cycle of crops and their efficiency in the use of nutrients and water; and, in general, in the soil functions.	Expert judgement
Spain	Pest and disease control	A	Its occurrence decreases agricultural production, even crops and the biodiversity associated with them decrease or even die off; soil microbial communities are affected, especially those related to roots (mycorrhizae, etc.)	Expert judgement

Appendix A 3 Workflow in task 2.2

- A. First step was an international review of reports, paper and relevant documents about soil threats and SES describing the soil threats, SES and bundles and their associated indicators. This was no systematic review but it includes 48 documents, reports and papers of soil threats; 44 of SES and 6 of bundles of soil threats and/or SES from local to European scale.
- B. Parallel a preliminary prioritisation of the soil threats and SES were conducted in the project member states. In some countries the prioritisation was discussed in stakeholder workshops, whereas in other an expert judgement was taken. The specific approach for the different project member states is given in the Appendix A 1 und Appendix A 2.
- C. This first exercise revealed discordance in the understanding of the assessed soil threats and SES among partners. Hence, an intensive discussion of the definitions, based on the definitions found in the reviewed literature (step A) was undertaken. Over several weeks all arguments and alternative definitions were collectively discussed online in a excel table. The results from this discussion were presented at a task workshop and those definitions of soil threats and SES which were still not clear were discussed and clarified in smaller groups.
- D. The definitions and information on the first selection of soil threats and SES with their associated indicators were submitted in the first milestone M2.2 from task 2.2 in M8. This milestone was the draft of this deliverable D2.2. Subchapters have been written by several authors. The project partner signed up as lead and co-authors for specific chapters and sub-chapters.
- E. The milestone report M2.2; draft of D.2.2) was reviewed by other project colleagues.
- F. During the review also other soil threats and SES were discussed and "Soil drought" was added to the list of soil threats.
- G. Project member states had time to revise their prioritisation due to the revised common harmonised definitions.
- H. Finally the chapter- and sub-chapter teams finalised this report D2.2 about soil threats and SES of interest in SERENA.

Over the process we had eight task meetings and the task leader and co-leader were present at the overall SERENA jour-fix to ensure a close collaboration with other tasks and WPs in the SERENA project.

Limitations:

All chapters have been written and reviewed by several project partners, however the expertise of the team are not covering all aspects to the same degree. Especially the little experience of bundles was a challenge.